

EXPLORING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ROAD TRAFFIC NOISE, AIR QUALITY AND HYPERTENSION

WISDOM KWESI ADZA

Thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements
of the University of the West of Scotland
for the award of Doctor of Philosophy

April 2023

Table of Contents

Abstract	<i>xi</i>
Declaration	<i>xii</i>
Acknowledgements	<i>xiii</i>
Terms and Definitions	<i>xiv</i>
Acronyms	<i>xvi</i>
Chapter 1	1
INTRODUCTION	1
1.1 Background to the study	1
1.2 Gap in Knowledge that will be filled and how that is done	8
1.3 Problem Statement.....	10
1.4 Aim	11
1.5 Objectives	11
1.6 Thesis Outline.....	12
Chapter 2	14
LITERATURE REVIEW	14
2.1 Noise pollution and exposure	14
2.2 Sources of noise.....	15
2.2.1 Environmental Noise.....	15
2.2.2 Social Noise.....	16
2.2.3 Occupational Noise	16
2.3 Types of environmental noise.....	17
2.3.1 Industrial Noise	17
2.3.2 Transport Noise	17
2.3.3 Neighbourhood noise	17
2.4 Recommended Standards for Noise Exposure	18
2.5 Effects of Environmental noise levels	20
2.5.1 Non-auditory effects of noise exposure	20

2.5.2 Auditory effect of noise exposure	22
2.6 Environmental noise, air pollution and their effects.....	24
2.7 Policies, Laws and Legislations of Noise and Air Pollution	32
2.7.1 Acoustics - Measurements of sound pressure levels released by stationary road vehicles (ISO 5130:2007+A1:2012)	33
2.7.2 Specification of test tracks for measuring noise output by road vehicles (ISO 10844:2014).....	34
2.7.3 Noise and Statutory Nuisance Act of 1993 & Environmental Protection Act of 1990.....	34
2.7.4 Anti-social Behaviour, Crime and Policing Act 2014 and Police Reform Act 2002	35
2.7.5 Regulation (EU) No. 540/2014	35
2.7.6 Regulation (EU) No. 168/2013	36
2.8 Air quality monitoring, managing and legislation.....	37
2.9 Road traffic, the use of peak hours, building typologies and morphological structures and their impact	44
2.10 Road traffic exposure to noise and air pollution related to Hypertension	48
2.11 Road traffic, noise pollution, air pollution and public health in communities	52
2.12 Using GIS to explore association between road traffic noise, air pollution with hypertension	55
2.13 Exploring the link between road traffic noise, air quality and public health– a review and perspective for a UK environmental health tracking system (EHTS)	59
2.14 Conceptual framework for an Environmental Health Tracking System that link road traffic noise and air pollution with hypertension.....	62
2.15 Application of DPSEEA framework as Surveillance to review links between noise and air pollution with hypertension	63
2.16 Driving force.....	63
2.17 Pressure.....	65
2.18 State	66
2.19 Exposure	67
2.20 Effect	69
2.21 Action	73
2.21.1 Implementation of Policy and legislation for environmental noise in the UK.....	73
2.21.2 Implementation of Policy and legislation for air quality in UK.....	74
2.21.3 Air quality network	76
2.22 Estimation of a standard for burden of disease.....	77
Chapter 3.....	81

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY	81
3.1 Selecting Suitable Research Methodologies.....	81
3.2 Methods	81
3.3 Study Design and Targeted Population	81
3.4 Data Source and Outcome	82
3.5 Source of Data	82
3.6 Primary Data.....	82
3.7 Secondary Data.....	82
3.8 Exposure assessment	93
3.8.1 Description of the study area.....	93
3.8.2 The specific location in Greater Glasgow	95
3.8.3 Method and classification of the count at a specific location	99
3.9 Data collection techniques.....	103
3.10 Noise Level Monitoring.....	109
3.10.1 Design of measurement.....	109
3.10.2 Sound meter and Personal dosimeter	109
3.10.3 Sound Meter Characteristics	110
3.10.4 Personal Dosimeter	111
3.11 Environmental Noise Data Collection and Modelling Approaches	112
3.11.1 Simulation of road traffic noise pollution	112
3.12 Air pollution Data Collection and Modelling Approaches.....	115
3.12.1 Modelling of Road Traffic Air Quality	116
3.13 Prevalence of Hypertension and Modelling Approaches	118
3.13.1 Modelling methodology for prevalence of hypertension	120
3.14 Canonical Correlation Methods.....	121
3.14.1 Two Sets of Categorical Variables.....	122
3.15 Analysis and presentation.....	123
3.16 Pre-testing.....	125
3.17 Expected results and dissemination.....	126
3.18 Ethical Approval.....	126
Chapter 4	127
RESULTS	127

4.1 Literature search results.....	127
4.2 Demographic background characteristics of respondents	130
4.2.1 Summary of background characteristics of respondents of SHeS Survey	130
4.3 Chi-square test of the difference between the two groups (Case group and Control).....	133
4.4 Prevalence and characteristics of hypertension	136
4.4.1 Medical History	136
4.5 Prevalence of hypertension among household's persons (those of the 5 sampling locations) and control group.....	138
4.6 Road Annual Daily Traffic Flow.....	141
4.7 Noise frequency range measurements at community study (Primary data).....	143
4.8 Geospatial results of data at five locations	145
4.9 A model of road traffic noise level(Lden) at five specific monitoring areas (23/11/2020).....	146
4.10 RELATIONSHIP OF NOISE LEVEL AT DIFFERENT PERIODS AND FREQUENCY COMPONENT USING TERNARY PLOT COORDINATES	158
4.11 Noise exposure period	163
4.11.1 Average noise level at different measured periods (primary data)	163
4.12 Multivariate Analysis and Scatter Matrix Analysis of Joint Air Concentration and Noise Level at Frequency Component Range with Hypertension Rate and Registered Hypertension Cases.....	165
4.13 Multiple Regression Analysis of Joint Air Concentration and Noise Level at Frequency Component Range with Registered Hypertension Cases	168
4.14 Proximity Measure for Attributes between Vectors of Values.....	173
4.15 Canonical correlation between noise at different frequency component and air concentration with hypertension register and hypertension rate	175
4.16 Multivariate analysis of factors influencing the hypertension among the respondents.....	177
4.17 Relationship between Years of Noise and Air pollution Exposure and Hypertension.....	181
Chapter 5.....	182
DISCUSSION	182
5.1 Background characteristics of respondents	182
5.2 Suitable conceptual framework as well as the application of the conceptual framework for an Environmental Health Tracking System that link road traffic noise and air pollution with hypertension.	184
5.3 Annual average residential exposure to air pollutant ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) and noise at different frequency components (low, mid and high) (Lden) and it association Using QGIS.....	185
5.4 Noise and air pollution exposure and prevalence of hypertension in the communities.	191

5.5 Joint relationship between air pollutant and noise level at different frequency components on hypertension rate and registered cases using QGIS.....	195
5.6 Associations between key factors such as age, gender, BMI and hypertension among.....	207
the exposed population	207
5.6.1 Relationship between gender and hypertension among respondents.....	207
5.6.2 Relationship between BMI and hypertension among respondents	210
5.6.3 Relationship between age and HBP among respondents	211
Chapter 6.....	213
CONCLUSIONS.....	213
Chapter 7.....	219
RECOMMENDATION, STRENGTH AND LIMITATION AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS.....	219
7.1 Recommendation.....	219
7.1.1 Government bodies (DEFRA, UKHSA).....	219
7.1.2 EPA	221
7.1.3 Communities and Local authorities.....	222
7.1.4 Household persons	222
7.2 Future direction.....	223
7.3 Strength and Limitation of study	223
References	228
Appendix	253
Operating procedure of Casella CEL-63x & 1/3 Octave Band Sound Level Meter.....	253
Operating procedure of Casella dBadge2 IS Pro Personal Noise Dosimeter.....	254

FIGURE

Figure 2:1:Boundaries Between Index Points for Each Pollutant Source:(DEFRA, 2020)	42
Figure 2:2: Modified DPSEEA framework for the assessment of the joint cause-effect relationship between road traffic noise, air pollution and hypertension (Adza et al, 2022)	64
Figure 2:3: Average number of people on agglomerations from UK exposed to noise from roads (Lden and Lnight) (Source: Transparency data, 2019).....	67
Figure 2:4: Total UK Road transport emissions 1990-2017(Source : Jones et al., 2019).....	68
Figure 3:1 : Directions of traffic flow at the monitoring locations.....	97
Figure 3:2 : Map of study area. The maps were created using the QGIS 3.24.3-Tisler software (Open Source Geospatial Foundation Project, Chicago, USA).....	98
Figure 3:3 : Position of sound meter and air monitor at monitoring sites.	99
Figure 3:4: Sound Meter instrument.....	110
Figure 3:5: Personal Noise dose meter instrument	112
Figure 4:1: Flowchart illustrating selections of studies included in this review using PRISMA diagram (Prisma, 2020).....	129
Figure 4:2: Annual daily traffic flow of the type of vehicles in various monitoring sites	141
Figure 4:3: Community noise levels (LAeq) measured at different frequency component at urban areas in central belt of Scotland (30/11/2020-3/03/2021).....	143
Figure 4:4: A model of road traffic annual average noise level (Lden) at monitoring areas at five monitoring locations (23 November 2021): (a) road traffic noise (Lden) at GHS, GK, and GT; (b) road traffic noise (Lden)at EDK; (c) road traffic noise (Lden) at EDB.	147
Figure 4:5: A model of annual road traffic noise levels (Lden) at monitoring areas at five monitoring locations (23 November 2021): (a) Community noise level (Lden)at GHS, GT, and GK; (b) Community noise level (Lden) at EDK; (c) Community noise level (Lden) at EDB.	149

Figure 4:6: Joint annual average NO ₂ , PM ₁₀ and PM _{2.5} concentration($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), and noise level (Lden) at five monitoring locations (23 November,2021): (a) Joint air- noise pollution (Lden)/($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) at GHS, GT and GK; (b) Joint air-noise pollution (Lden)/ ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) at EDB; (c) Joint air-noise pollution (Lden)/ ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) at EDK.	152
Figure 4:7: Joint annual average NO ₂ , PM ₁₀ , and PM _{2.5} concentrations ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) and noise level (Lden) at five monitoring locations (23 November 2021): (a) joint air–noise pollution and hypertension at GK, GT, and GHS; (b) joint air–noise pollution and hypertension at EDK; and (c) joint air–noise pollution and hypertension at EDB.....	156
Figure 4:8: Clustering map of air pollutant, noise level and hypertension register at Greater Glasgow in central belt of Scotland	157
Figure 4:9: Ternary plot using percentage of noise level at frequency component for each monitoring sites for each measured period.....	159
Figure 4:10: The magnitude of noise level at the three-frequency component (low, mid, and high) in all five monitoring sites.	162
Figure 4:11: Average noise exposure at different measured periods at five monitoring sites for respondents	163
Figure 4:12: Relationship of average noise level within different measured periods at five monitoring sites	164
Figure 4:13: Relationship between joint air concentration and noise level at different frequency component range and hypertension rate at the five monitoring sites: (a) Joint air-noise pollution (dBA)/($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) with hypertension rate at GT; (b) Joint air-noise pollution (dBA)/ ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) with hypertension rate at GK; (c) Joint air-noise pollution (dBA)/($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) with hypertension rate at EDB; (d) Joint air- noise pollution (dBA)/($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) with hypertension rate at GHS; (e) Joint air-noise pollution (Lden)/ ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) hypertension rate at EDK.	165

Figure 4:14: Relationship between joint air concentration and noise level at different frequency component range and registered hypertension cases at the five monitoring sites: (a) Joint air-noise pollution (dBA)/($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) with registered hypertension cases at EDB;..... 167

Figure 4:15: Linear regression of noise level at low, mid and high frequency component and air concentration of NO_2 , PM_{10} and $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ on hypertension register..... 169

Figure 4:16: A 3D scatterplot showing the correlation between air concentration and noise level at different frequency components and hypertension rate..... 172

Figure 4:17: Canonical correlation between joint noise at different frequency components combined with air concentration, registered hypertension cases, and hypertension rate. 176

Figure 4:18: Influence of years of noise and air pollution exposure on hypertension 181

TABLE

Table 2:1: Allowable Daily Exposures (Hours per Day) based on OSHA and NIOSH.....	18
Table 2:2: Non-auditory effects of noise exposure.....	20
Table 2:3 : Air Quality index analysis in the UK.....	41
Table 2:4: Components of conceptual frameworks linking environment and health Source (WHO, 2010)	62
Table 2:5: PAF for risk factors for all-cause YLLs rate per 100,000 population for England, Scotland, Wales, and Northern Ireland, both genders, 2016 (Source: Steel et al., 2018).....	70
Table 3:1: Summary of different data sources and origins.....	92
Table 3:2: Model and classification of the count at a specific location.....	101
Table 3:3: Vehicle classifications counted in the investigated areas.....	102
Table 3:4: Characteristics of analysed roads	102
Table 3:5: Parameters for creating a 3D scatterplot for the vector layers	121
Table 4:1: Gender, Age 16+ in 3 groups, Marital status - grouped, Current employment situation, household size and years of exposure.....	130
Table 4:2: Summary of background characteristics of respondents	133
Table 4:3: Medical history of respondents	136
Table 4:4: Prevalence of hypertension among various groups of respondents	138
Table 4:5: Relationship between household's environment and hypertension	139
Table 4:6: Relationship between household's environment and hypertension	140
Table 4:7: Spearman correlations between frequency components of road noise levels, air pollutants, and traffic flow rates.....	142
Table 4:8: Normality in distribution of annual noise levels(dB) at different frequency range in five monitoring sites (23/11/2020-24/11/2021).....	143
Table 4:9: Relationship between joint annual average road traffic noise frequency component and concentration of NO ₂ , PM ₁₀ and PM _{2.5} in all the five monitoring sites	144

Table 4:10: Relationship of noise level within the different frequency component.....	161
Table 4:11: Comparing of noise level at low, mid and high frequency component.....	162
Table 4:12: The regression coefficients of joint noise level at low-, mid-, and high-frequency components and air concentrations of NO ₂ , PM ₁₀ , and PM _{2.5} (µg/m ³) showing impact on registered hypertension cases	168
Table 4:13: The regression coefficients of joint noise level at low-, mid-, and high-frequency components and air concentrations of NO ₂ , PM ₁₀ , and PM _{2.5} µg/m ³ showing impact on hypertension rate.	170
Table 4:14: Correlation Matrix of noise level at low, mid and high frequency component and air concentration of NO ₂ , PM ₁₀ and PM _{2.5} µg/m ³	170
Table 4:15: Distance Correlation of vectors of values of joint noise level at different frequency component and air concentration and hypertension rate using proximity matrix	174
Table 4:16: Canonical correlation and Eigen values	175
Table 4:17: Variance and Eigen values	175
Table 4:18: Model Fitting Information.....	177
Table 4:19 : Likelihood Ratio Tests	177
Table 4:20: Model Fitting Information.....	178
Table 4:21: Likelihood Ratio Tests	178
Table 4:22: Model Fitting Information.....	179
Table 4:23: Likelihood Ratio Tests	179
Table 4:24: A logistics regression of influence of gender, age, body mass index and smoker status on hypertension.....	180

Abstract

Background: There is evidence that exposure to the air pollution and noise from transportation is associated with risk of hypertension. Most studies have, however, only looked at relationships between single exposures and hypertension.

Objective: To examine the combined association of outside air pollution and road noise with risk of hypertension.

Methods: Using a cross-sectional design, information from the Scottish National Health Survey (2020) involving 33932 adults was linked. The survey assessed information on hypertension using the self-reporting of doctor diagnosed hypertension to a separate information from the NHS Scotland database of 776,579 hypertension patients' registrations and rates per 13.80 people at the GP practice levels. Based on geospatial attributes, data on residential areas were added by modelling annual average air pollutant concentrations, including particulate matter (PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), and road-traffic noise at different frequency components (Lden) (23 November 2020–23 November 2021). The relationships between exposure to road noise, air pollution, and hypertension were examined using multiple regression and multivariate analysis.

Results: Traffic noise and air pollution at various frequency components were associated with both registered hypertension cases and hypertension rates. Based on the canonical loading technique, the variance explained by the canonical independent variable at a canonical correlation of 0.342 is 89%. There was a significant correlation between joint air pollution and noise at different frequency components and combined registered hypertension cases and hypertension rate. Based on Moran I autocorrelation, geographically close values of a variable on a map typically had comparable values when there is a positive spatial autocorrelation. This means clustering on the map was influenced significantly by NO₂, PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}, and Lden at most monitoring locations. Hypertension was significantly associated with PM₁₀, PM_{2.5} and NO₂ and Lden at all monitoring location.

Conclusion: Studies that only consider one of the two related exposures (outside air pollution and road noise) may exaggerate the impact of the individual exposure while underestimating the combined impact of the two environmental exposures.

Declaration

The research presented in this thesis was carried out by the undersigned. No part of the research has been submitted in support of an application for another degree or qualification at this or any other University.

Acknowledgements

I would like to express my utmost gratitude and warmest appreciation to my three supervisors: Prof. Andrew Hursthouse, Dr. Daniel Boakye and Mr. Jan Miller for their invaluable support and guidance throughout the entire course of the PhD. Without their patience, understanding and experience the thesis would not have been possible. Due to their highly approachable natures and encouragement, the project was very enjoyable and well driven.

I would like to thank some other faculty members at the University who were exceptionally helpful including: Mrs. Jane Tobias who assisted me greatly with the mental health Science aspect of the project, Dr. Collins Mathias, who provided invaluable advice and support.

I would also like to thank my office colleagues for providing a good working atmosphere including Dr. Fredrick Asiedu.

Finally, I would like to thank my parents Mr and Mrs Adza for their patience and support of everything I do. I would also like to thank my wife Christina Adza for her support and encouragement.

Terms and Definitions

Noise can also be defined according to physiological, acoustic, and electronic aspects as a signal whose intensity varies randomly and does not bear any information with time. Noise corresponds to unwanted sound but is a sensory perception.

Cardiovascular disease (CVD) is "all diseases affecting the heart and blood vessels found in the cardiovascular system."

Hypertension is simply defined as a usual increase in the pressure of blood vessels.

WHO (2019) defined the Lden (Day Evening Night Sound Level) as "the average sound level over 24 hours, with a penalty of 5 dB added for the evening hours or 19:00 to 22:00, and a penalty of 10 dB added for the nighttime hours of 22:00 to 07:00".

Lnight is simply a "night-time noise indicating average sound level over the 8-hour night period of 2300 - 0700 hours".

Disability-adjusted life years (DALYs) is defined as "the sum of the years of life lost to due to premature mortality (YLLs) and the years lived with a disability (YLDs) due to prevalent cases of the disease or health condition in a population."

Homogenous exposure groups (HEG) are defined as a group of people who experience similar exposure in such a way that the results of the evaluation of the direction of any people from the group are representative of the disclosure of all the other peoples in that group.

'LAeq' is the average sound level throughout measurement".

dB(A) is the *A-weighted* sound level in decibels.

Decibel (dB) is the standard physical unit for measuring sound level and noise exposure.

Environmental Health Tracking System (EHTS) is the ongoing collection, integration, analysis, interpretation, and dissemination of data from environmental monitoring and data from human exposure and health effects surveillance.

Acronyms

Leq	Weighted average continuous equivalent sound level
dB	Decibels
dBA	Average-weighted decibels
DW	Disability weight
EPA	Environmental Protection Agency
Hz	Hertz
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
SHeS	Scottish Health Survey
EPHSS	Environmental Public Health Surveillance System
SPL	Sound Pressure Level
SLM	Sound level meter
HEG	Homogenous exposure group
WHO	World Health Organization

Chapter 1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the study

According to the British Heart Foundation (Scarborough et al., 2011), a cardiovascular disease (CVD) refers to diseases affecting the heart and blood vessels. Several factors are associated with CVD risk, and they include family history, lifestyle factors (smoking, diet, physical inactivity, alcohol consumption, obesity) and medical history (diabetes and hypercholesterolaemia). CVD is the leading cause of deaths in the UK (Owen-Williams. (2020).

For the UK, data from a health survey estimating the prevalence of hypertension for areas in England revealed that about 11.8 million adults had hypertension, equating to 22.6% of the population (Forouzanfar, 2017; Scholes et al., 2020). The Scottish Public Health Observatory (ScotPHO, 2020) estimates that the risk of hypertension is high and can lead to significant morbidity. In 2019 the prevalence sharply increased among people aged 16 years and above (ScotPHO, 2020). Hypertension in Wales increased by 15.8% between 2018 and 2019 and is currently the most prevalent morbidity (Quality and Outcomes Framework Statistics for Wales (QOF), 2019). Nonetheless, according to the Northern Ireland Quality and Outcome Framework Statistics (QOF), the rate of hypertension is 14.0%, making it the most prevalent morbidity in Northern Ireland (QOF, 2020).

Noise and air pollution have detrimental health effects, as defined by WHO (WHO, 2019). The Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) goal 3 requires “ensuring healthy lives and promoting well-being for all ages.” Noise and air pollution are on the ascendency, and this has compelled several countries to develop regulations to govern them.

Diseases associated with PM_{2.5} have been linked to effects, including respiratory tuberculosis (TB) and malignant neoplasms of the trachea, bronchi, and lungs. The processes through which air pollution affect the risk of TB have been the subject of certain investigations. The immune system's resistance to oxidative stress is weakened by increased exposure to PM_{2.5}, which also makes the host more susceptible to tuberculosis (Nel, 2005). The remaining respiratory and cardiovascular system diseases include diabetes mellitus, ischemic heart disorders, pulmonary embolism, cerebral vascular diseases, pneumonia, acute lower respiratory infections, and chronic lower respiratory diseases (Mak et al., 2021).

Disorders such as pulmonary tuberculosis, malignant neoplasms of the trachea, bronchus, and lung, and lower respiratory diseases are related to NO_x traffic emissions (Mak et al., 2021).

Vehicle emissions, in many places, are the sources of nitrogen oxides (NO) and particulate matter (PM) (Zhang et al., 2013). Particularly close to large roadways, the severity and duration of traffic congestion can significantly increase pollutant emissions and worsen air quality (Zhang et al., 2013). According to this study, significant health hazards may be associated with congestion. Increasing traffic can significantly increase risks depending on the road style and other variables. Danger brought on by congestion must consider travel time, the length of rush hour, estimates of the emissions caused by the congestion, and uncertainty. These emissions raise the morbidity and mortality risks for motorists, commuters, and those close to roads (Zhang et al., 2013).

According to ENE (2020), potential adverse effects of noise pollution include annoyance, sleep disturbance, cardiovascular disease and cognitive impairment. Studies on road traffic and environmental noise have reported an association with auditory and wider health impacts such as hearing loss and cardiovascular related events such as myocardial infarction, hypertension, stroke and heart failure (ENE, 2020).

The European Environmental Agency (EEA) and the Environmental Noise in Europe (ENE, 2020) identified that urbanization, economic development activities (e.g., transport development of road lanes, increase in traffic and high construction and extension of cities) were the main drivers for the increase in environmental noise in 2020. The most common type of environmental noise among other sources is road traffic noise.

A conceptual framework model for environmental health tracking gives a systematic procedure that aids in the collection of factors and to examine issues linked to actual or predicted environmental health relationships (Eisenberg et al., 2007; McGeehin et al., 2004; Kyle et al., 2006; Edokpolo et al., 2019; Frank et al., 2019 and Harwell et al., 2019). Furthermore, conceptual frameworks can join separate monitoring plan of action and assist development of new indicators, policies, legislation and plan of action (Niemeijer et al., 2008; Eriksson et al., 2017). Most common evaluations of conceptual frameworks were found to focus on five approaches: Driving Force-Pressure-State Exposure-Effect-Action (DPSEEA), Pressure-State-Response (PSR), Force-Pressure-State-Impact-Response (DPSIR), Multiple Exposures Multiple Effects (MEME) and Integrated Environmental Health Impact Assessment (IEHIA). Environmental public health tracking (EPHT), according to the UK Health Security Agency (UKHSA), is the use of public health data to assist in the management of threats that are both environmental and other. As part of its specialised responsibilities, EPHT gathers, compiles, and analyses environmental health data to help guide measures aimed at lowering the burden of disease (UKHSA, 2022).

Urbanisation, which contributes to noise and air pollution, is growing. Between 2007 and 2017 it increased by 55.4% in the UK (Coates et al., 2019).

Road traffic noise and air-pollution generates considerable interest due to increase in economic and social activities in most cities that are densely populated, especially the urban areas of the UK (EEA, 2006). The transport sector is the largest source of noise

and air emissions in urban environments. Studies from the US have shown that urban areas are polluted by high frequency of noise in association with air pollution and that high car traffic volumes correlate positively with high frequency noise and air pollution, especially at night-time (Ross et al., 2011). Environmental noise from road traffic is also the target of many campaign groups in UK due to the relative air emissions, and road traffic noise and air pollution have a strong correlation (Davies et al., 2009).

Despite the potential adverse effects of noise and air pollution on health, it is anticipated that the next decade will see increase transport of vehicle with passengers more than 8.3 billion affecting remarkable features of Great Britain in both residential areas and commercial/business districts (TSGB, 2019).

It is significant to acknowledge the caveat on the increase in transportation and passengers as COVID restrictions has change peoples' habits and work practices.

According to statutory requirements (Barnes et al., 2015), the UK Government leads on the UK's input to International and European legislation relating to air quality, with input from the Scottish Government, and the other devolved administrations. Linking to the requirements of the EU Directives, the latest Air Quality Strategy published in July 2007 (DEFRA, 2007) established the framework for air quality improvements across the UK. Measures agreed at the national and international level are the foundations on which the strategy is based. The strategy sets out the Air Quality Standards and Objectives which have been set to benchmark air quality in terms of protecting human health and the environment. However, air quality is a devolved matter within the UK, with the Scottish Government having responsibility for the development of air quality policy and legislation for Scotland and other regions with similar responsibilities.

In the UK, a network of monitoring stations focuses on a range of six major air pollutants (COMEAP, 2009; COMEAP, 2011) that include ozone, carbon monoxide (CO), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), sulphur dioxide (SO₃), fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}),

coarse particulate matter (PM₁₀), and nitrogen dioxide (O₃). To publish air quality levels that combine these pollutants, DEFRA utilises a specific UK air quality measure called the “Daily Air Quality Index” (DAQI). On a scale of 1 to 10, the DAQI rates air quality, with 1–3 representing “Low”, 4–6 denotes “Moderate”, 7–9 denotes “High”, and 10 denotes “Very High” (COMEAP, 2009; COMEAP, 2010; COMEAP, 2011).

Emissions of nitrogen dioxide, carbon monoxide, and particulate matter (PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}) emissions from road transport have fallen by 77 % (4.5 million tonnes, 16,000 tonnes and 17,000 tonnes respectively) between 1990 and 2017 but high levels of air pollutant still exist (Jones et al., 2019). Between 1970 and the late 2000s, levels of both pollutants generally fell year over year. There are numerous factors contributing to this long-term decline in emissions across most emission sectors, but the burning of less coal and tighter emission regulations for industrial and transportation activities are the main ones. Annual emissions of particulate matter have varied from year to year since the late 2000s. Significant increases in emissions from burning solid fuels in industry (especially the burning of biomass) and home wood burning have more than offset significant declines in emissions from other industries (Jones et al., 2019). Road traffic will continue to be a significant source of PM emissions (12% of PM₁₀ and 13% of PM_{2.5} in 2017). Due to stronger emissions rules, exhaust emissions have significantly fallen since 1996 (by 90% for both PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}). Between 1996 and 2017, non-exhaust road emissions, such as brake, tyre, and road wear, accounted for 10% of PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} emissions and stayed practically unchanged (8 and 9% lower for PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}, respectively). Following more strict exhaust emission standards, emissions of numerous pollutants that are particularly harmful to human health (such as carbon monoxide, particulate matter, and nitrogen oxides) have decreased. As the UK strives to achieve net zero emissions by 2050, reducing emissions from road transportation remains a serious problem; as of the end of 2018, 0.5% of all vehicles permitted in the UK were ultra-low emission vehicles. From 255 billion miles driven on British roads

in 1990 to 328 billion miles in 2018, there was a 29% rise. Due to newer vehicles' higher fuel efficiency, the total amount of fuel used for road transport in the UK remained largely consistent between 1990 and 2017. While gasoline consumption decreased throughout this time, diesel use climbed.

Currently, the cities are considered the most polluted environments because of their high population densities set to become a vital factor in dominating private transport in public road traffic (Department for Transportation (DfT), 2019).

A city Member of the Scottish Parliament (MSP) dubbed the M8 highway through Glasgow as a "threat to public health" due to noise pollution generated by vehicles (Kelly, 2021).

According to a "noise map" published by the Scottish Government (TNAP, 2019), the M8 generates more than 80 dB on average, comparable to the runway at Glasgow Airport. After long term exposure to road-traffic noise with LAeq, 24h values of 65-70dBA, cardiovascular consequences have also been shown. There may be a higher risk of hearing loss from short-term exposure to noise with LAeq at levels higher than 80 dBA. Additionally, noise exceeding 80dBA may decrease prosocial behaviours and promote annoyance (WHO, 2018). Afterwards, its construction in 1970, the part of the motorway that passes through Charing Cross, Anderston, and Cowcaddens has sparked debate due to the destruction it caused at the time and the pollution it has generated since. City officials have drawn up proposals to limit the M8 where it runs beneath the landmark Mitchell Library, but one MSP believes they are insufficient. Add to that the city's pollution and decay. It is undeniably a severe threat to Glaswegians' physical and psychological well-being. According to the MSP, since 2015, Glasgow City Council has proposed a partial cap over the M8 canyon between Charing Cross and Bath Street, but this is insufficient to address the magnitude of the problem (Kelly, 2021). When improving pollution, the motorway canyon is covered from Charing Cross to St Vincent Street and from Charing Cross to Great Western Road north of Charing Cross. Road

improvement would significantly lessen the severe noise and air pollution it produces daily in central Glasgow while freeing up millions of square feet of publicly held excellent real estate (Kelly, 2021). In 2021, a public petition urging the Scottish Government to "explore possibilities for removing and minimising the impact of the central Glasgow part of the M8" received over 1,570 signatures (Kelly, 2021). The civic involvement committee of Holyrood will be debating it later this year.

However, the Scottish Government has identified that noise and air pollution from significant highways can influence the quality of life and our natural environment. They are striving to address these issues.

Therefore, the transportation noise action plan by the Scottish Government is adopting a range of activities to decrease transport noise, including the consideration of particular noise management measures at issue spots on the trunk road network."

The association between environmental noise and air pollution needs to be assessed to allow reliable action planning if threshold limits are exceeded (Murphy et al., 2010 and Beattie et al., 2015). In New York, a study conducted on the association of noise level and constituent air pollutants showed that noise threshold limit was exceeded. The constituent air pollutant includes nitrogen oxides and particle pollution (also known as particulate matter). There was an association between traffic, noise, and air pollution from combustion between intraurban areas suggesting confounding evidence impacting on epidemiological studies of health-related traffic issues (Kheirbek et al., 2014).

Regarding this, this research aims at using noise and air quality mapping to better understand how road traffic air and noise pollution link in space and identify their combined association with prevalence of hypertension among community households.

1.2 Gap in Knowledge that will be filled and how that is done

The current situation on prevalence of hypertension associated to noise and air pollution is something that needs a critical look. The joint association between road traffic noise at various frequencies and air pollution, however, is not well understood. However, a research gap exists between the combined association of road traffic noise and air pollution with hypertension in the UK. Many studies of the genesis of hypertension have been conducted in many parts of the world, both developed and developing; Even though cohort studies are ongoing in European countries to assess issues related to traffic noise and air pollution exposures. Both road traffic noise and air pollution may be associated with hypertension, but mechanisms may differ (Babisch et al., 2014; Pitchika et al., 2017; Fuks et al., 2017; Sears et al., 2018). The joint relationship between road traffic noise at various frequencies and air pollution, however, is not well understood (Chang et al., 2019).

However, the magnitude of this research remains relatively small in UK despite the attention given to environmental problem such as air and noise pollution. Review of national and regional health problems touch only briefly on hypertension. In situations where researchers are conducted in these areas, they only cover a limited range of urban communities and problems relating to the availability, validity and completeness of data. Evidence testing the combined association of noise and air pollution with hypertension is limited (Van et al., 2012; Gan et al., 2012; Tétreault et al., 2013; Floud et al., 2013 and Clark, 2015). There is thus a need for more acceptable data that can help bridge the gap especially in UK.

Understanding the association between these pollutants and their joint effects on human health are essential for developing population-based policies for further improving health outcomes.

This can be explored by analysing combined associations between modelled noise levels at various frequency components and air pollution utilising other spatial units

and area attributes, this study explores this using GIS models. The research will contribute to knowledge through GIS modelling in the epidemiological field related to environmental noise, air pollution and hypertension. GIS model can better be used to create an informative spatial visualisation from this data and joint association to evaluate potential links to health outcome indicators. This approach can address the links between combined noise pollution and air pollution with hypertension cases and rate. It will help future needs and development. It will help deepen awareness on hypertension among community households. Since, much is not known about the effects or specific effects this has on the individual as well as the whole populace. Since the true size of the problem is not accurately known, there is a low level of political will to deal with the situation. This study will clearly show the size of the problem to raise awareness among opinion leaders, decision makers and the public about the prevalence of hypertension among community household persons in such settings. These could be justified on several grounds. Additionally, there are no general conceptual framework model available in the literature that link the joint cause-effect of road traffic air and noise pollution in association with hypertension for an environmental health tracking system (EHTS) for UK. The study will formulate generalized conceptual framework model linking joint cause-effect of road traffic air-noise pollution with hypertension.

It is therefore relevant to embark on a study of this kind to contribute additional knowledge to the exposure of high levels of noise and air pollution, estimating the magnitude of noise pollution quantitatively. A single noise and air pollutant exposure may result in hypertension when road traffic noise and air pollutant add up over time. Therefore, this study will help community persons recognize the importance and value of avoiding noise and air pollutant exposure and accepting of valuable risk of hypertension. This study will help prevent hypertension among community households which would enable them to contribute their quota towards national development. This is because when people are healthy it affects their productivity level.

1.3 Problem Statement

Road traffic noise studies have reported an association with cardiovascular-related problems such as hypertension (Chang et al., 2019; Chang et al., 2014). Deteriorating air quality is a major problem in many nations. Significant pollution issues still challenge Scotland and the wider UK in general (AQMA, 2015).

It has been suggested that the risk of hypertension in European regions may be related to environmental noise and air pollution. Potential and established risk factors for hypertension include age, family history, smoking and physical inactivity (Scarborough et al., 2011). A probable reason for the hypertension cases in communities could be the presence of combined road traffic noise at various frequencies and air pollution. The consequences of the presence of exposure to different traffic noise frequency ranges and air pollution also present additional problems which include CVD, hypertension, auditory health complications, acoustic nuisance to persons within the community and violation of local byelaws, national and international laws and regulations on noise and air quality.

It is not yet clear whether the impact of environmental noise related to hypertension is independent, additive, or synergistic to the effect of air pollution. Studies show that it has no noise control and vice versa, but it is established that there are strong associations with health implications.

Furthermore, the foregoing review of literature has also shown that most studies just consider one of these two associated exposures. The effect arising from such studies also pose the danger of overstating the effect of hypertension because of the analysed exposure while underestimating the overall impact of the combined environmental exposures. Another important reason for targeting community household in urban area with major road is because of the prevalence of hypertension cases and rate reported to

NHS at GP level. This is evident in records obtain from NHS Scotland Database (SPIRE). The database includes all hypertension registers and hypertension rates covered by hospitals nationwide as part of the disease prevalence at GP offices in Scotland. Data on disease prevalence at GP offices in Scotland, ISD, February 2020.

In summary, the study identifies three research issues:

1. A research knowledge gap in using GIS model to evaluate the combined association between air pollutant and noise at different frequency components with hypertension.
2. A lack of public health conceptual framework models available in the literature that provide the opportunity to link road traffic noise and air pollution with hypertension.
3. Age, gender, and other health factors are not sufficient for estimating the risk of hypertension

It is hypothesized that, there is a link between road traffic noise with air pollutant and an increased chance of hypertension cases and rate.

1.4 Aim

The main aim of this project is to assess the relationship between combined road traffic noise levels at different frequency components and air pollution with hypertension.

1.5 Objectives

1. To determine the suitability of the conceptual framework as well as demonstrating the application of the conceptual framework for an Environmental Health Tracking System (EHTS) that link joint road traffic noise and air pollutants with hypertension.
2. To ascertain the annual average residential exposure to certain levels of NO₂, PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} pollutants ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) and community noise (Lden), at five different locations in urban Glasgow.

3. To obtain and interrogate primary data of community noise and secondary data using DEFRA, NHS Scotland and UK Data Service databases to investigate the inter and intra associations of air pollution, noise pollution and hypertension.
4. Use QGIS to explore the joint association of air concentration and noise levels at different frequency components with hypertension rate and cases registered.
5. To establish associations between key factors such as age, gender, BMI and hypertension among the exposed population.

1.6 Thesis Outline

The thesis is split into a further seven chapters, as follows:

Chapter one describes the background of the study and statement of the problem of the research. It shows details of the research objectives; the formation of the research questions; significance of the study; the problems associated with road traffic noise, air quality and hypertension.

Chapter two review literature exploring the link between road traffic noise, air quality and public health and identify some previous empirical evidence using the conceptual framework of DPSEEA. This study concludes and discuss the synthesised evidence. The DPSEEA conceptual framework provides an effective review method to conduct data surveillance monitoring and assessment and tracking outcomes more effectively with different types of empirical evidence in the field of environmental public health and epidemiology.

Chapter three discuss methods used to assess noise and air concentrations and the prevalence of hypertension. This chapter discusses methods used to collect data, study design, description of the study area and specific location in Greater Glasgow, were deployed. This chapter describes techniques of measurement using Casella Cel-63x and Casella dbadge2. It shows details of simulating and modelling of noise and air pollution from road traffic. The chapter identify some of the techniques for collecting data on the prevalence of hypertension. All data collected was discussed under statistical analysis

and presentation. The chapter shows description of pre-testing, expected results and dissemination.

Chapter four presents the results of three surveys performed in the central belt of Scotland on noise pollution and air pollutants on road traffic with a prevalence of hypertension in communities.

The discussion of results is identified in the fifth chapter.

The conclusion of research findings will be in the sixth chapter.

Finally, chapter seven discuss recommendation, limitation, and future direction of research.

Chapter 2

LITERATURE REVIEW

This chapter reviews relevant literature on the topic under study. For easy reference and better understanding, the literature was reviewed under the following headings: Noise pollution and exposure, Sources of noise, Types of environmental noise, Recommended Standards for Noise Exposure, Effects of Environmental noise levels, Environmental noise, air pollution and their effects, Policies, Laws and Legislations of Noise and Air Pollution, Air quality monitoring, managing and legislation, Road traffic, the use of peak hours, building typologies and morphological structures and their impact, Road traffic exposure to noise and air pollution related to Hypertension, Road traffic, noise pollution, air pollution and public health in communities, Using GIS to explore association between road traffic noise, air pollution with hypertension and Exploring the link between road traffic noise, air quality and public health– a review and perspective for a UK environmental health tracking system (EHTS)

2.1 Noise pollution and exposure

Noise can define as a complex sound with little or no periodicity (WHO, 2015). We can measure or analyse its characteristics. Noise, according to physiological, acoustic, and electronic aspects, is a signal whose intensity varies randomly and does not bear any information with time. Sound and noise have no difference in terms of their physical part, and noise corresponds to unwanted sound but is a sensory perception. Like any sound, we can describe every noise as intermittent, impulsive, explosive and even continuous. We consider noise in terms of sound pressure level (SPL) expressed in decibel (dB) and measured in hertz in terms of the frequency spectrum (Hz).

An important classification of noise is impulse and impact noise. Impact noise is the acoustic phenomena produced by two complex objects 'barging' together. Measuring

noise impact is at the maximum amplitude and duration. We can only estimate the amplitude of impact noise at the maximum amplitude peak, and the period in the time it takes for the wave to decay 20 dB from its peak level. On the other hand, Impulse noise is the acoustic phenomenon associated with explosions. The amplitude of the initial overpressure describes the waveform of impulse and the duration of time required for the decay of the peak pressure to the ambient pressure level.

Noise pollution is perhaps a shared community and environmental hazard linked to urbanisation. Yet, the impact of noise on health is mostly not given to many audiences (Moela, 2010). Studies have proven that prolonged exposure to excessive sound produces physical and psychological damage (Chowdhury, Razzaque, Helali, & Boden, 2010). The intensity and the duration of noise exposure determine the potential for damage to the hair cells of the inner ear. Noise can cause permanent hearing loss at chronic exposures equal to an average SPL of 85 dB (A) or higher for eight hours. Four hours of noise exposure at 88 dB(A) and one hour at 94dB(A) is the same noise "dose" as eight hours at 85 dB(A).

Very high levels may cause damage after relatively short periods, even when the noise is intermittent. Hearing loss may frequently find people firing guns as an occasional hobby, as well as in people who are exposed to the noise of lower levels but more constant, such as those working on construction sites or in other industrial locations such as mines and airports (Aguis, 2006).

2.2 Sources of noise

2.2.1 Environmental Noise

A pollutant agent should be present for enough time and under conditions that interfere with people's health and comfort. This pollutant agent link to one of the main concepts in toxicology: the dose. Paracelsus, who stated: "Dosis sola" facit venenum", i.e., all

substances are potentially harmful, depending on how much they reach and act on the receiver (Albert, 1997).

In this same vein, exposure to environmental noise for prolonged periods can cause serious health issues for humans and animals. Exposure to high levels of noise is said to be ecological exposure. It refers to a non-wanted direction related to sounds/noises that reach the place where the receiver is, e.g. traffic noise, music from stores, or neighbourhood noises, which the receiver cannot reject. If the person should stay in that place, this exposure will be non-avoidable (González, 2014).

2.2.2 Social Noise

Social noise exposure is noise chosen by the receiver. It involves voluntary attendance in noisy places as well as the "consumption" (in a broad sense) of high levels of sound, e.g. the use of personal music devices at high volume, the listening to loud music, the practice of sports like shooting, as well as other noisy activities (Gonzalez, 2012).

2.2.3 Occupational Noise

The concept of "dose of noise" is usually applied to assess occupational noise exposure and it is expressed as a percentage. Thus, a 100% dose is the maximum acoustic energy that a worker may receive during a working day. Any exceedance on exposure is an overdose, i.e., a dose of noise greater than 100% (González, 2014). Occupational hearing loss resulting from exposure to high noise levels depends not only on exposure time but also on the frequency, intensity, and the type of noise (continuous or impact) (Ahmedf et al., 2001).

The workplace is demarcated and identified by a notice indicating that the relevant area is a noise zone when noise exceed limit. Therefore, workers must wear devices for protection. The appropriate mandatory symbolic safety sign for hearing protection is put in a conspicuous place at all entrances to and exits from such areas. Also, only persons wearing suitable hearing protection devices are allowed into such areas. (Pathology & Humanities, 2013).

Noise-induced hearing loss (NIHL) is very costly. Approximately 100 million dollars are paid annually for compensation in Sweden (Ivarsson et al., 1992). According to the legislation, routine audiometric tests and medical examinations are compulsory and should occur annually (Pathology & Humanities, 2013).

2.3 Types of environmental noise

2.3.1 Industrial Noise

It is sound with a high-intensity sound caused by industry machines. Sources of such noise pollution are generated by machines from machines in various factories, industries, and mills. Noise from mechanical saws and pneumatic drills is unbearable and a nuisance to the public (Atmaca et al., 2005). According to reports, increasing industrial pollution damages the hearing ability by at least 20%. Workers in the steel industry, who work close to heavy industrial blowers, are exposed to 112dB for eight hours and suffer from occupational pollution.

2.3.2 Transport Noise

Transport noise mainly consists of traffic noise from the road, rail and aircraft. The number of automobiles on roads like motors, scooters, cars, motorcycles, buses, trucks and diesel engine vehicles have increased enormously in the recent past, further aggravating the problem of transport noise (Babisch, 2006).

Noise levels in most residential areas in metropolitan cities are hovering around the borderline due to increased vehicular noise pollution. This high level of noise pollution leads to hypertension in the elderly (Babisch, 2006).

2.3.3 Neighbourhood noise

This type of noise includes disturbance from household gadgets and the community. Familiar sources include musical instruments, TV, VCR, Radios, Transistors, Telephones, loudspeakers etc. Statistically, ever since the industrial revolution noise in environment has been doubling every ten years (Berglund et al., 1999).

2.4 Recommended Standards for Noise Exposure

There are two recommended standards on noise dose defined by the USA: the National Institute for Occupational Safety and Health (NIOSH) criteria for recommended standard (NIOSH, 1998) and Occupational Safety and Health Administration (OSHA) Occupational Noise Standard (OSHA, 1983)

NIOSH re-evaluated the recommended exposure limit (REL) for occupational noise exposure and affirmed support for 85-dBA REL in 1998. Based on scientific evidence, NIOSH recommends a 3-dB exchange rate (Murphy & Franks, 2002). The more conservative NIOSH criteria rely on scientific data relating noise levels to the risk of hearing damage and are more protective of hearing than OSHA criteria. OSHA allow for higher and more extended exposure periods.

Table 2:1: Allowable Daily Exposures (Hours per Day) based on OSHA and NIOSH

Noise level (dBA)	85	88	90	92	94	95	97	100
OSHA	16		8	6		4	3	2
NIOSH	8	4			1	$\frac{3}{4}$	$\frac{1}{2}$	$\frac{1}{4}$

The EPA Act 1994 (Act 490) mandates the agency to prescribe standards and guidelines relating to the pollution of air, water, land, noise and in pursuance of this mandate, the agency has developed permissible noise level guidelines to regulate the level of noise within the environment," he stated"

The environmental agency puts permissible ambient noise levels in residential 55 decibels (dB) during the day and 48 dB at night. The agency set permissible ambient noise levels at 55 dB during the day and 50 dB at night for educational health facilities, while the noise level for areas with commercial or light industrial activities was

registered at 60 dB and 55 dB during the day and night, respectively. The guidelines also permit 65 dB noise levels during the day and 60 dB during the night for light industrial areas and places of entertainment and public assembly such as churches and mosques (EPA, 2011).

Predominant commercial areas are allowed 70 dB during the day and 65 dB at night, while the noise level for heavy industrial areas are allowed at 70 dB during the day and night.

The allowed noise level in A-weighted decibels (the unit used to assess environmental noise) is:

Daytime (7 a.m. to 19 a.m.) 41 dB

Evening (between 19:00 and 23:00) 37 dB

31 dB during the night (from 23:00 to 7:00 a.m.)

If the underlying noise level is less than 24 dBA, the decibel level is 34 dBA (decibels corrected).

If the noise level is more than 24 dBA, increase the volume by ten dBA. According to (DEFRA, 2007), we should consider the proper amounts at different times of the day. It proven that we can introduce scientifically measured levels, if violated at any moment during the day, will result in a conviction-able offence. The objectively measured intervention levels for the day, evening, and night are 41dB, 37dB, and 31dB, respectively. The LAeq, 5min, is the parameter to utilise.

If the underlying noise level is less than 21dB between 23.00 and 07.00 (night), 27dB between 19.00 and 23.00 (evening), and 31dB between 07.00 and 19.00 (day), the allowable levels are 31dB, 37dB, and 41dB for each of the noise control times.

Having studied noise levels into context, 40dB is the sound of a refrigerator buzzing from two metres away. Theses settings cannot be used where the background

(underlying) noise level is high, such as in town. In these situations, the noise level should not surpass the background level by more than 10 decibels.

When considering noise levels for planning new roads or dwellings and offices near routes there is no legal restriction on traffic noise.

Drop-sided vehicles generate noise at 40-50 Hz range, primarily due to exhaust noise. The legal noise limit for a car exhaust in the United Kingdom is 82dB. Due to exhaust and body vibration, HGVs have two frequency peaks: 63 Hz and 630 Hz. At 30 mph, the average automobile produces 62 dB, and at 50 mph, a vehicle emits 70 dB.

Noise produced by cruiser bikes (such as Harley Davidson) is primarily in the 100-400 Hz band. $L_{max} = 84.8$ dB. Mopeds and scooters dominate the 1000-2000 Hz frequency band, which spans 200-5000 Hz. $L_{max} = 62.3$ dB.

Sports bikes have a flat spectrum in the 125-8000 Hz range. $L_{max} = 78.3$ dB.

2.5 Effects of Environmental noise levels

Noise exposure has two main effects; auditory and non-auditory (Gaganija et al., 2011).

The acoustic effects are mainly ONIHL and tinnitus (ringing in the ear). The non-auditory results are below.

2.5.1 Non-auditory effects of noise exposure

Table 2:2: Non-auditory effects of noise exposure

Physical effects	Increased cardiovascular risk Fatigue and sleeplessness Impaired communication High accidents and injury risks.
Psychological and social effects	Annoyance Depression Memory loss Reduced quality of life

	Social isolation and stigmatization and self-esteem.
Economic effects	Increased absenteeism Reduced productivity and performance Employment and income disruption

Source: Gaganija et al. (2011)

Noise pollution affects both human and animal health. It leads to the contraction of blood vessels. They are making skin pale excessive adrenalin in the bloodstream, which is responsible for high blood pressure. Blaring sounds causes mental distress, heart attacks, neurological problems, congenital disabilities, and muscle contraction causing nervous breakdown, tension, etc. The adverse reactions cause change in the hormone content of blood, which in turn increases heartbeat, constriction of blood vessels, digestive spasms, and dilation of the pupil of the eye. Adverse effects on health, work efficiency and behaviour. Noise pollution may cause damage to the heart, brain, kidneys, liver and produce emotional disturbance. The acute effect of noise is hearing loss, affecting some part of the auditory system. Prolonged noise exposure to frequency patterns leads to chronic damage to the inner ear. Impulse noise may cause psychological and pathological disorders (Gaganija et al., 2011). Ultrasonic sound can affect the semi-circular canals of internal ear, respiratory, digestive and cardiovascular system. The brain is adversely affected by loud noise by jets and aeroplanes. People are subject to psychiatric illness. Recent reports suggest that blood is thickened by excess noise. The optical system of human beings is also affected by noise pollution. Severe noise pollution causes pupillary dilation, impairment of night vision and a decrease in the rate of colour perception (Gaganija et al., 2011).

2.5.2 Auditory effect of noise exposure

Noise-induced hearing loss has been listed as the third epidemic disease worldwide. It can cause physiological and psychological dysfunction (Yuen, 2014) and is the most common cause of tinnitus (Axelsson et al., 2000). In the early stage, it is complicated to diagnose the occupational health diseases as they often have a long latency period, most workers are affected through high noise level (Ashrafi, 2005).

Hearing loss caused by noise exposure due to recreational or non-occupational activities is called sociocosis. Hearing loss due to injurious noise at work is known as occupational noise-induced hearing loss (ONIHL). The term acoustic trauma means hearing loss due to single exposure to intense sound (medicine.medscape.com, 2018).

ONIHL is a more common cause of noise-induced hearing loss (NIHL) which is simply the result of damage to the sensory hair cells in the cochlea, and more severe problem than sociocosis for the following reasons: (1) the fear of losing jobs may push people to remain in environments with noise levels higher than they would otherwise accept, and (2) in the workplace, high levels noise may be sustained regularly for many hours each day over many years. Consequently, occupational noise exposure has drawn the most attention and is the best-studied (medicine.medscape.com, 2018).

Several factors contribute to NIHL, such as sound frequency, duration of exposure and individual susceptibility. Sensory hair cells can repair initially when they are affected by sound energy. They can also recover after exposure to loud noise for a short period followed by a rest or a period of quiet time. But exposure to excess noise or repeated inflammation from sound energy can permanently destroy hair cells. Since humans cannot regenerate hair cells, the result of damaged hair cells is PTS (permanent threshold shift) or permanent hearing loss (Alberti, 2001).

Several studies report hypothesis on presbycusis (hearing loss due to ageing). It is still challenging to recognise one factor responsible for causing presbycusis (Rosenhall, 2003). No clear-cut differences exist between young and older individuals in their

susceptibility to noise-induced hearing loss, but a lot of males than females report noise-induced hearing loss (NIHL) (Dell et al., 2012).

ONIHL occurs in two phases. The first phase is known as a Temporary Threshold Shift (TTS). TTS is characterized by slight hearing loss following noise exposure removed after a rest period. With this phase, a significant complaint of workers is a "ringing sensation " in the ears after work periods. Recovery time in this phase is usually within 16-24 hours, however, injury is not to the sensory cells (Šušković, 2012). The second phase, known as Permanent Threshold Shift (PTS), occurs only after continuous and frequent exposure to noise levels that cause TTS. When a worker moves from TTS to PTS, the damage at this level is permanent because the sensory cells have been compromised (Šušković, 2012).

Sensorineural and conductive hearing loss are the two main types of hearing impairment. Sensorineural hearing impairment is irreversible and occurs in the inner ear, while conductive hearing impairment is reversible and occurs in the outer and middle ear. Also, there is an 8% risk of workers experiencing sensorineural hearing impairment when the noise exposure exceeds 85 dBA in the work environment (NIOSH, 1998). The sensorineural hearing loss, damage to the auditory nerve, usually occurs at the 4,000 Hz frequency range. The hearing loss will expand across 2,000 or 3,000 through 6,000 Hz when an individual continues exposure to high-frequency noises (Barber, 2010).

According to the American College of Occupational and Environmental Medicine (2002), the principal characteristics of occupational NIHL. It is always sensorineural, primarily affecting the cochlear hair cells in the inner ear. It is typically bilateral since most noise exposures affect both ears symmetrically.

Nevertheless, individuals with non-NIHL, such as presbycusis, may have hearing threshold levels more than these values. Hearing loss due to continuous or intermittent noise exposure increases most rapidly during the first 10 to 15 years of exposure, and

the rate of hearing loss then decelerates as the hearing threshold increases. Medium contrasts with age-related loss, which accelerates over time. The risk of NIHL increases with long-term noise exposures above 80 dB and increases as exposures rise above 85 dB. Continuous noise exposure throughout the workday and over the years is more damaging than interrupted noise exposure, which permits the ear to have a rest period. Individuals with NIHL may experience significant morbidity from hearing loss, concomitant tinnitus, or impaired speech discrimination. On the job, such hearing loss can impact worker communications and safety

2.6 Environmental noise, air pollution and their effects

The impacts of noise pollution in Europe are highly significant. Around 22 million adults living in agglomerations or near primary noise sources with levels starting at 55 dB Lden are highly annoyed from road traffic, railways, aircraft, and industry. Moreover, about 6.5 million adults suffer severe sleep disturbance because of night-time noise levels equal to or above 50 dB at Lnight. The exposure to noise from road traffic, railways, aircraft, and industry are estimated to contribute every year to about 48,000 new cases of ischaemic heart disease and 12,000 premature deaths. Aircraft noise is associated with a decrease in children performance in schools that are affected by flight paths. Coincidentally, the United Kingdom has the most prevalence of aircraft noise association in children performance, but they are the first country to take the initiative to curb the situation. As a result, about 12,500 children in Europe between the ages of 7 and 17 years have a reading impairment due to exposure to aircraft noise (ENE, 2020).

Regarding individual noise sources, road traffic noise is the most prevalent source of environmental noise. According to ENE. (2020), road traffic noise has the most significant contribution to the burden of disease due noise (75 %), followed by railway (20 %), aircraft (4 %) and industry (0.5 %) noise. A part of the disease burden is

annoyance, sleep disturbance, heart disease and cognitive impairment due noise that occurs inside urban areas of more than 100,000 inhabitants.

Previous study by WHO compare the burden of disease across noise sources and health outcomes, they used a standard metric, the Disability Adjusted Life Year (DALY). Key pieces of information needed for these calculations were noise exposures and population distributions, population data on disease occurrence, mortality rates, and life expectancy, disability weights (i.e., weighting factor that reflects the relative severity of a disease/health state) and exposure-response relationships (ERR) between health outcomes and noise exposures (ENE, 2020). According to the burden of disease results estimated from the noise data covered by the END, Disability-Adjusted Life Years (DALYs) lost due to noise-induced health outcomes were estimated to be equivalent to 437,000 years for sleep disturbance, 453,000 years for annoyance, 156,000 years for heart disease and 75 years for cognitive impairment of children. However, a simple summation of DALYs for each health effect may indicate that about 1 million healthy years of life are lost every year because of environmental noise health effects assessed. The evidence of risk estimation for the burden of cardiovascular disease attributed to environmental noise in European regions relate to environmental noise effects on health following epidemiological studies (ENE, 2020).

According to Bromfield et al. (2013), high blood pressure is the leading Global Burden of Disease Risk Factor, therefore the impetus for worldwide prevention programs.

Given the world, 1.6%, 9.8% and 12.6% of deaths are caused by hypertensive heart disease, cerebrovascular disease, and ischaemic heart disease, respectively. Ischaemic heart disease has led to 22.8% and 9.4% of total death in developed and developing countries, according to Global Burden of Disease 2000 and analysis of the Global Burden of Disease 1990 - 2010 study (Lim et al., 2012).

Worldwide, the WHO Global burden of Disease 2013 study has concluded that 13.5% and 1.4% deaths are attributable to high blood pressure (hypertension) and urban air pollution (Bromfield et al., 2013).

According to WHO methods and data sources for the global burden of disease estimates 2000-2016 on Global DALY methods, the Disability Weights (DW) represent the relative severity of disease stages to be incorporate in summary measures of population health (WHO, 2018). They investigated the level of agreement on disability weights in Western European countries with different valuation methods. The visual analogue scale (VAS), the time trade-off technique (TTO), and the person trade-off technique (PTO) are the three valuation methods that measure the level of agreement of disability weight.

Environmental noise causes health impact following exposure of the noise frequency or wave of noise. An acute or long exposure to noise has led to adverse effects such as annoyance, sleep disturbance, interference with speech or other 'desired' sounds, anxiety, hearing damage and stress-related cardiovascular health problems. To conclude that exposure can have an adverse effect depending on the accurate and control measurement noise.

The transport sector is the most significant source of traffic noise and air emissions. Both road traffic noise and air pollution have the same sources occurring on the road, from the vehicle engine and exhaust. Noise frequency is created from vehicle tyres and engines.

Measuring noise and air pollution will aid to depict the risk. Noise is measured in decibels (dB) using a pattern-approved sound level meter. The measurements of noise

and air pollution are typically taken daily or over weeks, considering weather conditions and vice versa. In 2020, research by the (ENE, 2020) identified that urbanisation development activities (transport development of road lanes, increase in traffic and high construction and extension of cities) were the main drivers of the increase in environmental noise. The evidence of risk estimation for the burden of cardiovascular disease related to environmental noise in European regions effect health following epidemiological studies (ENE, 2020).

Due to the increase in economic activities and social activities, pollution in most cities is especially in the urban areas of the United Kingdom (EEA, 2006). Cities are most polluted environments because of their high population densities and associated high levels of the dominance of private transport on air quality in cities and public road traffic (DfT, 2019). Air and noise pollution from road traffic affect the roadside ecology in residential areas and commercial/business districts (Davies et al., 2009).

Studying the association between environmental noise and air pollution is important to allow reliable action planning if threshold limits are exceeded (Transportation Noise Action Plan (TNAP), 2019, Air Quality Management Area, 2015).

Road traffic is a crucial source of environmental noise. Studies of road traffic noise have reported an association between exposure to auditory and more comprehensive health impacts such as hearing loss and myocardial infarction and hypertension. Annoyance and disturbed sleep are common effects because of road traffic exposure. Furthermore, epidemiological studies have found that environmental noise is associated with an increased incidence of arterial hypertension, myocardial infarction, heart failure, and stroke. Observational and translational studies indicate that significantly nighttime noise increases stress hormones and oxidative stress levels, which may lead to endothelial dysfunction and arterial hypertension (Münzel, 2018).

Despite this obvious co-exposure, exploring the link is ongoing in the UK and worldwide (Foraster, 2013) dealing with road noise and air pollution. However, this has

changed in recent years, and studies on their combined effects are currently underway (WHO, 2018). Some cohort studies in the UK have used the distance to major roads as a surrogate for exposure to air pollutants which follow cardiovascular health impact (Cai et al., 2017, 2018). Some studies also use spatial and temporal to draw associations between road traffic noise and air pollution with cardiovascular health issues (Fecht et al., 2016; De Kluizenaar et al., 2013). Studies are ongoing in Europe countries on issues of traffic noise and air pollution exposures. Both are associated with hypertensive heart disease, but mechanisms may differ. (Babisch et al., 2014; Pitchika et al., 2017; Fuks et al., 2017, Sears et al., 2018). Understanding the association between these pollutants is essential to understand better their relationship and joint effects on human health (Fecht et al., 2016).

Researchers can explore them by evaluating associations between model noise and air pollutants using different spatial units and area characteristics.

Noise at different components of road traffic exposure frequency could be used to predict the risk of hypertension (Chang et al., 2014). Researchers could use the different range of frequency of road traffic noise exposure to predict the risk of hypertension

A standard framework methodology for measurement of noise exposure is called the Common noise assessment method in Europe under the Environmental Noise Directive (2002/49/EC). The European Union (EU) initiated the common objective framework due to differences in approach to a collection of data and techniques among EU member states. The common objective framework provides knowledge on noise levels and related health problems to European citizens so that an action plan will take place to remedy and improvise preventive measures that are judicious and efficient against exposure to hazardous noise levels (Kephalopoulos, 2012-2014). In 2017, this had taken effect and implemented in ongoing strategic noise mapping of third-round making measuring noise at different range of frequency valid for road traffic from 125 Hz to 4000 Hz. Road traffic noise is measured in octave bands (Kephalopoulos, 2012-2014).

The EEA database covers noise sources specified in the Environmental Noise Directive (END) (such as major roads and urban agglomerations) and the number of people exposed to each noise source inside and outside urban areas. Access to noise mapping data for the urban population compared to the total population is available. The noise mapping data is extrapolated only to agglomerations of a population threshold of 250000 inhabitants. The UK noise mapping data produce data from urban areas with a population between 100,000 to 250.000 inhabitants.

Noise levels are represented in 5-dB interval bands at Lden 55 dB (an average of day, evening, and night) and night (Lnight) 50 dB but a different component of frequency of traffic noise are reasonable and common predictors of adverse health effects in a population. Also, diverse components of frequency of traffic noise might be helpful in reflecting special noise index for setting health-related noise limits.

Health sectors can consider different frequency of traffic noise to determine specific health effects such as hypertension. Study on road traffic noise frequency and prevalence of hypertension in Taichung, Taiwan, suggests that exposure to road traffic noise at low and hearing-sensitive frequencies is associated with hypertension. Noise exposure at 125 Hz may have the most significant risk for hypertension (Chang et al., 2014).

UK countries have monitoring networks for air pollution in Scotland, Wales, Northern Ireland, and England. The DEFRA of the UK handle issues about Air Quality management and monitoring. The government of the various regions are responsible for air quality management. Hence, they have a webpage concerning air pollution monitoring which are used as a platform to disseminate information for adult and children (O'Brien, 2016). Government of regions of the UK website publishes daily air quality forecasts. The public can also access the website of various regions through the internet to monitor air pollution in their area. Measurement of air pollution is published

on Air Quality monitoring website base on hourly limits and the results from the air quality network database are single measurement points. Based on the banding system (COMEAP, 2011), various regions in the UK use Daily Air Quality Index (DAQI) for their forecast.

Studies are conducted by various governments in regions of the UK on strategy noise mapping for major roads, rail, airports, and industry agglomeration to check environmental noise for competent authorities such as transport noise to take an action plan. Various criteria are used to select the transportation links at major roads. These criteria are roads with more than 6,000,000 vehicle passages per year and agglomeration of populations of more than 250,000. The roads with more than 3,000,000 vehicle passages per year and agglomeration of populations of more than 100,000 (one hundred thousand). These criteria are part of the strategic noise mapping and action planning. The various governments in regions of the UK produced strategic noise maps for END Round 3 (for 2017) using a computer-based prediction methodology. The public can find the outputs on the DEFRA and Noise Mapping websites of various governments (Transportation Noise Action Plan (TNAP), 2019).

Air quality guidelines are used by various air quality website subregions of the UK such as England, Scotland, Wales, and Northern Ireland. The guidelines stipulate that exposure to a concentration of $PM_{2.5}$ should not be greater than $10 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ or $25 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for annual mean or 24-hour mean, respectively. The guidelines stipulate that exposure to a concentration of PM_{10} should not exceed $20 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for annual mean or $50 \mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ for 24 hours mean respectively.

However, many parts of the UK's air pollution levels may be above the limits of air quality regulations, which are not legally binding.

According to the updated air quality data by Scottish air quality UK, the risk of numerous health effects increases linearly with daily pollution levels in the range of the most common particulate matter concentrations. The network should be able to produce a complete series of daily data allowing the health impact of the daily variation in the pollution concentration to be assessed and the annual average calculated, and noise exposure modelled by the Scottish transport noise.

Government statistics estimate that air pollution in the UK reduces the life expectancy of every person by an average of 7–8 months, with an associated cost of up to £20 billion each year. UK government have introduced legislation and policies aiming to minimise cause-effect of air pollution on health and the environment (EEA, 2014; Ricardo Energy & Environment, 2019).

The comparative burden of disease studies demonstrates that air pollution is the primary environmental cause of disability-adjusted life years lost (DALYs). Environmental noise is ranked second in terms of DALYs in Europe, and the DALYs attributed noise were more than those attributed to lead, ozone, and dioxins. However, the DALYs of environmental noise and air pollution are not clear in the UK. Data on an estimation disease burden in the UK is not precise until data is modelled to describe the burden of disease that cause the DALYs (ENE, 2020).

Air and noise pollution of urban traffic is the most typical of these categories. Unfortunately, reliable methodologies are lacking for the impact management of some varieties, as is the case of noise. Considering that transport and housing are cornerstones of the world production system, traffic noise is one of the categories likely to gain relevance soon, given its effects on human health. Air and noise pollution of urban traffic is the most typical of these categories. Unfortunately, reliable methodologies are lacking for the impact management of some types, as is the case of noise. Considering

that transport and housing are cornerstones of the world production system, traffic noise is one of the categories likely to gain relevance soon, given its effects on human health.

2.7 Policies, Laws and Legislations of Noise and Air Pollution

The EU Directive on the management of environmental noise adds road traffic as environmental noise. The European union have various noise limit and policy controlling environmental noise and such policies followed and monitored to prevent its effects on man. UK Government has produced these noise maps in response to the European Parliament and Council Directive for Assessment and Management of Environmental Noise 2002/49/EC, more commonly referred to as the Environmental Noise Directive (END). This directive deals with noise from rail, air traffic, road, and industries. To embrace their responsibility to deliver the requirements of the END legislation in the UK, countries such as Scotland under the Scottish Government published the Environmental Noise (Scotland) Regulations 2006.

Various countries have taken an initiative to address environmental noise and air quality. Governments of countries in the UK have exhibited courage to the directives of the EU, such as the Scottish government (Barnes et al., 2018).

The Jacobs consultants, on behalf Scottish Government, embarked on a study on exposure noise mapping for major roads, rail, airports, and industry agglomeration to check environmental noise for competent authorities such as transport noise to take an action plan. Various criteria are used to select transportation links for major roads. Roads with more than 6,000,000 (six million) vehicle passages per year for round one, roads with more than 3,000,000 (three million) vehicle passages per year for round two and agglomerations with a population of more than 250,000 (two hundred and fifty thousand) and agglomerations with a population of more than 100,000 (one hundred thousand) respectively. These were part of the strategic noise mapping and action

planning. Jacobs Consultants produced the strategic noise maps for END Round 3 (for 2017) on behalf of the Scottish Government. These were created using a computer-based prediction methodology, and the public can find the outputs on the Scottish Noise Mapping website. (TNAP, 2019)

According to the Glasgow agglomeration proposed noise actions between 2018 to 2023, noise action options fall into three categories. The potential remedial measures will be the subject of a cost-benefit analysis. They will consider those responsible for any proposed actions and whether they are affordable or desirable.

The current state of knowledge on noise sources and population exposure in Europe is primarily based on data submitted by the EU member state on a five-year cycle to the EEA. The EEA database covers noise sources specified in the END (such as major roads, major railways, major airports, and urban agglomerations) and the number of people exposed to each of the noise sources inside and outside urban areas. Noise levels are calculated and represented in 5-dB interval bands at $L_{den} \geq 55$ dB (an average of day, evening, and night) and at night ($L_{night} \geq 50$ dB (Jarosińska et al., 2018).

2.7.1 Acoustics - Measurements of sound pressure levels released by stationary road vehicles (ISO 5130:2007+A1:2012)

ISO 5130:2007+A1:2012 [ISO, 2012] defines a test protocol for determining the noise level emitted by road vehicles when stationary. The test method maintains a constant engine speed while monitoring the noise level when the throttle is released. The microphone is placed 0.5 metres away from the exhaust vent. This process is not intended as a method of checking the exhaust sound pressure level while the engine is operating at realistic loads or a form of checking the exhaust sound pressure levels against a general noise limit for types of road vehicles, as described in the Standard.

2.7.2 Specification of test tracks for measuring noise output by road vehicles (ISO 10844:2014).

The ISO 10844:2014 [ISO, 2014] standard covers a test surface's materials, design, construction, and attributes to reduce inter-site variation in-vehicle noise measurements caused by texture, sound absorption and possibly mechanical impedance or stiffness properties of the surface layer.

In the United Kingdom, vehicles older than three years must pass an annual Ministry of transport (MOT) test to ensure roadworthiness. When a car fails an MOT requirement, it cannot be driven on the public roadway until the defect is fixed, save to and from the test centre if necessary. The following are the steps involved in the testing:

During the MOT test, the exhaust system is visually inspected for flaws, such as holes in the pipes. Although this is primarily a safety examination, it does identify exhaust systems that may be creating noise because of inadequate maintenance or just an outdated exhaust. • A subjective assessment of the efficacy of the exhaust system is also made.

2.7.3 Noise and Statutory Nuisance Act of 1993 & Environmental Protection Act of 1990

The Environmental Protection Act (EPA) of 1990 establishes the primary regulatory framework for statutory nuisances, such as noise nuisances, arising from industrial, recreational, or household activities. Noise on the street is now a statutory nuisance, thanks to the Noise and Statutory Nuisance Act of 1993, which altered vital sections of the EPA. This includes noise from automobiles (for example, car alarms), machines, and other equipment like loudspeakers and this does not include noise from traffic.

Noise to be classified as a statutory nuisance under Part III of the EPA, it must be harmful to the complainant's health or cause unreasonable and persistent disruption to the complainant's lifestyle.

2.7.4 Anti-social Behaviour, Crime and Policing Act 2014 and Police Reform Act 2002

The police have the authority under Section 59 of the Police Reform Act 2002 to stop, seize, and remove a vehicle if they have reasonable grounds to believe that the car is being used in a manner that constitutes careless and inconsiderate driving (as defined by the Road Traffic Act 1988 ["Road Traffic Act 1988"]) or is causing, or likely to cause, alarm, distress, or annoyance to members of the public.

Section 60 empowers the Secretary of State to issue regulations governing the removal, retention, release, and disposal of motor vehicles confiscated under Section 59.

Following the change to the Police Reform Act's Part 1 of Schedule noise emissions from road vehicles must be tested as part of EU-type approval procedures. A manufacturer can get certification from a competent body that the product meets the standards of a specific Directive through the type of approval process.

2.7.5 Regulation (EU) No. 540/2014

Regulation (EU) 540/2014 [EPCEU, 2014] for motor vehicles and Regulation (EU) 168/2013 [EPCE, 2013] for motorcycles define the acceptable noise levels for vehicle type certification.

Regulation (EU) 540/2014, which repeals European Directive 70/157/EEC [EC, 2014], establishes sound emission limitations for road vehicles and shows more representative techniques for monitoring sound emissions from exhaust systems and silencers. Several changes have tightened these restrictions.

Limits for eight types of passenger and commercial vehicles range from 72 to 80 decibels (A) (A). Over the next ten years, these limits are projected to be tightened again. Most new passenger automobiles are scheduled to have a noise level of 68 dB(A) by 2026 (Vehicle Certification Agency, 2019).

2.7.6 Regulation (EU) No. 168/2013

This Regulation, which replaces Directive 78/1015/EEC [EC, 1878], defines sound level limitations for motorcycles and regulations for exhaust or intake silencers. This establishes a standardised testing technique with limit values ranging from 63 dB(A) to 80 dB(A) for three types of motorcycles (A).

The Motor Vehicles (Type Approval) (Great Britain) Regulations 1984, under the Road Traffic Act 1972, put these type approval Regulations into UK law.

The Road Vehicles (Construction and Use) Regulations of 1986 are a set of regulations that govern the construction and use of road vehicles.

The Road Vehicles (Construction and Use) Regulations 1986 (Road Vehicle regulation, 1986), under the Road Traffic Act 1972 (as amended) (Road Traffic Act, 1972), aim to ensure that vehicles used in the United Kingdom are of good quality. These rules are utilised to put EU directives into effect.

The following regulations address noise emission limits for road vehicles:

must meet specified noise regulations, effectively implying that noise emissions are unchanged compared to the original suppressor. Furthermore, there must be no rise in noise because of improper maintenance.

- Type approval limitations are required for new vehicles under Regulation 55 (cars) and Regulation 57 (motorcycles).
- Regulation 97 prohibits excessive noise whiles operating the vehicle, and the usage of audible warning devices.
- Regulation 54 prohibits the modification of equipment such as silencers so that the noise level exceeds when it was first constructed. Silencers for mopeds and motorbikes must be replace.

" Uniform provisions for licencing motor vehicles with at least four wheels in terms of their noise emissions," according to UNECE Regulation 51.

This Regulation (UNECE, 2019) lays out the processes for evaluating noise during the approval of automobiles, vans, lorries, and buses. The method provided in ISO 362 "measurement of noise created by accelerating road vehicles" (ISO, 2015; ISO, 2009) is used during the type of approval procedure. Additional Sound Emission Provisions (ASEP), a new test procedure, was added to the type certification process in 2016. Noise limitations for different vehicle types is reduced over time, there has been concern that these reductions have not resulted in lower-traffic noise levels. The ASEP presents a new test that is more reflective of real-life situations.

"Uniform provisions governing the authorisation of motorcycles with relation to noise," according to UNECE Regulation 41. The provisions relating to the type of approval of motor vehicles with two or three wheels in terms of noise are outlined in this Regulation. Testing Noise emissions using the procedures established by ISO 5130 (ISO, 2012) and ISO 362 (ISO, 2015; ISO, 2009); like UNECE Regulation 51; however only the acceleration test result is accepted for type approval purposes. Tests under the ASEP process are now required, just as they are under Regulation 51.

"Uniform provisions governing the authorisation of two-wheeled mopeds," according to UNECE Regulation 63.

The noise emission restrictions for mopeds are outlined in this regulation 51. The noise limitations are the same as those outlined in Regulation (EU) 168/2013.

2.8 Air quality monitoring, managing and legislation

Activities relating to the monitoring and managing air quality in the UK are driven by European (EU) legislation. The 2008 ambient air quality directive (2008/50/EC) sets legally binding limits for concentrations in ambient (outdoor) air of major air pollutants that are known to have a significant impact on human health, including particulate matter (PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}) and nitrogen dioxide (EU Legislation and policy, 2015).

The 2008 directive replaced most of the earlier EU air quality legislation and was made law in Scotland through the Air Quality Standards (Scotland) Regulations 2010. The Regulations also incorporate the 4th air quality daughter directive (2004/107/EC) that sets targets for levels in ambient air of specific heavy metals and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons.

According to (the UK and Scottish Air Quality Legislation, 2015), the UK Government leads the UK's input to International and European relating to air quality, with information from the Scottish Government and the other devolved administrations. Linking to the requirements of the EU Directives, the latest Air Quality Strategy published in July 2007 established the framework for air quality improvements across the UK. Measures agreed upon at the national and international levels are the foundations on which the strategy is based. The plan sets out the Air Quality Standards and Objectives which have been set to benchmark air quality in terms of protecting human health and the environment. However, within the UK, air quality is a devolved matter, with the Scottish Government responsible for developing air quality policy and legislation for Scotland.

The local authority must declare an Air Quality Management Area (AQMA) and implement an Air Quality Action Plan to improve air quality within the areas that exceed recommended limit (AQMA, 2015).

Given the key requirement of the Environment Act (1995), the central government was to produce an Air Quality Strategy. Part IV of The Environment Act 1995 sets provisions for protecting air quality in the UK and local air quality management. Unfortunately, following the Royal Assent of the Regulatory Reform (Scotland) Bill (2014). Local Authorities in Scotland are no longer required to undertake further

assessments of air quality following the declaration of an Air Quality Management Area under Section 37 of the Bill, subsection 1 of section 84 of the Environment Act 1995.

The local authority will address issues under the AQMA for producing how an action plan is outline.

Between 2000-2002, Air Quality (Scotland) Regulations and Air Quality (Scotland) Amendment Regulations were enacted following a tighter objective for benzene, carbon monoxide and delicate particulate matter. The acceptable particulate matter objective (PM₁₀) is the most stringent in the UK. (AQMA, 2015).

WHO did Amendment Regulations on Air Quality (2016) and Scotland was the first country in Europe and UK to adopt to WHO guideline value for PM_{2.5} delicate particulate matter into legislation (WHO, 2019).

According to the Cleaner Air for Scotland (CAFS, 2016), currently, thirty-eight AQMAs in Scotland in fourteen local authority areas, are declared for transport-related emissions of nitrogen dioxide and PM₁₀. Scotland Environmental Protection Agency (SEPA) also has a part to play through its roles as a regulator of industrial emissions and an advisor for air quality reviews, assessments, and action plans. With the approval of Scottish Ministers, SEPA can question the Scottish local authorities whenever they must to make sufficient progress towards meeting the air quality targets and actions.

According to CAFS (2017), 40 actions plan deliver further air pollution reductions. Furthermore, this action has led to progress considering significant reductions in overall levels of key pollutants. They have also adopted to WHO guideline level for PM_{2.5}. The move has led to the expansion of monitoring. Public information and development of models for the major cities and texting of regional model guidance have improve due measures being taken.

In many countries, deteriorating air quality is a serious issue. Scotland, and notably the UK, is plagued by severe pollution problems. Continuous air quality monitoring throughout cities is one of the first steps toward better understanding the problem. The

Scottish government have stepped forward to install air quality sensors and make the data publicly available. Air quality Scotland is a platform that gathers data from all public sources and presents it in a user-friendly format.

Then, map the sensor data for PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀ and NO₂ concentrations. The goal is to create an informative spatial visualisation from this tabular data.

Works have gone into an introduction of Scotland's Low Emission Zone (LEZ) in Glasgow at the end of 2018. Further LEZs will be established in Aberdeen, Dundee, and Edinburgh by 2020. Given all other AQMAs, they will be established by 2023 where the evidence supports such an approach.

Given this fact, there are still challenges that persist. Challenges such as continuing exceedance of NO_x and particulate levels at specific sites persist. Agriculture and domestic burning emissions stay. The degree of integration between air quality, place-making, and climate change continues. Unresolved air quality strategic continue to persist. Ricardo Energy & Environment monitors air pollution on behalf of the Scottish Government. They deliver information relating to air pollution in Scotland to the public on their websites (O'Brien, 2016). The website publishes daily air quality forecasts. Members of the public can receive daily alerts (via mobile phone text message or e-mail) when the air pollution levels in their areas are moderate or high. The forecast uses Daily Air Quality Index (DAQI) based on the band system developed by COMEAP. The band system classifies pollutant levels on a scale of 1 to 10 (COMEAP, 2011).

Measuring is based on hourly rather than annual mean limits and the results from the air quality network database are single measurement points. Therefore, models are essential to understand processes, identify relationships, associations, and causality, formalise stakeholder models, and quantify prevention and interventions effects. Models can help to explain data, as well as deployment of information and location of sensors by identifying hotspots and areas of interest where data collection may achieve the best results. Also, it is recognised a paradigm shift in how the integration of models

and sensors can contribute to harnessing “Huge Data”. Data importantly, make the vital step from “Huge Data” to “Huge information”.

In the UK, a network of monitoring stations focuses on a range of six major air pollutants (COMEAP, 2009 and COMEAP, 2011).

These pollutants include ozone, carbon monoxide (CO), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), sulphur dioxide (SO₃), fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}), coarse particulate matter (PM₁₀), and nitrogen dioxide (O₃). To publish air quality levels that combine these pollutants, DEFRA utilises a specific UK air quality measure called the “Daily Air Quality Index” (DAQI). On a scale of 1 to 10, the DAQI rates air quality, with 1–3 representing “Low,” 4–6 denotes “Moderate,” 7–9 denotes “High,” and 10 denotes “Very High”.

Table 2:3 : Air Quality index analysis in the UK

Air pollution banding and value	Accompanying health messages for at-risk individuals*	Accompanying health messages for the general population
1-3:LOW	Take part in your regular outdoor activities.	Take part in your regular outdoor activities.
4-6:MODERATE	People and children with lung difficulties and adults with heart problems should consider minimising strenuous physical activity, especially outdoors, if they are experiencing symptoms.	Take part in your regular outdoor activities.
7-9:HIGH	People and children with lung difficulties and adults with heart problems should consider minimising strenuous physical activity, especially outdoors, if they are experiencing symptoms.	If you have sore eyes, a cough, or a sore throat, you should limit your activity, especially if you are outside.
10:VERY HIGH	Adults and children with lung difficulties, those with cardiac problems, and the elderly should avoid strenuous physical exercise. Asthmatics may find that they need to use their reliever inhaler more frequently.	Reduce physical activity, especially outside, if you have symptoms like a cough or a sore throat.

Source: (DEFRA, 2020).

The hourly mean concentration was used for nitrogen dioxide. For each pollutant, the boundaries between index points. The latest 24-hour running mean for the current day is based on the daily mean concentration for historical data for PM_{2.5} particles. The present day's 24-hour running mean is calculated using the daily mean concentration for historical data for PM₁₀ particles.

POLLUTANT	Index	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
	Band	Low	Low	Low	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	High	High	High	Very High
P.M10	µg ^{m-3}	0-16	17-33	34-50	51-58	59-66	67-75	76-83	84-91	91-100	101 or more
P.M2.5	µg ^{m-3}	0-11	12-23	24-35	36-41	42-47	48-53	54-58	59-64	65-70	71 or more
NO2	µg ^{m-3}	0-67	68-134	135-200	201-267	268-334	335-400	401-467	468-534	535-600	601 or more

Figure 2:1:Boundaries Between Index Points for Each Pollutant Source:(DEFRA, 2020)

Air quality index is an annual mean concentration guideline for particulate matter from the World Health Organization. The guideline stipulates that PM_{2.5} not exceed 10 µg/m³ annual mean or 25 µg/m³ 24-hour mean; and that PM₁₀ not exceed 20 µg/m³ annual mean, or 50 µg/m³ 24-hour mean.

(WHO, 2020), has published guidelines on outdoor (ambient) air pollution levels, which are frequently used as reference tools by policymakers worldwide to define air quality regulations and goals. The guidelines lay forth evidence-based, health-based requirements for various air contaminants that cities should use as targets for improving air quality. The guidelines were first established in 2005 and revised in 2021. Air pollution has serious health consequences in cities worldwide, and the World Health Organization currently considers it the single greatest environmental danger to human health. Air pollution is projected to cause 7 million premature deaths every year.

PM_{2.5}, or tiny particulate matter with a diameter of 2.5 micrometres or less, is the most harmful pollutant because it can pass through the lungs and into the bloodstream, causing cardiovascular and respiratory disorders and cancer. It affects more people than other pollutants and has health consequences even at deficient levels. Countries can

lessen the burden of sickness and long and short-term ailments by lowering air pollution levels.

Annual average PM_{2.5} concentrations should not exceed 5 g/m³, and 24-hour average exposures should not exceed 15 g/m³ more than 3 - 4 days per year, according to the new guidelines.

Interim targets aid in planning incremental milestones toward cleaner air, particularly for cities, regions, and countries with significant levels of air pollution. In the case of PM_{2.5}, they are an annual mean of 35 g/m³, 24-hour mean of 75 g/m³, the annual mean of 25 g/m³, 24-hour standard of 50 g/m³, the annual mean of 15 g/m³, 24-hour mean of 37.5 g/m³ and yearly mean of 10 g/m³, 24-hour standard of 25 g/m³

PM₁₀ (particulate matter having a diameter of fewer than 10 microns) concentrations of 15 g/m³ yearly and 45 g/m³ on a 24-hour basis. NO₂ concentrations of 10 g/m³ yearly and 25 g/m³ on a 24-hour basis.

Considering the current policy and air quality index, it was appropriate to evaluate air quality in the context of WHO, 2020.

Risk assessment of Environmental Burden of Disease (EBD) involves reviewing the relationship between environmental noise and its related health effects (WHO, 2019). Estimating EBD for road traffic noise requires knowledge of the distribution of noise exposure in the population, an exposure-response relationship for each health outcome of interest, and an estimate of a disability weight (DW) for each result (Brown, 2015). These EBD calculations use an exposure-based approach by calculating the country-specific population-attributable fraction (impact fraction). Attributable cases can be calculated based on the distribution of the population in different exposure categories and the respective relative incidence of disease (WHO, 2019).

Studies prepared by experts in working groups are convened and published by WHO Regional Office for Europe. They provide technical support to policymakers and their advisers in the quantitative risk assessment of environmental noise, using evidence and data available in Europe. Their studies have concluded that noise indicators used for noise mapping in the EU can be used for a quantitative risk assessment regarding cardiovascular risk if exposure-response relationships are known. They consider two endpoints (Hypertension and ischemic heart disease) and different exposure-response curves if necessary.

They consider the burden of disease calculations based on an annual occurrence of the event of interest multiplied by duration. However, the prevalence data used must reflect a yearly prevalence. Therefore, only point prevalence data and the previous year's data should be considered.

2.9 Road traffic, the use of peak hours, building typologies and morphological structures and their impact

The potential environmental and health challenges posed by excessive traffic emission and associated traffic-related air pollution (TRAP) are heavily influenced by liveability conditions, neighbouring environmental features, and the socioeconomic status of affected households, particularly in densely populated areas, for example seen in Hong Kong (Mak et al., 2013).

As a result, it is critical to first incorporate “social determinants of health” into the retrieval of local-scale traffic emission distributions and then study the potential links between citizens, well-being, and health quality via air quality modelling (Mak et al., 2013).

In this case study determinants include social patterns, such as working hours, usual peak hours, citizen traffic mobility, the character of the area and population density, as well as the building typologies located on various streets. Considering the “official

working hours” of offices and private companies, as well as the operational timeslots of retail shops in business districts (e.g., commercial areas), it is expected that the traffic flow between most residential districts and nearby commercial districts will be the heaviest during rush hours (i.e., early morning and evening periods); thus, the highest NO_x and PM_{2.5} emissions should also be detected during these timeslots (Mak et al., 2013).

While pollution concentrations are lower at midnight due to lower traffic loading, the residual levels still have an impact. It still affects residents living near public roads, particularly in Hong Kong, due to tall building typologies near roadside transportation routes under the constraints of limited space for utilisation (Mak et al., 2013).

The case study also attempted to develop a systematic geo-processing framework via data analytics, which processes available hourly traffic NO_x and PM_{2.5} emission records of all roads in Hong Kong, to obtain a more realistic distribution of district-wise traffic emissions for the modelling of spatial pollution profiles, which may open new windows for conducting health exposure assessment, particularly during peak hours (Mak et al., 2013).

In many places, vehicle emissions are the sources of high levels of nitrous oxide (NO) and particulate matter (PM) (Zhang et al., 2013). Particularly close to large roadways, the severity and duration of traffic congestion can significantly increase pollutant emissions and worsen air quality (Zhang et al., 2013). According to a previous study, significant health hazards may be associated with traffic congestion. Increasing traffic can significantly increase the risks, depending on the road style and other variables. Danger brought on by traffic congestion must consider travel time, length of rush hour, estimates of the emissions caused by the congestion, and uncertainty. These emissions raise the morbidity and mortality risks for motorists, commuters, and those living close to roads (Zhang et al., 2013).

The various causes of noise in road vehicles can be identified depending on the vehicle category. The engine, powertrain, tyres cooperating with the road surface, the flow of liquids and gases in the vehicle's systems and installations, vibration of the vehicle and its components, and so on are the principal causes of noise in road vehicles. Limit levels for pass-by noise of road vehicles are defined by UNECE regulations. Limit values for allowable external noise emitted by different categories of road vehicles in laboratory circumstances are determined in the Road Vehicles (Construction & Use) Regulations 1986 on the classification of motor vehicles and trailers, as well as specifications for vehicles in road traffic.

Both the European Union's and the current UK legislative frameworks for controlling and mitigating vehicle noise do not specify the maximum levels of noise emitted by cars in the two wheeled category. This can be explained by the fact that these vehicles are dragged rather than self-driving. The two wheeled category of cars, on the other hand has an impact on overall traffic noise. The interaction of the wheels with the road surface and the airflow demonstrates this influence. Due to the problems that noise, and air pollution pose, finding the best approach to control them is essential. One of the most challenging procedures in existence is managed by urban planners and public health specialists (Pavlović et al., 2021). It involves controlling vehicle traffic noise and air pollution (Pavlović et al., 2021).

Additionally, a study conducted in Shirdi, India, found that noise levels and air pollution exceeded the recommended limit. The authors suggested that the government should put action plans in place, such as facilitating proper management of traffic signals. Secondly, the government should divert all traffic to another subway. Thirdly, the government should declare Shirdi city as “No Horn city”. Fourthly, the government should implement measures to control pollutant emissions. Finally, they suggested that government should conduct a long-term study on concentrations of particulate matter

in the spatial and temporal dimensions of various cities due to the development of infrastructure (Kankal et al., 2011).

During the COVID 19 shutdown, when vehicle use was heavily restricted, the environment and nature benefit. A significant climate shift is the outcome of decreased human dominance in the environment. The usage of fossil fuels has significantly decreased as a result, largely as a result of industry closures and restrictions on automobile travel (Paital, 2020).

Traffic was reduced by 69% overall throughout the lockout study period (74% for light and 35% for heavy vehicles). NO₂ measurements from 129 monitoring stations showed mean decreases of 38.3% (equaling 8.8 g/m³) and 16.5% (2.2 g/m³) in PM_{2.5}. Urban traffic areas saw the greatest reductions in NO₂ and PM_{2.5}, while background places, where a sizable majority of the population resides, saw relatively modest reductions. Contrarily, O₃ concentrations increased on average by 7.6% (+4.8 g/m³), with roadside sites experiencing the biggest increases because of a decrease in local NO₂ emissions (Jephcote et al., 2021).

As a result, several metropolises around the world have drastically cut their NO₂ and CO₂ emissions. On the one hand, these beneficial natural changes have allowed species to roam freely, and on the other, biodiversity has increased everywhere (Paital, 2020). People are experiencing a never-before-seen elevated environmental revival due to cleaner air, sparkling water bodies, and beautiful landscapes in many places, including Italy, Spain, France, Los Angeles of the United States, Wuhan city of China, and New Delhi of India. Due to fresher air, sparkling water bodies, and gorgeous wild animals roaming close to human settlements, people are experiencing an environmental renaissance that has never been this high. Wild creatures, particularly birds, are taking advantage of a quiet atmosphere because buses, trains, and aircraft have been suspended.

It is nothing more than Mother Nature trying to recover. It has been thought that existence is conceivable without such a contemporary lifestyle, especially those acts connected to fossil fuels, after the end of 100 days of lockdown in some countries (Paital, 2020).

2.10 Road traffic exposure to noise and air pollution related to Hypertension

Researchers in Netherland investigated the relationship between road traffic noise and air pollution and hospital admissions for ischemic heart disease (IHD: International Classification of Diseases (ICD9) 410-414) or cerebrovascular disease using a baseline questionnaire data on hospital admission and road traffic noise and air pollution exposure for a large random sample (N = 18,213) of inhabitants of the Eindhoven region (De Kluizenaar et al., 2013).

On average, cardiovascular diseases relate to higher road traffic noise during day, evening, and night level (Lden) and air pollution exposure at home. Increased exposure did not exert a significantly increased risk of hospital admission for IHD or cerebrovascular disease. Relative risks (RRs) between 5 and 95 percentile interval increase were 1.03 (0.88-1.20) for L den; 1.04 (0.90-1.21) for particulate matter (PM₁₀); 1.05 (0.91-1.20) for elemental carbon (EC); and 1.12 (0.96-1.32) for nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) in the full model. While the risk estimate seemed highest for NO₂, between 5 and 95 percentile interval increase, expressed as RRs per 1 $\hat{I}^{1/4}$ g/m³ increases, hazard ratios seemed highest for EC (RR 1.04 [0.92-1.18]). In the subgroup of study participants with a history of cardiovascular disease, RR estimates seemed highest for noise exposure (1.19 [0.87-1.64] for L den); in the subgroup of elderly, RR seemed highest for air pollution exposure (RR 1.24 [0.93-1.66] for NO₂) (De Kluizenaar et al. (2013).

Studies from high traffic location in New York City on continuous measurement and correlation of traffic noise-air pollutants reveals that strong day-night and weekday-

weekend variation noise and air pollutants and correlations between pollutants varied by noise frequency (Ross et al., 2011). Mid and high noise frequencies were generally more strongly correlated with traffic-related pollutants than noise at low-frequency. The correlation of noise at mid- high frequency was generally stronger at night. Correlations with night-time high frequency noise were particularly high for car traffic (Spearman $r = 0.84$), nitric oxide (0.73) and nitrogen dioxide (0.83).

Data was deduce using an aethalometer for continuous elemental carbon measurement, which was co-located with a constant noise monitor near a major urban highway in New York City for six days in August 2009. They collected hourly elemental carbon measurements and hourly data on overall noise levels and low, medium, and high frequency noise levels. They obtained average concentrations of fine particles and nitrogen oxides. They also measured wind speed and direction and count car, truck, and bus for an hour using nearby regulatory monitors. Overall temporal patterns, as well as day-night and weekday-weekend patterns, were characterized for all variables. Noise levels correlated with car, truck, and bus traffic and air pollutants (Ross et al., 2011).

A similar study conducted in Taichung, Taiwan, by Chang et al., 2014, investigated road traffic noise frequency and prevalent hypertension. According to them, epidemiological studies have reported the association between Hypertension and exposure to road traffic noise, but the association between noise frequency characteristics is unclear. They sampled 820 residents living near main roads for more than three years. They took measurement of frequency components of traffic noise and traffic flow rates during 9am to 17pm on weekdays simultaneously in 2008.

Considering indicators such as adjusting for potential confounders and traffic flow rates, multiple logistic regressions were needed. Also, multiple logistic regressions were used to estimate odds ratios (ORs) for diagnosed hypertension.

The high-exposure group ($\geq$ the median of noise levels [decibels, dB]) at 63 Hz, 125 Hz and 1000 Hz had ORs for hypertension of 2.77 (95% confidence interval [CI]: 1.17-6.52), 4.08 (95% CI: 1.57-10.63) and 1.98 (1.00-3.92) (95% CI: 1.00-3.92), respectively, compared to the low-exposure group ($<$ the median of noise levels [dB]). There was an increasing trend in the prevalence of Hypertension by exposure to road traffic noise at 63, 125 and 1000 Hz in all subjects and men. Total subjects exposed to ≥ 51 dB at 125 Hz had an OR of 4.65 (95% CI = 1.46-14.83) compared to those exposed to < 47 dB. They acknowledge that low component of frequencies is associated with hypertension, specifically at 125 Hz (Chang et al., 2014).

According to a study undertaken in Sweden by Bodin et al. (2016) to assess the relationship between road traffic noise, air pollution and incident myocardial infarction (MI) in both current (1-year average) and medium-term (3-year average) perspectives. Yearly average levels noise (Lden) and air pollution (NO_x) were estimated using a geographic information system for residential addresses every year until censoring. The mean exposure levels for road traffic noise and air pollution in 2005 were Lden 51 dB(A) and NO_x 11 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$, respectively. After adjustment for individual confounders (age, gender, body mass index, smoking, education, alcohol consumption, civil status, year, country of birth and physical activity), a 10 dB(A) increase in current noise exposure did not increase the incidence rate ratio (IRR) for MI, 0.99 (95 % CI 0.86-1.14). Neither did a 10- $\hat{1}\frac{1}{4}\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ increase in current NO_x increases the risk of MI, 1.02 (95 % CI 0.86-1.21). The IRR for MI associated with combined exposure to road traffic noise >55 dB(A) and NO_x >20 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ was 1.21 (95 % CI 0.90-1.64) compared to <55 dB(A) and <20 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. This study did not provide evidence for an increased risk of MI due to exposure to road traffic noise or air pollution at moderate average exposure levels (Bodin et al., 2016).

The association between air-noise pollutants leads to thinking about the development of common strategies (Montes-González et al., 2018). A cohort study by Montes-González et al., 2018, shows an association of traffic-related air and noise pollution with maternal blood pressure and hypertensive disorders of pregnancy.

They believe this may increase the risk for cardiovascular disorders, especially among susceptible populations like pregnant women when exposed to traffic-related air and noise pollution.

The objective of this study was to evaluate the association of exposure to traffic-related air pollution and traffic noise with blood pressure in pregnant women. They extracted systolic blood pressure (SBP) and diastolic blood pressure (DBP) at ≥ 20 weeks' gestation weeks' as well as hypertensive disorders of pregnancy from medical records in the HOME Study, a prospective pregnancy and birth cohort from Cincinnati, OH (n = 370). The estimated exposure to elemental carbon attributable to traffic (ECAT)¹, a marker of traffic-related air pollution, at women's red women's at ~20 weeks' gestation weeks' using a validated land-use regression model and traffic noise using a publicly available transportation noise model. They used linear mixed models and modified Poisson regression adjusted for covariates to examine associations of ECAT and traffic noise with blood pressure and hypertensive disorders of pregnancy risk, respectively. In adjusted models, they found a 1.6 (95% CI= 0.02, 3.3; p= 0.048) mm Hg increase in SBP associated with an interquartile range increase in ECAT concentration; the association was stronger after adjusting for traffic noise (1.9 mmHg, 95% = 0.1, 3.7; p = 0.035). ECAT concentrations were not significantly associated with DBP or hypertensive disorders of pregnancy (Montes-González et al., 2018).

A narrative review of studies by Stansfeld (2015) in which the associations of both environmental noise and air pollution with health have reveals Hypertension, myocardial infarction, stroke, mortality, and cognitive outcomes.

Results suggest that independent effects of environmental noise from road traffic, aircraft and, with fewer studies, railway noise on cardiovascular outcomes after adjustment for air pollution.

The comparative burden of disease studies demonstrates that air pollution is the primary environmental cause of disability-adjusted life years lost (DALYs). Environmental noise is ranked second in terms of DALYs in Europe, and the DALYs attributed noise were more than those attributed to lead, ozone, and dioxins. In conclusion, in planning and health impact assessment, environmental noise should be considered an independent contributor to health risk. Environmental noise has a separate and substantial role in ill-health from air pollution. It is concluded that there is good evidence from extensive population studies that environmental noise from road traffic and aircraft is associated with cardiovascular morbidity and mortality independent of the association with air pollution (ENE, 2020). There may be both independent and common mechanisms involving associations of environmental exposures with health. Ecological planning and policy should consider both exposures when assessing ecological impacts (ENE, 2020).

2.11 Road traffic, noise pollution, air pollution and public health in communities

Bucharest is one of the most polluted cities in Europe, with a very high population density and heavy traffic. Because many residential buildings and shopping centres are near busy roads and crossroads, the air pollution-induced by traffic affects the inhabitants of the area (Danciulescu et al., 2015).

Monitoring air pollution needs to be constant to take appropriate measures when the concentrations exceed the limits. Most of the measurement techniques require time and expensive equipment. The paper presents some preliminary studies regarding the correlation between noise pollution and NO₂, SO₂ concentrations. Different distances from some jam-packed roads and crossroads are measured to determine a pattern. Statistical analysis program can analyse data on noise level and urban air pollution

generated by traffic. According to them, most results indicate a good correlation between noise and chemical pollutants. Noise could be a good indicator of air pollution, especially in the situation when there is no need for a precise determination. (Danciulescu et al., 2015).

Triggered by a Belgian study on the relation between traffic-related noise and ambient air pollutants in a street canyon, a three-week test in 2011 was performed at an air quality station near the A2 motorway in Maastricht (Severijnen, 2017).

Few studies use cheap microphones as a proxy for traffic-related air pollutants. Most reviewed studies are designed on the effects noise and air pollutants on human health. The relation between traffic-related noise and air pollutants is often a by-product, resulting from analysing all studied parameters (Severijnen, 2017).

Together with all reviewed studies, the conclusion can only be that modelling traffic-related concentrations by noise measurement is hard and testing separately is essential. On the other hand, using cheap microphones as proxies for traffic-related air pollutants should still be promoted, as reliable, low-cost sensors for air pollutants and other parameters tend to be employed more and more in cities in high-density networks (Severijnen, 2017).

Studies on the association between traffic noise and cardiovascular diseases have rarely considered air pollution as a covariate in their analyses. Isolated systolic hypertension has not yet been the focus of epidemiological noise research (Wolfgang et al., 2014).

Traffic noise (weighted day-night average noise level; Ldn) at the facade of the dwellings are derive from noise maps. Annual average PM_{2.5} mass concentrations at residential addresses using land-use regression. Blood pressure readings, self-reported doctor-diagnosed hypertension, and antihypertensive drug intake was used to evaluate hypertension. In Greater Augsburg, Germany, studies show that traffic noise and air pollution were not associated with hypertension. In the City of Augsburg population (n

= 1,893), where the exposure assessment was more detailed, the adjusted odds ratio (OR) for a 10-dB(A) increase noise was 1.16 (95% CI: 1.00, 1.35), and 1.11 (95% CI: 0.94, 1.30) after additional adjustment for PM_{2.5}. The adjusted OR for a 1- $\hat{I}$ / $\hat{4}$ g/m³ increase in PM_{2.5} was 1.15 (95% CI: 1.02, 1.30), and 1.11 (95% CI: 0.98, 1.27) after additional adjustment for noise. For isolated systolic Hypertension, the fully adjusted OR noise was 1.43 (95% CI: 1.10, 1.86) and for PM_{2.5} was 1.08 (95% CI: 0.87, 1.34). Traffic noise and PM_{2.5} were both associated with a higher prevalence of Hypertension. Mutually adjusted associations with Hypertension were positive but no longer statistically significant (Wolfgang et al., 2014).

According to a study done by Fuks et al. (2017), they investigated whether traffic-related air and noise pollution is associated with incident hypertension in European cohorts. They included seven cohorts of the European countries in the study for air pollution effects (ESCAPE). They modelled concentrations of particulate matter with aerodynamic diameter ≤ 2.5 μm (PM_{2.5}), ≤ 10 μm (PM₁₀), > 2.5 , and ≤ 10 μm (PM coarse), soot (PM_{2.5} absorbance), and nitrogen oxides at the addresses of participants with land-use regression. They study modelled residential traffic noise data according to the EU Directive 2002/49/EC. They assessed hypertension as (i) self-reported and (ii) measured (systolic BP ≥ 140 mmHg or diastolic BP ≥ 90 mmHg or intake of BP-lowering medication (BPLM). They used poisson regression with robust variance estimation to analyse traffic-related exposures with an incidence of hypertension, controlling for relevant confounders. They combined the results from individual studies with a random-effects meta-analysis. Among 41,072 participants free of self-reported hypertension at baseline, 6207 (15.1%) incident cases occurred within 5-9 years of follow-up. Incidence of self-reported hypertension was positively associated with PM_{2.5} (relative risk (RR) 1.22 [95%-confidence interval (CI):1.08; 1.37] per 5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) and PM_{2.5} absorbance (RR 1.13 [95% CI:1.02; 1.24] per 10 - 5m⁻¹). These estimates

decreased slightly upon adjustment for road traffic noise. Road traffic noise was weakly positively associated with the incidence of self-reported hypertension. Among 10 896 participants at risk, 3549 new cases of measured Hypertension occurred. They found no clear associations with measured Hypertension.

They concluded that long-term residential exposures to air pollution are associated with an increased incidence of self-reported hypertension.

2.12 Using GIS to explore association between road traffic noise, air pollution with hypertension

A study conducted in the metropolitan of Taichung, Taiwan, looked at the temporal and spatial variations in road traffic noise for different frequency components (Wang et al., 2016).

According to them, there is association of health effects related exposure to road traffic noise, but few studies report noise at different frequency characteristics. Therefore, the impetus is to assess 24-h noise levels and analyse their frequency components to investigate associations between seasons, meteorology, land-use types, and traffic. They gathered information on land-use types, road parameters, traffic flow rates, and meteorological variables to analyse the annual averages of road traffic noise and its frequency components.

The result showed that the annual average LAeq,24h in Taichung, was 66.4 ± 4.7 A-weighted decibels (dBA). They observed a Significant difference in LAeq,24h and frequency components between land-use types (all p-values < 0.001), but not between seasons, with the highest two noise levels of 71.2 ± 1.0 dBA and 70.0 ± 2.6 dBA measured in stream-channel and commercial areas, with the highest component being 61.4 ± 5.3 dBA at 1000 Hz. Road width, traffic flow rates, and land-use types were significantly associated with annual average LAeq,24h (all p-values < 0.050). Noise

levels at 125 Hz had the highest correlation with total traffic (Spearman's $\rho = 0.795$) and the highest prediction in the multiple linear regression ($R^2 = 0.803$; adjusted $R^2 = 0.765$). Furthermore, the findings reveal the spatial variation in road traffic noise exposure in Taichung. They observed highest correlation and predictive between this variation and noise levels at 125 Hz. They recommend that government agencies should take action to reduce noise levels from traffic vehicles (Wang et al., 2016).

Studies on frequency associations between noise exposure and health have been done by (Chang et al., 2019; Liu et al., 2016). Their studies revealed the use of the LUR model to predict road traffic noise at different frequencies. Their studies observed specific frequency associations between noise exposure and health effects. They reported that, most significant association of noise at 4000 Hz was prevalent and incidents of hypertension among workers (Chang et al., 2019).

Using spatial units and features of the area is a typical example of study on association of road traffic noise and air pollution in London from 2003-2010 (Fecht et al., 2015). A study was conducted for 190,000 postcodes in the UK. To explore associations between road traffic noise and air pollutants. They used UK's Calculation of Road Traffic Noise (CRTN) to find annual average of noise ($L_{Aeq,24\text{ h}}$, L_{den} , $L_{Aeq,16\text{ h}}$, L_{night}). They used a dispersion model (KCL urban) to measure initial dispersion of nitrogen dioxide, nitrogen oxide, ozone and $PM_{2.5}$ and PM_{10} from traffic only. They analysed noise pollution correlations at the postcode level (~50 people), and air concentration at 50 or 100 metre distance from major roads or deprivation tertiles. They considered spatial unit of postcodes stratified by London Boroughs (~240,000 people), neighbourhoods (Lower layer Super Output Areas) (~1600 people) and 1 km grid squares.

It is observed across all London postcodes that moderate correlations between model noise and air pollution is stable over time (Spearman's ρ range: 0.34-0.55).

Correlations varied depending on the spatial unit. Correlation is seen in largest ranges in neighbourhoods and 1 km grid squares (both Spearman's rho range: 0.01–0.87) and was less for Boroughs (Spearman's rho range: 0.21–0.78). There was little correlation between exposure tertiles, distance from road or deprivation tertiles (Fecht et al., 2015).

According to a study by Khan et al. (2020) on the spatial relationship between traffic-related air pollution and noise in two Danish cities: Implications for health-related studies. Air pollution and environmental noise originating from urban road traffic has been linked to adverse health effects, e.g., cardiovascular disease (CVD), although their generation and propagation mechanisms vary. The annual average (2005) air pollution (NO_x, NO₂, PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}) and noise levels (L_{day}, L_{eve}, L_{night}, L_{den}, L_{Aeq,24h}) at address locations in Copenhagen and Roskilde (N=11,000 and 1500) can be modelled. The new AirGIS system, and the Operational Street Pollution Model (OSPM), produce air pollution models. Noise pollution can be modelled using Common Noise Assessment Methods in the EU (CNOSSOSEU, hereafter CNOSSOS) with relatively coarser inputs (100 m CORINE land cover, simplified vehicle composition).

They compare noise estimation (L_{day}, L_{eve}, L_{night}) according to CNOSSOS with CRTN methods using Nordic noise prediction standards. The correlation between air concentration and noise pollution varied significantly (Spearman's rho range: 0.01-0.42), which was mainly affected by the background concentrations of air pollution and non-traffic emission sources. Moreover, neither AADT nor traffic speed substantially influenced the air-noise relationship. The noise levels estimated by CNOSSOS were substantially lower and showed much lower variation than levels obtained by RTN-96. CNOSSOS, therefore, needs to be further evaluated using more detailed inputs (e.g., 10m and cover polygons) to assess its feasibility for epidemiological noise exposure studies in Denmark. Lower to moderate air-noise correlations point towards the

significant potential to determine the independent health effects of air pollution (Khan et al., 2020).

Research, according to Khan et al., 2018, was conducted to estimate exposure to road traffic and air and noise pollution. Observation reflects a more extensive variety among air pollution models compared to the applied noise models. A GIS tool was to model combined exposure of traffic-related air and noise pollution using the geographical location of both exposures.

Work to understand the effects of urban road traffic on air and noise pollution has been reviewed (Khan et al., 2018) and highlight the importance of other contributing factors. these such as dispersion models applied, relevant Geographic Information System (GIS)-based tools, spatial scale of exposure assessment, study location, sample size, nature of traffic data, and detailed building geometry. The most popular assessment method for short- and long-term exposure to noise and air pollution is deterministic modelling. Compared to applied noise models, it was found that air pollution models had a wider variety The correlations between air and noise pollution vary widely (0.05–0.74) and depend on several factors, including traffic and building characteristics, and meteorological conditions (Khan et al., 2018).

Buildings serve as filters for the spread of pollutants, although the influence on noise pollution is far greater than that of air pollution. While also crucial for noise pollution, meteorology has a higher impact on air pollution levels than it does on noise. To aid in the facilitation of studies pertaining to health, there is a substantial potential for the development of a standard method to evaluate combined exposure to traffic-related air and noise pollution. The use of GIS is well established and has a significant capacity to simultaneously handle both exposures because of its spatial character (Khan et al., 2018).

2.13 Exploring the link between road traffic noise, air quality and public health– a review and perspective for a UK environmental health tracking system (EHTS)

The public health evaluation framework models available in the literature that provide the opportunity to address the joint associations of road traffic noise and air pollution with hypertension are evaluated. Through a systematic literature review, the implementation and policy integration and assessment of progress on selected issues of the joint cause-effect relationships between road traffic noise and air quality and implications for public health, particularly in relation to the UK and its devolved nations. The aim and objective of the study was to determine the suitability of the conceptual framework as well as demonstrating the application of the conceptual framework for an Environmental Health Tracking System (EHTS) for UK. Considering that the research is centered on selecting a conceptual framework for EHTS in the UK, the research would benefit from introducing what is a conceptual framework and why it is important to have one for an EHTS. A Conceptual Framework for the development of an EHTS relevant to the UK.

A conceptual framework model for environmental health tracking gives a systematic procedure that aids in the collection of factors and to examine issues linked to actual or predicted environmental health relationships (Eisenberg et al., 2007; McGeehin et al., 2004; Kyle et al., 2006; Edokpolo et al., 2019; Frank et al., 2019; Harwell et al., 2019). Furthermore, conceptual frameworks can join separate monitoring plan of action and assist development of new indicators, policies, legislation and plan of action (Niemeijer et al., 2008; Eriksson et al., 2017). Most common evaluations of conceptual frameworks were found to focus on five approaches: Driving Force-Pressure-State Exposure-Effect-Action (DPSEEA), Pressure-State-Response (PSR), Force-Pressure-State-Impact-Response (DPSIR), Multiple Exposures Multiple Effects (MEME) and Integrated Environmental Health Impact Assessment (IEHIA). Consequently, we focused on these conceptual framework models were examined to fit the content of the literature search terms suitable for reporting environmental and health issues in the UK.

A conceptual framework serves as a representation of the researcher's synthesis of the literature on how to explain a phenomenon. It lays out the procedures that must be done during the study given his past knowledge of other researchers' points of view and his observations about inquiry (Regoniel et al., 2015).

The conceptual framework "sets the scene" for the presentation of the specific research issue that motivates the reportable investigation based on the problem statement. The setting and problems that motivated the researcher to conduct the study are described in the problem statement of a thesis (McGaghie *et al.*, 2001).

Environmental public health tracking (EPHT), according to the UK Health Security Agency (UKHSA), is the use of public health data to assist in the management of threats that are both environmental and other. As part of its specialised responsibilities, EPHT gathers, compiles, and analyses environmental health data to help guide measures aimed at lowering the burden of disease (UKHSA, 2022). One of the key surveillance initiatives of the UKHSA is environmental public health surveillance system (EPHSS). EPHSS development is in two stages. A surveillance system for serious environmental incidents is part of the first phase. To report on the surveillance of the nature and amount of environmental health-related occurrences, this acute system connects with already-existing incident management systems, like City Inventory Reporting and Information System (CIRIS) and Health Protection Zone (HPZone).

The second phase began with initial user needs and design consultations. Broader environmental, exposure, and health databases for chronic events and exposures are added to the acute incident surveillance system. This stage aids in investigating connections between environmental exposures and health results (UKHSA, 2022).

Stakeholders prioritised two topics for the needs of intelligence and surveillance data. It is a method that advances knowledge of environmental public health and global health, enhances risk comparisons across geographical regions, promotes openness and trust among citizens, organisations, and the commercial sector, and supports preventative

decision-making (Lauriola et al., 2020). In order to locate, gather, compile, and analyse data intelligence and information on environmental dangers, exposures, and health effects, the system adopts a thorough and systematic strategy (Lauriola et al., 2020). In this study, selecting a conceptual framework for EHTS in the UK is key to locate, gather, compile, and analyse data intelligence and information on environmental dangers, exposures, and health, the system builds a thorough and systematic methodology.

The established Driving Forces, Pressures, State, Exposures, Health Effects and Actions (DPSEEA) framework can be strengthened with the aid of EPHT (Lauriola et al., 2020). In the context of actual drivers, pressures, and states, EPHT encourages a systematic integration of the DPSEEA components, considering environmental and health characteristics.

In this study, the DPSEEA conceptual framework (Driving force, Pressure, State, Exposure, Effect and Action) was used as the basis of a review focused on the main environmental health (EH) concerns and related actions in the two policy areas of road traffic noise and air quality (Frumkin et al., 2016) and extended to include association with hypertension. It summarizes the process of the implementation of an indicator system based on internationally agreed legislation, methodology and comparable data and gives an insight into the development of government action plans for environmental health indicators and the approaches for selecting a common goal. It also reviews the current strategic noise and air quality mapping and monitoring networks in UK identifying challenges of integrating these environmental indicators.

2.14 Conceptual framework for an Environmental Health Tracking System that link road traffic noise and air pollution with hypertension

The requirement of a conceptual framework is that it should have exact link between sources that effectively cause environmental change, and the causes related to effect on health with appropriate intervention put in place. Therefore, it is important to look out for the best conceptual framework component that fits a model for a UK EHTS.

Table 2:4: Components of conceptual frameworks linking environment and health

Conceptual Framework	Recommended components of a Conceptual Framework linking environment and health					
	Driving force	Pressure	State/ Hazard	Surveillance Exposure	Effect Impact Health	Action
PSR Pressure-State-Response [Levrel et al.,2009]		√		√		√
DPSIR Force-Pressure-State-Impact-Response [Wei et al., 2009]	√	√	√		√	√
MEME Multiple Exposures Multiple Effects [Change et al., 2015]				√	√	
IEHIA Integrated Environmental Health Impact Assessment [Huynen et al., 2015]	√	√	√		√	√
DPSEEA Driving Force-Pressure-State Exposure-Effect-Action [Chiabai et al., 2018]	√	√	√	√	√	√

Source (WHO, 2010)

The DSPEEA conceptual framework model appears to address the criteria highlighted in the literature review as indicated in Table 2:4. It covers the ongoing monitoring, integrated data and new data used in developing environmental health indicators. It showed the relationship of environmental exposure and health effects following their determining factors that associate environmental health tracking to public health action. Moreover, it identified intervention points along environmental health causal components and measure impacts of actions taken to improve health (Liu et al., 2012). It allows the intersection of road traffic noise and air pollution and the link to health impacts. Links and indicators based on environmental health such as the driving force of air-noise pollution and pressure of air-noise pollution on the environment were evaluated. The pressure alters the state of the environment, exposing the population to

air-noise pollution leading to adverse effects on human health and stimulates a response in the form of action plan. In 1995, WHO developed the DPSEEA framework to describe the cause-effect linkages between human health and environment (WHO, 1997) as a template to frame a general procedure for analysing environmental problems and related health effects. The DPSEEA model has been modified in various studies to focus on developing adaptive, flexible and innovative approaches that relate to other areas of environmental and public health (WHO, 2004; Morris et al., 2004; Ansare et al., 2009; Liu et al., 2012; Hambling et al., 2011; Reis et al., 2015). The adoption of this framework to address this topic is summarised in Figure 2:2 below.

2.15 Application of DPSEEA framework as Surveillance to review links between noise and air pollution with hypertension

The DPSEEA conceptual framework provides an effective review method to more effectively, conduct data surveillance monitoring and assessment, and tracking outcomes with different types of evidence in the field of environmental public health. There is great scope demonstrating the use of the DPSEEA conceptual framework to highlight the casual relationship between exposure and effects taking into account other factors such as driving force, pressure, state, exposure and action and to incorporate as surveillance information in the environmental health tracking system (EHTS).

2.16 Driving force

The driving force for air-noise pollution from traffic due to the increase population across the UK (EEA, 2006), have resulted in incorporating extensive highway systems. More recent evidence suggests that urbanization, economic development activities (industrialization, service sector) and transport are the main drivers for the increase in environmental noise (EEA, 2014; WHO, 2012; ENE, 2020). Between 1990 and 2018, road traffic increased by 29% in the UK due to growth in travel from 255 to 328 billion miles (DfT, 2018).

This has driven a rapid increase in the passenger transport, raising tensions in the urban planning and in Europe has led to the END and Air quality directive. The END imposes on its members the need to present noise maps and more importantly give responsibility to local authorities to implement action plans for larger urban areas, major roads, railways and airports, with the aim to reduce the populations' exposure to noise.

Figure 2:2: Modified DPSEEA framework for the assessment of the joint cause-effect relationship between road traffic noise, air pollution and hypertension (Adza et al, 2022)

However, few members completed the second round of noise mapping and presented action plans from agglomerations (EEA, 2014; Environmental Protection, United Kingdom, 2008; DEFRA, 2011).

The UK Air Quality Strategy was implemented due to the EU directive on air quality to improve air quality across its regions through a framework that regulates and preserves the environment and the health of humans (Barnes et al., 2018), with an increasing number of studies identifying a need to prevent global burden attributed to cardiovascular disease (Lim et al., 2012; Bromfield et al., 2013).

2.17 Pressure

The pressure on the environment drives exposure of the population in different landscapes to hazardous sound levels and concentrations of pollutants. Built environments such as residential developments, workplaces and aggregations into neighbourhoods where noisy activities are sustained for longer than 8 hours per day may result in exposure of residents and employees to potentially hazardous noise emissions (Adza et al., 2021).

The increase in gross domestic product, industrialization and passenger transport exerts pressure on the environment. Mattioli et al. (2020) call into question some past assumption that there will be increase in car ownership because of individual increase in gross domestic income. Furthermore, a significant increase in transportation relating to higher frequency and longer distance of trips is expected (Barber, 2012; Krzyżanowski, 2005).

Even though noise and air pollution from cars and trucks has been reduced by more than 85% and 90% respectively, road traffic noise has not been significantly reduced during the last 15 years (Jones et al., 2019). Therefore, it can be deduced that external cost of noise is not negligible compared to the cost of air pollution (EEA, 2014).

It has long been acknowledged that one of the pressures exerted on environment is change in use of land for the development of transportation systems (Litman (1995). The advances in extent of traffic lanes and high construction levels and the extension

of cities result in modification of land use that is typically related to population growth, consequently placing most inhabitants close to road systems and its intrinsically associated air and noise pollution (Kasraian 2016). The proximity to the road network is a direct influence on employment density, land cover and population compared to rail development (Simmonds 2004), and transport infrastructure influences the decisions of residents and industry in several ways.

One of the major drawbacks exerting pressure on the environment is individual human dependency. Human behaviours such as regular use of automobile vehicle for transportation have contributed to personal vulnerability, risk of exposure, and traffic congestion or influence the intensity of environmental pressures. People prefer to be housed close to the roadside for easy movement between town and home (TSGB, 2019). Unfortunately, there are no reduction but rather pressure from the increased concentration of air pollutants in the environment such as greenhouse emissions and particulate matter. The UK government has adopted a clean air strategy (DEFRA, 2019) and air quality plan for nitrogen dioxide in 2017 to examine how it can be reduced.

2.18 State

Both road traffic noise and air pollution have common source from road traffic loads (ENE, 2020). They occur on the road from the vehicle engine. The traffic noise is caused by noise frequency directly from the vehicle, created by vehicle tires and the engine (Cohen, 2017). Inadequate regulations governing carrier emissions pollutant from non-exhaust such as vehicle tyre, brake wear and road abrasion can lead to increase in pollution emissions associated with traffic (DfT, 2019).

Air pollution is also caused by emission from the exhaust of vehicle and this emission combining with dust particle to form aerosol (Health Effects Institute (HEI), 2010). The factors influencing vehicle emissions are vehicle features, traffic activities and weather conditions. They include vehicle features (e.g., type of vehicle and fuel, function of the vehicle, vehicle engine, size of vehicle, efficiency of fuel, standards and technology for

emission regulation), traffic conditions (e.g., traffic a distance, traffic capacity, average speed of traffic flow, regulation for traffic signal and limit to traffic speed) and weather conditions (wind speed, direction of wind, snow, rainfall, sunlight and temperature of air).

The state of knowledge on road noise exposure and population exposed are reported over a 5-year cycle to the EEA from 2007, 2012 and 2017 by END of the UK government (Jarosińska et al., 2018).

2.19 Exposure

Data reported from strategic noise mapping in the UK in December 2017 on the number of people in agglomerations exposed to noise from roads (Lden and Lnight) in the various regions of the UK are described below in Figure 2:3.

Figure 2:3: Average number of people on agglomerations from UK exposed to noise from roads (Lden and Lnight) (Source: Transparency data, 2019).

Figure 2:3 shows the average number of people in agglomerations in various countries exposed to noise from roads (Lden and LnightM). The data show that, in all the four countries of the UK, the average number of people exposed in the different noise bands were greater during the day than at night.

In Europe and under the Environmental Noise Directive (2002/49/EC), a common framework methodology for measurement of noise exposure was initiated and called the Common Noise Assessment Method. This was initiated due to differences in approach to data collection and monitoring techniques across EU member states. It was established to provide knowledge on noise levels and health-related problems of the European citizens so that an action plan and effective preventive measures would be implemented to prevent exposure to hazardous noise level (Kephelopoulos, 2012-2014). In 2017, this took effect, and a third round of strategic noise mapping was implemented, making measurements of noise at a range of frequency (from 125 Hz to 4000 Hz) valid for road traffic. Calculations are performed in octave bands for road traffic. Environmental noise is the effect following an exposure to the frequency or wave of the noise (Brainard et al., 2004).

Figure 2:4: Total UK Road transport emissions 1990-2017(Source : Jones et al., 2019)

Figure 2:4 shows the level of air pollutant concentrations, particulate of matter (PM) and Greenhouse gases (GHG) of road transport emissions in UK. Data source from the study by Jones et al., 2019 show enormous increase in carbon monoxide in road transport emissions by vehicles in the UK resident basis. The total emissions of GHG in the UK decreased between 1990 and 2017 by 32%. Total emission of GHG related to transport in the UK has, however, risen over the same period by 6%. Therefore, in 2019, it was concluded that over 27% of emissions of GHG in UK was related to road transport (National statistics, 2019).

2.20 Effect

According to the UK Government statistics on air pollution, it is estimated that the life expectancy of every person is reduced by an average of 7–8 months, incurring a related cost of up to £20 billion each year. (EEA, 2014; Ricardo Energy & Environment, 2019). Several financial losses are incurred across regions of the UK due to the burden of disease. For example, over £2 billion is lost due to the current estimate of annual burden attributed to hypertension in England and other regions of the UK have yet to be assessed by the NHS. (EEA, 2014; Ricardo Energy & Environment, 2019). Annual effect due to long-term exposure to air pollution is equal to 28,000 to 36,000 deaths in the UK (COMEAP, 2011). A report on costs of air pollution and air quality damage reveals the update on cost damage and effect of pollutants in UK (EEA, 2014; Ricardo Energy & Environment, 2019). Similar studies have been undertaken assessing the cost of environmental noise due to hypertension in the UK (Hardingetal et al., 2013).

Studies from the UK on road traffic noise and air pollution and their joint effect on hypertension is not clear. However, hypertension is the third most common disease in the UK according to NHS (Public Health England, 2017). In the UK, data from a health survey on estimation of prevalence of hypertension around areas in England reveals that about 11.8 million adults had hypertension, equating to 22.6% of the population

(Hypertension prevalence estimates in England, 2017). Scottish Public Health Observation (ScotPHO, 2020) estimate that the risk of hypertension is high and can lead to major death cases. The prevalence sharply increased from ages 16 years and above in 2019 (ScotPHO, 2020). On the other hand, the prevalence in Wales increased by 15.8% between 2018 and 2019 and is currently the most prevalent morbidity (Quality and Outcomes Framework Statistics for Wales (QOF), 2019). Nonetheless, according to Northern Ireland Quality and outcome framework Statistics (QOF), 2020), the prevalence of hypertension is 14.0%, making it the most prevalent morbidity in Northern Ireland.

Table 2:5: PAF for risk factors for all-cause YLLs rate per 100,000 population for England, Scotland, Wales, and Northern Ireland, both genders, 2016 (Source: Steel et al., 2018)

PAF=population attributable risk fraction. YLLs = years of life lost.

Region	Hypertension PAF%	Air pollution PAF%
England	13.04	4.04
Scotland	14.62	3.87
Wales	15.53	3.91
Northern Ireland	14.99	3.58

Unfortunately, low levels of CO, PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} emissions still have implications for human health in the UK (DEFRA, 2019).

Ischaemic heart disease, lung cancers, cerebrovascular disease, and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease led to second highest death (YLLs) in UK at national and regional level according to a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease (GDB) 2016 study (Steel et al., 2018). A study by Bromfield et al. (2013) shows that, hypertension is a risk factor of most morbidities in the world. Therefore, the impetus to conduct

prevention programmes for the world. It is estimated that about 1.6%, 9.8%, 12.6% and premature deaths in the world are caused by hypertensive heart disease (WHO, 2021; WHO, 2017), cerebrovascular disease and ischaemic heart disease, respectively. Worldwide, WHO Global burden of Disease 2013, 2015, 2017 studies have concluded that between 13.5% and 1.4% deaths are attributable to hypertension, but new causes have been added in arterial hypertension (Vox et al., 2020) and to urban air pollution (Bromfield et al, 2013).

According to data from END on noise estimation of burden of disease, it is estimated that the DALYs attributable to noise effect on health output were approximately 156,000 years for heart disease for most European countries and the UK (ENE, 2020). The western Europe countries are part of those who experienced the largest DALYs lost from environmental noise, the estimations are 61000, 45000, 903000, 22000, 654000 years for ischaemic heart disease, cognitive, impairment of children, sleep disturbance, tinnitus and annoyance, respectively. This makes sleep disturbance and annoyance most of the burden of environmental related to road traffic noise constitute in European countries and the UK. The overall consideration for the burden of disease can range from 1.0–1.6 million DALYs. This connotes that road traffic noise impacts increase every year. Approximately 1 million healthy life years are lost in the western European countries and the UK, including the EU Member States (ENE, 2020). Europe have recorded one of the highest effects following noise pollution. New cases record approximately 48,000 cases of ischaemic heart disease. Unfortunately, 12,000 premature deaths are estimated to be caused by noise in the environment from road traffic, railways, aircraft and industry (ENE, 2020).

Studies carried out in London by Halonen et al. (2015) on association of exposure to road noise with hypertension concluded that there was some association in terms of morbidity in the general population. This was due to long-term exposure effect leading

to increased all-cause mortality and adverse cardiovascular outcomes especially stroke among the elderly group.

Few studies in UK have considered the joint association of road traffic noise and air pollution with health problems. A group of researchers in London have looked at the effect of both road traffic noise and air pollution on foetal growth (Smith et al., 2017). A retrospective cohort study from Greater London setting and surroundings up to 2317 km², UK was conducted. It included over 540 365 singleton term live births participants, making the research the largest study up to date in UK and the world. The association of the joint effect revealed that there was confounding associations between long-term exposure to traffic-related air pollution but less association attributable to road traffic noise. This means birth weight reduced after long-term exposure to air pollution especially exposure to PM_{2.5} traffic-exhaust but no association was found for road traffic noise after adjustment for relevant factors. It was estimated that 3% of term low birth weight (LBW) cases in London were directly attributable to residential exposure to PM_{2.5} >13.8 µg/m³ during pregnancy. The authors concluded that air pollution has effect on foetal growth in London but little evidence on the part of road traffic noise (Smith et al., 2017).

It has been suggested that road traffic noise should be considered an independent risk factor for health outcomes separate to that of air pollution as demonstrated in the studies by Smith et al. (2017) and Stansfeld et al. (2015), even though Smith et al. (2017) agree that there is limited evidence on the association between road traffic noise and birth weight.

A narrative review by Stansfeld et al. (2015) assessed the joint association of environmental air-noise pollution with health outcomes such as hypertension, myocardial infarction, stroke, mortality and cognitive. The findings of the review show that after adjustment for air pollution, there were independent effects of environmental noise from road traffic on cardiovascular outcomes. Comparative burden of disease

studies also demonstrates that air pollution is the primary environmental cause of DALYs. Environmental noise is ranked second in terms of DALYs in Europe, and the DALYs attributed to noise were more than those attributed to lead, ozone and dioxins (Stansfeld et al., 2015).

2.21 Action

2.21.1 Implementation of Policy and legislation for environmental noise in the UK

Various countries have taken initiative to address environmental noise and air quality. There is mitigation measure to tackle cardiovascular health impacts as result of traffic noise and air pollution effect (Curran et al., 2013).

Government of various devolved regions in the UK have made significant steps to enable the relevant EU directives. Studies conducted by the devolved regions of the UK include strategic noise mapping for major roads, rail, airports, and industry agglomeration to check environmental noise for relevant authorities such as transport agencies to make an action plan. Various criteria were used to select the transportation links that were modelled at the major road level. Therefore, the first-round model looked at roads with more than 6,000,000 vehicle passages per year in agglomerations with a population of more than 250,000. The second-round model looked at roads with more than 3,000,000 vehicle passages per year of agglomerations with a population of more than 100,000 (one hundred thousand) and were part of the strategic noise mapping and action planning. The strategic noise maps for END Round 3 (for 2017) were produced using a computer-based prediction methodology, and the outputs can be found on the DEFRA and Noise Mapping website of various government platforms (TNAP, 2019). Strategic noise mapping methodology is based on modelled data and does not directly collect population exposure to noise levels over a range of different frequencies. In addition, the estimation of the relationship between the burden of disease and air and

noise pollution has several assumptions and high levels of uncertainty. However, the assessment of road traffic noise at different noise frequency range has been evaluated (Kephalopoulos, 2012-2014).

Noise Action plan 2018 to 2023 was suggested by the devolved regions of the UK to deal with major agglomerations. The Glasgow action plan suggests that possible restoration actions of noise management with cost benefit analysis will be considered from any party that proposes an action plan. Also, the action plan will be tested whether the proposed action will be useful and affordable. Currently an agreement according to Paris agreement on Zero emission vehicles (ZEV) is ongoing through transition council action plan. These action plans are focused beyond 2022 to charging infrastructure, carbon dioxide or fuel efficiency standards and regulations, pace of the transition and technology choices for zero emission heavy duty vehicles and ensure the ZEV transition is truly global (COP26, 2021).

2.21.2 Implementation of Policy and legislation for air quality in UK

The EU passed an air quality directive (2008/50/EC), which devolved responses to member states monitor and manage air quality. The EU sets limits of concentrations for ambient (outdoor) air of major air pollutants which became legal agreement binding UK and the EU. The limit was binding to air pollutant which has adverse health effects on human including particulate matter (PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}) and nitrogen dioxide (EU Legislation and policy, 2015). The 2008 directive was made law in all regions of UK through the Air Quality Standards Regulations 2010 including integrating the 4th air quality daughter directive (2004/107/EC).

An Air Quality Improvement framework was established across UK linked to the Air Quality Strategy (2007) that was formed in line with requirement of the EU directive. Furthermore, the purpose of the strategy was to enact the Air Quality Standard and objectives to regulate air quality to protect the health of humans. However, air quality

in UK is solely the responsibility of individual devolved regions (Barnes et al., 2018). This in turn identified Air Quality Management Areas with an associated action plan to curb air quality beyond the recommended limit by national, regional and local authorities according to gravity of the air quality issues (AQMA, 2015). The local authorities of Scotland and Northern Ireland and other regions in UK under the Part IV of The Environment Act 1995 enable them to implement air quality action plan. This action plan aims to reduce pollution in an area as part of approach to the strategy objectives at a local level and to achieve air quality limit values.

The local authority is responsible under an AQMA to bring about action plan and arrange how problems will be sorted. Between 2000 and 2002, Air Quality Regulations and Air Quality Amendment Regulations in Scotland were enacted following a tighter objective for carbon monoxide, fine particulate matter and benzene. The strictest objective in UK is the fine particulate matter (PM₁₀) (AQMA, 2015). However, Amendment Regulations on Air Quality (2016) were presented, and Scotland was the first region in the UK to embrace the WHO recommended criteria for PM_{2.5} fine particulate matter into legislation.

According to the Cleaner Air for Scotland (CAFS, 2016), there were thirty-eight AQMAs in fourteen local authority areas, with two announcing breaches due to emission from transport impacting on nitrogen dioxide and/or PM₁₀. The Scottish Environmental Protection Agency (SEPA) review these to enforce strategy and action plans to address air quality targets. In CAFS (2017), 40 actions plans were identified to reduce air pollution. Furthermore, this action has led to targeting the greatest reductions in total constituent pollutant levels. Air quality monitoring has increased as a result and progress on model criteria for regions and major cities has improved as a result of the action being taken. As part of the action, the Low Emission Zone (LEZ) is in progress and operates in all regions in UK especially Scotland and London to curb vehicles that produce more pollution using heavy diesel to become cleaner. Major cities

have embraced the approach in UK. In Scotland, LEZ have been introduced in Glasgow (LEZ, 2018) but in London LEZ standard for heavier vehicles came in October 2020 (Tougher LEZ emissions standard) (LEZ, 2018). In 2021, other AQMAs such as (Zero Emission Vehicles Transition Council (ZEVTC)) have been established where such an approach will be supported by evidence (COP26, 2021).

Effort to reduce emission in UK can be transposed into the initiative taken to reach zero emissions (Road to zero strategy, 2018) by 2050. Hence, to target the reduction of emission, 0.5% of all vehicles with ultra-low emission were licensed at the end of 2018. Emissions of nitrogen dioxide, carbon monoxide, and particulate matter (PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}) from road transport have fallen from 4.5 million tonnes, 16,000 tonnes and 17,000 tonnes respectively between 1990, 2002 and 2017 by 77 %, (DfT, 2019).

The implementation of the regulations particularly the Euro exhaust emission limits regulation aimed to improve air quality by reducing the emissions of these pollutants (Pastorello et al., 2016). There are various guidelines stipulated by the WHO for UK and other member state for exposure to particulate of matter concentration. According to the guidelines, exposure concentration of PM_{2.5} should not be greater than 10 µg/m³ or 25 µg/m³ for annual mean or 24-hour mean, respectively.

2.21.3 Air quality network

UK regions have monitoring networks for air pollution. The UK DEFRA handle issues pertaining to Air Quality management and monitoring. The government of the various regions are responsible for air quality management. Hence, they have website concerning air pollution monitoring which are used as a platform to disseminate information and counsel to adult and children (O'Brien, 2016). Various websites of the regional governments publish daily air quality forecasts, accessible to the public through the internet to report on air pollution in their area. Most of the Air Quality monitoring website measurements for air pollution are based on hourly limits. The results from air quality network database are single measurement points. Based on the

system of banding (COMEAP, 2011), various regions in UK use Daily Air Quality Index for their forecast.

2.22 Estimation of a standard for burden of disease

According to WHO, population health can be estimated using disability adjusted life years lost (DALYs). DALYs were used to estimate global burden of disease (2000-2016) for which the UK happened to be part. The Disability Weights show the various stages and its relative intensity to be included in a survey of determined population health. There is a different valuation method that is agreed in UK to assess hypertension; however, many countries in the western Europe also use different valuation approaches. The visual analogue scale, the time trade-off technique, and the person trade-off technique are the three valuation methods that were used to measure level of agreement of disability weight (WHO, 2018).

Several financial losses are incurred across regions of UK due to burden of disease. For example, over £2 billion is lost due to the current estimate of annual burden attributable to hypertension in England and other regions in UK are yet to be assessed by the National Health Service (NHS). In response to this environmental health issue, policies and legislation have been laid down to address and further reduce the impact of air pollution. Therefore, an action plan called prevention, detection and management of high blood pressure was developed as an approach to tackle hypertension by the support of group of leaders in both national and local government, health and academia system including the voluntary sector (Tackling High Blood Pressure, 2014). However, in 2017, an update on an additional approach to action plan added a cross-cutting initiative looking at the approaches taken in two or more of the previous action plans (Jamie, 2018).

Results of studies on the association of road traffic noise with hypertension provide a relatively consistent perspective, but studies on the joint association of road traffic noise and air pollution with hypertension are sparse.

This review highlights a lack of direct measurement of exposure data on traffic noise at different frequency range in UK. However, ongoing predictive exposure data are computed methodically to determine the environmental noise based on road movement in their regions coherent with the EU Directive 2002/49/EC based on road traffic noise levels and exposed population. This is limited to major roads and urban agglomerations with populations of 100,000 to 250,000. It is evident that data from noise mapping is not extended across the regions and population of UK.

Result from noise calculation is depicted in noise bands of an interval of 5 or 4-dB at L den _ 55 dB (an average of day, evening, and night) and at night (L night) _ 50 dB, but it is hypothesized in this study that different frequency characteristics of traffic noise are appropriate for a forecast of harmful health consequences for the population. They could be useful in delineating areas where noise problem exists and for setting health-related noise limits.

There is a strong guideline stipulated by the WHO for UK and other EU member states for exposure to particulate of matter. According to the guidelines, exposure concentration of PM_{2.5} should not be greater than 10 µg/m³ or 25 µg/m³ for annual mean or 24-hour mean, respectively. This is used by various air quality website subregions of UK.

According to the update on monitoring air quality in UK, the daily risk factor of exposure to concentration of pollutant, GHG and particulate of matter risk are reported daily in forecast and neglecting daily monitoring of noise. A single exposure to noise will not cause significant health effect, but the sustained exposure and average noise levels on a regular basis will be important considerations. Noise monitoring network is needed. Therefore, it is important to report daily traffic noise and the daily risk of exposure of road traffic noise.

A joint impact of air and noise pollution can be deductive even though noise has a role in hearing impairment. Noise pollution is the primary environmental cause of DALYs.

Furthermore, noise may also be a risk factor for several diseases such as hypertensive heart disease. Therefore, it is expedient to assess the joint cause-effect of air and noise pollution relating to hypertension due to road traffic. However, the joint effect of environmental noise and air pollution is not clear in UK. Data on estimation of comparative burden of disease studies demonstrated in UK point out that air pollution is the primary environmental cause of DALYs (Stansfeld et al., 2015). Environmental noise is ranked second in terms of DALYs in Europe and UK, and the DALYs attributed to noise were more than those attributed to lead, ozone and dioxins (Stansfeld et al., 2015). Therefore, it is suggested that compartmental model may be a more robust approach of describing joint relationship of the burden of hypertension disease that causes the DALYs.

Air and noise pollution from urban road traffic are the most common environmental pollution issues across society. The integration of both aspects with health impacts is missing in public health assessment. Methodologies to assess their synergistic contribution are also lacking.

Challenges such as the constant and persistent increase in nitrogen dioxide, carbon dioxide and particulate of matter emissions at places and around UK along with the merger of air quality and climate change and delivery of a coherent air quality strategy. Air quality monitoring networks look at both short- and long-term limits. Integrating noise measurements needs to consider persistence of “noise scapes” for the exposed population.

Also, a study conducted in Shirdi, India, found that both noise level and air pollution exceeded the recommended limit. The authors recommended that the government should put action plans in place such as facilitating proper management traffic signals properly. Secondly, the government should divert all the traffic for another subway. Thirdly, the government should declare Shirdi city as “No Horn city.” Fourthly, the government should put measures in place to control emission of particulate. Finally,

they suggested that government should conduct a long-term study on concentrations of particulate matter in the spatial and temporal dimension of various cities due to current development in infrastructures (Kankal et al., 2011).

Night-time noise related issues such as endothelial dysfunction and arterial hypertension have been proven to occur because of high levels of stress hormones and vascular oxidative stress due to noise exposure at night (Schmidt et al., 2013; Münzel, 2018; Herzog et al., 2019).

Community noise is an important concern of the household persons. Various elements concerning a person's environment near road can lead to or predispose him to developing a disease process. Community hazards that are causing growing concern now is noise and air pollution. Urban road traffics are one such source with high noise levels and air pollution because of their traffic activities. There is no doubt that road transport has economic significance. However, the effects they have cause. To the household persons in terms of excessive air-noise pollution levels cannot be overlooked. During the given period, all noise measurements in Greater Glasgow exhibited exceedances. Noise levels that have been measured may be harmful to people' health.

Chapter 3

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Selecting Suitable Research Methodologies

3.2 Methods

The first phase assessed the development of a conceptual framework for environmental health tracking system (EHTS) (Kyle et al., 2006; Edokpolo et al., 2019) focused on issues of road traffic noise, air quality and public health in the UK.

A viable EHTS in UK will require:

1. operational potential in the UK
2. a useable conceptual framework model
3. emerging and specific environmental health indicators
4. a technical operational plan for the system design
5. application with available data; and
6. assessment of the outcome

3.3 Study Design and Targeted Population

The study design is an analytical cross-sectional design. This study was conducted to allow for data collection at one point in time.

Road traffic levels of NO₂, PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} pollutants and traffic exposure (noise at different components of frequencies) of community households in association with the prevalence of hypertension were assessed.

The registered population with NHS Scotland is 5,626,383 million. Information from the NHS Scotland database of 776,579 hypertension patients' registrations and the rates per 13.80 people were linked with the national health survey in Scotland. Each patient population at GP practice level of hypertension disease registrations and rates per 13.80 people were geocoded, so nobody was disqualified for a missing geocode (ISD, 2019).

This study linked the national health survey called Scottish Health Survey (SHeS) conducted in 2020 to the NHS Scotland database. The Scottish Health Survey (SHeS) has data with information on 33,932 population of adults aged over 16+ years. There was missing data in the system for the 32012 population. Therefore, missing data was excluded. Essentially this study used 1920 subjects, exactly 813 males and 1107 females could be included and had full data set. Therefore, only 1920 subjects were included in the data analysis from the SHeS.

3.4 Data Source and Outcome

3.5 Source of Data

3.6 Primary Data

Primary data was gathered from field work on road traffic noise monitoring (community noise) at (Glasgow High Street, Glasgow Townhead, East Dunbartonshire Bishopbriggs, East Dunbartonshire Kirkintilloch, and Glasgow Kerbside) urban areas.

3.7 Secondary Data

Secondary data on the other hand was culled from registers from Disease Prevalence data (ISD) at GP practices in Scotland on the NHS Scotland database (SPIRE).

This study involves registry information regarding the population and proportion of registered cases on hypertension register and hypertension rate patients from various areas in Scotland, including Greater Glasgow. The database includes all hypertension registers and hypertension rates covered by hospitals nationwide as part of the disease prevalence at GP offices in Scotland.

Data on disease prevalence at GP offices in Scotland, ISD, February 2020. The data used to create the Disease Prevalence “Data Visualization” displayed on the ISD Website are contained in this study.

For 17 illnesses, disease registrations and rates per 100 people are shown at the Scottish, NHS Board, HSCP, Cluster, and GP practice levels. This study looked at hypertension register and hypertension rate.

Since data are not accessible for all practices, illness registrations aggregated at the HSCP (and occasionally Cluster level) and higher are likely to be understated.

Statistics on disease prevalence are based on April 1, the year after the fiscal year. Data for 2018–19, for instance, is based on April 1, 2019.

A select few practises that supplied data on April 1 of a given year, even though they did not submit an extract. The ISD website provides total patient populations at the HSCP, Board, and Scotland levels (ISD, 2019). This study used data on the years 2018–19 consisting of 911 practices. Only practises open as of October 2019 are included in the data. QOF Calculator, as a source. Data was not uploaded for several practises because QOF Calculator was no longer supported after QOF terminated in 2016. (QOF for ISD, 2016). Data is no longer accessible using the QOF calculator as of April 2019. This will eventually be obtained through SPIRE.

Survey (questionnaire and interview) data was extracted from the Scottish Health Survey that can be found on the UK data service database.

The data addressed concerns about a person’s personality, general health, household composition, CVD and diabetes, asthma, COVID-19, physical activity, diet, smoking, alcohol, dental health, food insecurity, social capital and loneliness, mental wellbeing, self-reported height and weight, ethnic background, and religion.

The SHeS data consist of person number in the household grid and address of origin. Missing values are represented as “Not Applicable”, “Refused”, and “Don’t Know”. The SHeS apply other missing value conventions (-2 and -6) in earlier SHeS surveys.

Private households are widespread in the metropolis. Thus, household persons can be easily accessible. These techniques also allow readily available data to be chosen based on various requirements, such as an opt-in survey.

The households in the survey are those who participated after getting in touch with ScotCen Social Research through initial telephone contact. Individuals in households 16 years of age and older were allowed to participate in an interview. The model considered the following variables: the health board, age, gender, number of adults living there, employment status, marital status, tenure, rural status, and their SIMD15 region. The survey sampling method was multi-stage stratified. Random Sampling randomly selected eleven thousand addresses from the Postcode Address File (PAF).

The survey included the following variables in the final model by running backwards and forwards selection methods for the logistic regression: Age, gender, marital status, health board, number of adults living there and addresses within SIMD15.

In total, 1,920 adults answered the SHeS 2020 telephone survey. Health Board areas, local governments, and SIMD quintiles, respectively, indicate the number of adults per productive address and the number of achieved interviews as a proportion of the number of adults in productive households.

SHeS conducted interviews for each productive home with, on average, 1.69 adults living there, and 81.9% of them. The proportion of adults in families interviewed varied among the Health Board areas, from 88.2% in Orkney to 75.5% in the percentage of Isles (where there are most adults per household, at 1.9). (Where there were 1.62 adults per productive household).

The proportion of adults in productive families who were interviewed varied among local authority areas, from 67.3 per cent in East Renfrewshire (where there were 1.88 adults per family) to 91.3 per cent in Angus (where there were 1.64 adults per household).

Each SIMD quintile had a proportion of individuals interviewed in productive homes that ranged from 80.8 to 83 per cent, which is comparable. However, as degrees of deprivation decreased, the number of adults per abundant address rose, rising from 1.49 in the most deplorable places to 1.84 in the least disagreeable. Resulting in a significant skew in the number of responding adults in each deprivation quintile, going from 294 in the most deprivation areas to 619 in the minor deprivation areas, combined with the rising response rate as deprivation reduced. The method used the weighting strategy uneven distribution of responses across the quintiles.

Weighting is before the final stage of calibration. Weighted totals survey data matches NRS 2019 mid-year population estimates for Health Boards, age/gender distribution at the Scotland level, and age/gender distribution for the Glasgow and Greater Clyde Health Board. The household and non-response were combined and applied to the survey data.

The SHeS is a commission by the Scottish Government Health Directorates. The Scottish Government Health Directorates established the SHeS series in 1995 to provide data about the health of the population living in private households in Scotland. It was repeated in 1998 and 2003 and has been carried out annually since 2008.

The Scottish Health Survey (SHeS) series is a study that provides national data to target the health of one or more people in various communities with private households in Scotland in cases of hypertension. They conduct surveys of the space from 2018 to 2021 in collaboration with the Office for National Statistics (ONS), the Social and Public

Health Sciences Unit (MRC/CSO SPSU) at the University of Glasgow, the Centre for Population Health Sciences at the University of Edinburgh, and the Public Health Nutrition Research Group at the University of Aberdeen by the ScotCen Social Research.

During the COVID 19 pandemic, it was essential to assess the population's health at the national level through the SHeS (questionnaire and interview) following the sixteenth face-to-face survey series. Unfortunately, the COVID 19 pandemic made things impossible to move forward with the survey after March 2020. Therefore, in August and September 2020, an alternative SHeS 2020 telephone survey commenced gathering credible information being that information was inaccessible by operational/administrative databases in GPs and hospitals. On the other hand, the population's health and its relationship with the lifestyle factor data during the COVID 19 pandemic were not accessible. Furthermore, it was important for the government to have this health data. If the pilot study is feasible, knowing that people cannot access health services frequently.

The SHeS 2020 telephone survey is drafted to assess the adult population data among the communities in private households from August to September 2020. They collected report over a short period in 2020 (from August 5 to September 23), and it was impossible to capture data at the outset and in the early days of the COVID-19 pandemic when restrictions were at their most wide-ranging.

Measurements of height and weight are taken during interviews, as is standard practice for the Scottish Health Survey. Participants were requested to submit these measures independently since this was impossible during the telephone survey.

According to other studies, self-reported measurements typically overestimate height and underestimate the weight.

The self-reported metrics were adjusted using adjustment factors based on a comparison study done for the Health Survey for England to help resolve this ‘_adj’ denotes adjusted height, weight, and BMI DVs. The derived variable specification contains the syntax for these modifications. The 2020 Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation is used to compile the data from the telephone survey (SIMD, 2020). A “20” is present in the variable name, SIMD20 RPA, to denote the new SIMD quintiles. You can read more about SIMD, including how it’s calculated. SIMD is a comparative indicator of disadvantage across 6,976 local regions in the Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation (called data zones). If a place is labelled as “deprived,” this may refer to people having poor incomes, but it may also indicate fewer resources or possibilities available. Income, employment, education, health, access to services, crime, and housing are the seven categories that SIMD examines to determine the degree of deprivation in a community. Much helpful information, including the study’s history and future distribution goals, can be found on the Scottish Health Survey website (SHeS, 2020).

Participating households included in the survey were those from which a participant or participants took part after contacting ScotCen social research to opt-in. The primary interview questions’ data and extra variables derived from respondents’ answers are included in the SHeS 2020 telephone survey dataset. The SHeS 2020 telephone survey dataset also included disclosure control techniques from 2014 onward, which are stated in the variable listing.

All adults aged 16 and over within these households were eligible for interviews and were allowed to participate once they had made initial telephone contact. An opt-in approach was used, whereby potential participants were initially contacted by letter to invite them to participate and only re-contacted for an interview if they advised ScotCen social research that they were willing to participate. This typically leads to higher levels of non-response than is typical for SHeS due to the lack of an interviewer visit to

encourage participation. Weighting is used to account for non-response and various selection probabilities. They modified the 2020 telephone survey methodology, weighting from the 2019 approach to account for the lower number of completed interviews and other changes in participant patterns via telephone that is not visible in the face-to-face survey.

While there is a degree of self-selection bias in the traditional SHeS survey model, this is greater for an opt-in survey. To reduce bias, suppose preference is known to only relate to demographic factors, such as gender, age, and area deprivation. In that case, weighting can correct these (see section 1.7 of the appendix for more on the weighting approach); however, there is the potential for opt-in bias to relate to factors such as someone's health or health behaviours. Independent of the demographic factors considered part of the weighting process, telephone survey estimates are likely to differ, to some extent, from the actual population figures.

In-depth briefings were given before fieldwork to experienced interviewers who had previously worked on the face-to-face SHeS. Key differences from the face-to-face survey were noted, and the briefing addressed the survey's protocols in full. Interviewers received complete written instructions covering survey methods before beginning their job.

Ten percent of productive homes were recalled. These recalls verified with the interviewees that interviewers had interviewed following the correct survey methods.

The interviewers' computer programme also contained built-in soft checks (which can be suppressed) and hard checks (which cannot be hidden) linked to specific interview questions, in addition to the recall technique. These checks were triggered and shown as a warning message on the interviewers' laptops whenever answers that were unusual, implausible, or outside of a predetermined range were entered.

The interviewer is either advised to review the entered response once more (a soft-check) or is requested to make changes (a hard-check). As an illustration, a hard check was performed to ensure the age listed in the home grid for each participant matched the date of birth input and the interview date.

However, unlike hard checks, soft checks could be suppressed. A notice displayed requesting the interviewer to check and confirm that the entry was accurate, for instance, if the interviewer wrote that a participant walked for more than twelve hours each day. After determining whether the access was correct or not, the interviewer could suppress the soft check.

The Health and Care Research Ethics Committee for Wales provided ethical permission for the 2020 telephone survey (REC reference number: 17/WA/0371).

For the 2020 telephone survey, factors such as the presence or absence of a long-term health condition and mental health/wellbeing may have influenced willingness to participate. Those who perceive themselves as having better physical and psychological health may have been more likely to opt-in. The size of such an effect cannot be measured from the data collected. There may also be a degree of self-selection bias relating to other topics included in the survey, such as smoking, drinking and general health, and possibly compounding the bias due to mode effects.

With the different modes of collection, attempts were made to maintain the broad scope of the survey. However, the requirement for a shorter questionnaire meant that the questions were less detailed in some topic areas than in previous years.

Analysis of data on these topics was made up of three chapters. The first chapter consists of Ischaemic heart disease (or coronary heart disease) and stroke, the two main components of CVD, both clinical priorities for the NHS in Scotland. Behaviours associated with CVD (smoking, poor diet, lack of physical activity, obesity, and alcohol

use) remained a strong focus of the survey. The second chapter also focuses on mental health (including food security, social capital, and loneliness) and dental health. Also, mental wellbeing, self-reported height and weight, ethnic background and religion were considered to have all been topics of interest throughout the COVID-19 pandemic.

The final chapter investigated General health on long-term conditions (including cardiovascular disease (CVD) and respiratory infections.

A Copy of letters was sent to the residents to opt into a telephone interview and questionnaire survey at various sampled addresses through an online portal, by calling the survey freephone number, or by email. The invitation was stretched out to adults aged 16 and over, and participants had to be adults in these households who were 16 years of age or older. Each participating adult received a £10 Love2Shop gift as a token of appreciation.

The questionnaire responses were instantly entered into a laptop during the interview using Computer Assisted Telephone Interviewing (CATI).

Self-reported height and weight measurements were obtained from those willing to do so toward the end of the interview.

No interviewer-administered biological measurements were collected as part of the telephone survey, in contrast to the face-to-face study (where blood pressure, waist circumference, and saliva samples are taken for a subset of the adult sample).

Participants were all individual household people from each selected household to represent a group at the same postcode and close in proximity from the secondary data on the Scottish Health Survey (SHeS) series. A household was defined as a single individual or group of individuals who occupy the space as their sole or primary residence and either share at least one meal each day or a living area.

The first adult to be interviewed in the home was the only one to answer questions about their age, gender, date of birth, and information about their employment.

Participants were questioned about their history of having diabetes, angina, heart attacks, strokes, heart murmurs, abnormal heartbeats, or “other heart issues.”

No matter if they had ever been told they had the condition by a doctor or had experienced it in the preceding 12 months, the results reported in the SHeS 2020 telephone survey report include everyone who replied positively to any of these conditions. Women between the ages of 16 and 49 who reported having diabetes, high blood pressure, or angina were questioned to determine whether a doctor diagnosed them during pregnancy to remove those cases from the statistics provided.

The study subjects who participated lived in their current address for more than <5 and 5+ years, living within a 100m radius of these monitoring sites.

Based on the SHeS 2020 telephone survey, the SHeS contained screening questions for the generalised cardiovascular disease and diabetes module. The cardiovascular disease module was based on questions about hypertension, such as “You mentioned that you have had high blood pressure. Were you told by a doctor or nurse that you had high blood pressure?”.

Additionally, air pollutant data was made available from Openair LAQM Data Download Site (DEFRA) from the Scottish air quality monitoring network.

The table 3:1, shown below is the summary of the primary data, secondary data, source and origin of the data used in this research.

Table 3:1: Summary of different data sources and origins

Study Variables	Data Origins	Data sources	Data Set	Reference database	Data extracted
Air quality	DEFRA	Scottish air quality monitoring network	Openair LAQM Data Download Site	DEFRA. Estimated Background Air Pollution Maps. 2018. Available online: https://uk-air.defra.gov.uk/data/laqm-background-home (accessed on 24 December 2021).	Estimated Background Air Pollution Maps (2018)
Noise pollution	Casella CEL-63x and 1/3 Octave Band Sound Casella dBadge2 IS Pro Personal Noise Dosimeter	Field work on Road traffic noise monitoring at (Glasgow High Street, Glasgow Townhead, East Dunbartonshire Bishopbriggs, East Dunbartonshire Kirkintilloch, and Glasgow Kerbside)	Field work data on community noise	Author source	Noise at different frequency component from road traffic and community noise
Hypertension	Information Services Division (ISD) UK Data Service SN: 8834	Disease Prevalence data at GP practices Survey (questionnaire and interview)	Data visualisation of Disease Prevalence (Disease registers and rates per 100 population Scotland, NHS Board, HSCP, Cluster an GP practice level. Scottish Health Survey, 2020: Telephone Survey	General practice - disease prevalence data visualisation. (2020). https://beta.isdscotland.org/find-publications-and-data/health-services/primary-care/general-practice-disease-prevalence-data-visualisation/ ScotCen Social Research. (2021). <i>Scottish Health Survey, 2020: Telephone Survey</i> . [data collection]. UK Data Service. SN: 8834, DOI: 10.5255/UKDA-SN-8834-1	GP practices in Scotland. NHS Scotland database (SPIRE)/ UK data service database

3.8 Exposure assessment

3.8.1 Description of the study area

The Greater Glasgow is one of the Glasgow City Regions, made up of 8 local authorities in Scotland, and forms part of North Lanarkshire, South Lanarkshire, West Dunbartonshire, East Dunbartonshire, Renfrewshire, East Renfrewshire, and Inverclyde Local Authorities in the Glasgow City Region also known as Glasgow metropolitan area. The Greater Glasgow covers a total land area of about 265 km². It shares a physical attachment with Glasgow city, the municipal in Scotland. The population of Greater Glasgow, according to the 2019 European statistics, stands at 627,479.

Greater Glasgow is prominent for its urban settlement in Scotland. Postcode District G1-G84 is part of the metropolitan area, which was created, also called the Greater Glasgow Settlement Area. The postcode was grouped into various areas per number of addresses, with each postcode containing at least 500 residents.

It is considered that Greater Glasgow's traffic-geographical position is perfect. The city's location along the country's traffic corridor connects the Glasgow metropolitan area. The city of Glasgow's Road network comprises state roads of the I and II category and municipal roads. There are city arterial highways, city roads, and collection roads on the road network.

Cities are necessary for this study, and those are recommended for long and medium-distance city journeys. The link connects roads to highways and residential areas to the rest of the city entrance and other amenities, serving most of the city's local traffic and introducing intercity lanes.

Both motorised and non-motorised traffic uses Glasgow's city roadways. Scotland has had a 135% increase in the number of licenced motor vehicles from 1.3 million in 1975 to

over 3 million in 2021. Out of all the local authorities in Scotland, Glasgow has the most traffic.

Twenty-seven percent of Glaswegians walk or cycle to work, thirty percent take public transport (bus, train or subway), and forty-one percent drive or ride their cars.

The percentage of persons who bike to work is quite low (1.6% - Census, 2011).

Pedestrian trips into the city centre increased by 19% [2% annually] between 2009 and 2018, but they dropped sharply during the pandemic and have not fully recovered since.

In contrast, bike trips into and out of the city centre have increased by 165% between 2009 and 2021 [an average increase of 14% annually] (Cordon Count Survey, 2021).

There is a rise in freight traffic and public passenger transportation in addition to the daily increase in passenger automobiles.

The traffic regime in Glasgow's area is not stringent, and most roads are two-way. Direct intersections are controlled by light signals or horizontal signalisation on the city traffic network.

Passengers are transported for a variety of reasons. However, during the busiest hours of the day, the purposes of movement connected to going to work and school account for about 95% of total activity.

As the traffic volume increased, so did the amount of traffic noise. The amount of traffic noise emitted on Glasgow's territory is determined by the traffic load (number of vehicles per hour), traffic flow structures (passenger, freight, buses, etc.), vehicle speeds, traffic flow management (braking, acceleration), street characteristics (road surface layer, ascent, curvature), vehicle techniques (engine insulation, tyres, exhaust systems), driving style, and engine load.

In Greater Glasgow, noise measurements were taken at five locations believed to be the busiest in the city.

3.8.2 The specific location in Greater Glasgow

This study was conducted at roadside locations in residential areas of Greater Glasgow. Five study areas (Glasgow High Street, Glasgow Townhead, East Dunbartonshire Bishopbriggs, East Dunbartonshire Kirkintilloch, and Glasgow kerbside) were used for data collection (Figure 3:1). Located in the largest urban area in the central belt of Scotland, they are characterised by heavy traffic on major roads with urban residential settings. These sites were used because they have significant traffic flows with traffic noise and of where current monitoring is ongoing, which aids in the easy transportation of equipment, monitoring campaigns and other field study materials.

Monitoring locations used for noise measurement included five major urban traffic road junctions close to around 500 residential areas. These locations were selected using feedback from the air quality monitoring data and major-traffic road sites (with perceived high-traffic noise and air pollution data) based on urban background criteria (DEFRA, 2018). To locate monitoring locations for air pollutants as efficiently as possible, noise sampling sites were chosen using a location-allocation model. The study incorporated land use, road networks, population density, and regulatory air-quality monitoring. The study focused on the directions of traffic flow at the monitoring sites. These places below are their locations and environments are shown in Figure 3:1 and Figure 3:2.

EDK— Four-way intersection of the street leading to four ways round about:
Townhead and Industrial Street,

GT— Four-way intersection of the street: St. Mungo Avenue, Kennedy Street, North Hanover Street, and Cowcaddens Road

GK— Four-way intersection of the street: Hope Street, Argyle Street, and Oswald Street

EDB— Four-way intersection of the street: Kenmure avenue, Bishopbriggs Cross, Kirkintilloch Road, and A803.

GHS— Four-way intersection of the street: Duke Street, George Street, castle street, and A8.

In addition to high road traffic, these locations contain residential buildings with high housing density, business facilities, scientific and educational institutions, health, and other public institutions, such as the administrative buildings of the local authority.

The prevalence of hypertension among different categories of private households in Scotland was investigated. In different localities, the exposure related to population density and nearest neighbours were considered. Based on their similar locations at postcodes, these places were extrapolated from the Scottish Air Quality website, considering major-traffic road sites with heavy traffic noise and certain levels of NO₂, PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} pollutants ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$).

Figure 3:1 : Directions of traffic flow at the monitoring locations

(Figure 3:1) depicts five approaches to crossroads, each with arrows and numbers indicating possible traffic flow routes through the crossing.

Figure 3:2 : Map of study area. The maps were created using the QGIS 3.24.3-Tisler software (Open Source Geospatial Foundation Project, Chicago, USA).

Figure 3:3 : Position of sound meter and air monitor at monitoring sites.

3.8.3 Method and classification of the count at a specific location

The amount of traffic noise emitted depends on factors such as traffic load. As a result, in addition to the criteria indicated in (Table 3:3), when estimating noise levels in metropolitan areas, one of the most important aspects of road traffic is the load on the

road or traffic flow. The number of cars passing through the intersection's centre in a unit of time is the most straightforward way to define traffic flow.

Traffic counting can determine this attribute of road traffic. Traffic counting is critical when planning traffic in cities and designing spatial and urban plans. Data on the intensity and structure of traffic flows can be gathered by traffic counting, which can be done manually or automatically. Furthermore, traffic counts are necessary for determining the future size of roadways and crossings.

Remote traffic counting was done at places for this study. Vehicle frequency was measured under the required flows, i.e., traffic direction for each intersection (1,2,3,4). Counting traffic on the roads was automatic, meaning the number of cars passing through a specific road segment in a certain time frame was estimated using the previous year's Annual Average Daily Flow (AADF) method. The direction of movement and the type of vehicle used automatic basic counting patterns to record the counting when the cars passed. Automatic counts were compared with the manual count for accuracy in traffic flow counts. This study considered the estimation using the previous year's Annual Average Daily Flow (AADF) method in the five specific study locations. An AADF is the daily average number of vehicles passing a site on the road network over a year. During peak hours, traffic counts are taken at specified points along the roads. During the working hours of the day, the peak hour has the highest traffic volume. The peak hour in Scotland accounts for 6 – 7 % of total daily traffic and occurs in the morning and afternoon between (9 am – 2 pm) traffic load during peak hours. Furthermore, annual daily traffic flow data was collected on traffic flow from the department of transportation in the five locations (DfT, 2020) on the automatic counts and compared with the manual count for accuracy in traffic flow counts. This study considered the estimation using the previous year's Annual Average Daily Flow (AADF) method. Therefore, it was appropriate to use the secondary data (DfT, 2020).

The data consist of specific study locations. An AADF is the daily average number of vehicles passing a site on the road network over a year.

The table 3:2 below consist of specific geographical location of where daily traffic flow counting was carried out and estimation methods used.

Table 3:2: Model and classification of the count at a specific location

Latitude	Longitude	Link length/km	Link_Length miles	Count_point_id	Estimation_method_detailed
55.865488	-4.2355045	0.3	0.19	20817	Estimated using the previous year's AADF on this link (Major Roads)
55.856522	-4.2589577	0.2	0.12	40925	Estimated using the previous year's AADF on this link (Major Roads)
55.867183	-4.2362412	0.6	0.37	20916	Estimated using the previous year's AADF on this link (Major Roads)
55.870681	-4.2690032	0.3	0.19	1033	Estimated using the previous year's AADF on this link (Major Roads)
55.862368	-4.1586162	2.8	1.74	80278	Estimated using the previous year's AADF on this link (Major Roads)

Motorways and A-class roads are examples of major roadways. The study considers the Road Traffic Act 1930 on the UK's classification of a motor vehicle. The following are the vehicle categories used in this study:

Two-wheeled motor vehicles, M—passenger-carrying vehicles, abbr. PCVs (Car and taxi vehicles), N—goods-carrying vehicles (lorries and vans)—trailers and semitrailers, Light-goods vehicles (lgvs), Buses and coaches, and all heavy goods vehicles (all hgvs). Because the noise emission of different vehicle categories varies substantially, these categories are studied. On the other hand, the two-wheeled type of vehicle is included in our research since it impacts overall traffic noise. The interaction of the wheels with the road surface and the airflow demonstrates this influence. Data was taken on the annual daily road traffic flow of Car and taxi vehicles, Two-wheeled motor vehicles, Light-goods vehicles (lgvs), Buses and coaches, and all heavy goods vehicles (all hgvs) at each of the sites (Glasgow High Street, Glasgow Townhead, East Dunbartonshire

Bishopbriggs, East Dunbartonshire Kirkintilloch, and Glasgow kerbside) during the monitoring period from the department of transportation (road traffic statistics) on road traffic flow (DfT, 2019). The total traffic flow rate was the annual daily traffic flow of Car and taxi vehicles, Two-wheeled motor vehicles, and Light-goods vehicles (lgvs) in this study.

Table 3:3: Vehicle classifications counted in the investigated areas

traffic sites	pedal_cycles	two_wheeler	cars_and_taxi	buses_and_trucks	lgvs	hgvs_2_rigid	hgvs_3_rigid	hgvs_4_or_more	hgvs_3_or_4	hgvs_5_artic	hgvs_6_artic	all_hgvs	all_motor_vehicles
EDB	272	41	9829	374	1703	263	20	8	3	11	6	311	12259
GK	442	89	11377	74	1318	122	49	21	5	6	8	212	13069
GHS	24	18	5576	153	722	68	7	10	7	8	3	103	6571
GT	97	67	12902	194	2387	143	34	21	7	10	38	252	15801
EDK	61	20	5004	140	1028	128	32	8	4	10	3	186	6378

Table 3:4: Characteristics of analysed roads

	EDB	GT	GK	EDK	GHS
Geographical characteristics	The terrain of Approach 1 is flat, while approaches 2, 3, and 4 are falling or rising depending on the direction of movement	The terrain of approaches 1 and 3 is flat, while approaches 2 and 4 are falling or rising, depending on the direction of movement.	The terrain on approaches 1, 4, 2 is flat, while approaching 3 is under a slope, i.e., an ascent depending on the movement's direction.	The terrain of approaches 1 and 3 is flat, while approaches 2 and 4 are falling or rising, depending on the direction of movement.	The terrain on approaches 1, 4, 2 is flat, while approaching 3 is under a slope, i.e., an ascent depending on the movement's direction.
Characteristics of the space/ objects in the analysed area	Residential buildings, catering facilities, business facilities, public buildings, etc	Residential buildings, catering facilities, business facilities, educational institutions, etc.	Residential buildings, catering facilities, business facilities, educational institutions, etc.	Residential buildings, catering facilities, business facilities, etc	Residential buildings, catering facilities, business facilities, educational institutions, etc.
Characteristics of the road	Two-way traffic takes place on the approaches to all traffic routes. Approaches 1, 2, and 4 have three lanes, while approach 3 has two lanes per road. The main surface of the road is asphalt. Vertical traffic lights regulate traffic at the intersection.	Two-way traffic takes place on the approaches to all roads. The number of lanes is four for directions 1, 2, and 4, while direction 3 has three lanes. The main surface of the road is asphalt. Vertical traffic lights regulate traffic at the intersection.	Two-way traffic takes place on the approaches to all roads. The number of lanes is four for directions 1, 2, and 4, while direction 3 has three lanes. The main surface of the road is asphalt. Vertical traffic lights regulate traffic at the intersection.	Two-way traffic takes place on the approaches to all roads. The number of lanes is four for roads 1 and 2, while directions 3 and 4 have three lanes. The main surface of the road is asphalt. Vertical traffic lights regulate traffic at the intersection.	Two-way traffic takes place on the approaches to all traffic routes. Approaches 1, 2, and 4 have three lanes, while approach 3 has two lanes per road. The main surface of the road is asphalt. Vertical traffic lights regulate traffic at the intersection

The study population was drawn from all private households for each monitoring site along the major roads from August 2020 to September 2020.

The group included 15 households each from five locations (Glasgow High Street, Glasgow Townhead, East Dunbartonshire Bishopbriggs, East Dunbartonshire Kirkintilloch and Glasgow kerbside).

The sample of individuals included in the measurement were enough household persons that were randomly selected from each end of the homogenous exposure group (HEG). These involved dividing the population into familiar groups and then taking a simple random sample in each joint group (Kombo, 2006).

Therefore, the study power was related to several factors. Population size surveyed and exposed individuals who are at high risk are some of the factors considered for the outcome during road traffic noise and air pollutant study. This connotes that noise and air pollution from the working environment was related to high-risk factors that affected many individuals, thus environmental epidemiology. The higher the expected relative risk (RR), the smaller the population that needs to be surveyed. Conversely, the larger the population studied, the smaller the RR that can be detected.

3.9 Data collection techniques

The study used quantitative and qualitative data through methods like questionnaires and interviews, making this study analytical cross-sectional-method research.

Qualitative analysis was done using case studies on the prevalence of hypertension in Scotland. The study used existing scientific data such as an interview database on cases of hypertension from the Scottish Health Survey series commissioned by the Scottish Government Health Directorates in the urban areas of the UK.

Tools and techniques were combined in terms of mechanical, formality and informality attributes with written and unwritten questions of a telephone survey to offer the opportunity to probe further and obtain valuable information from respondents' knowledge of hypertension.

The first phase of this study underwent a noise survey to assess community households' environmental emissions and road traffic exposure (noise levels at different frequencies).

For the parallel continuous measurements in all five-monitoring locations (Figure 3.1), the Casella CEL-633C1 & 1/3 Octave Band Sound Level Meter and Casella dBadge2 IS Pro Personal Noise Dosimeter was used to determine the level of acoustic pressure depending on the different frequency ranges.

The concentrations of chemical pollutants were continuously monitored using air quality network data. Air pollution was sampled from the air quality network database, and the PM₁₀, NO₂ and PM_{2.5} levels was recorded in hourly averages. Five locations were chosen to site the instruments; the location was in the centre of Glasgow, characterised by heavy traffic on major roads. During the field monitoring, the Casella CEL-63x & 1/3 Octave Band Sound Level Meter was sited at 1.2–1.5 m on a tripod, at 1m from the road edge adjacent to the air quality monitoring equipment. It was often at least 10m from the centre line of the nearest lane of traffic in Glasgow (depending on the road type), at least 1m away from buildings to avoid noise reflection for each site location, and a consistent but safe distance from the road, kept within sight and supervised by researcher 100% of measurement time, both for equipment security and to reduce any issues should public or workers require access to the location.

Hence, the measurements were conducted in the same place where air quality monitoring equipment was sited. The CEL-63x is a precision measuring instrument, but the device was calibrated before each measurement run and again after each measurement run to ensure its measurements were accurate. When the CEL-63x

instrument detects a consistent 1 kHz calibration tone, it automatically picks the calibration screen. Only the Stop mode (when the instrument displays red screen bars) allows calibration mode to be used. Since the sound meter may have been subjected to vibration, shock and excessive cold on the way to the measurement site, the accuracy of the equipment may have been impaired. For this reason, it was necessary to calibrate the equipment on site to check that everything was operating well. The calibrator was attached to the meter's microphone, and the reading was compared with the calibrator's value. When required, the gain of the meter is adjusted to bring it into calibration.

The community noise exposure level was measured for 3 to 6 days during the daytime in the morning, afternoon, and night as Lden and Lnight, respectively. The road traffic noise was measured at the height of 1.2–1.5 m on a tripod, at 1m away from the road edge adjacent to the air quality monitoring equipment.

The environmental conditions involved dry road surfaces, no rain, a humidity of 5 % to 90 % RH non-condensing, a temperature of 10 °C to +50 °C (Class 1), 0 °C to +40 °C (Class 2), pressure of 65 kPa to 108 kPa and a wind speed below five m/s.

The measurement times were taken at a minimum of 1 h to 4 h in length most often at the end of a daily measurement. The community noise measurement and air quality monitoring start during the daytime between (09:00–17:00).

Sampling location was selected using a location-allocation model that included land use, road networks, population density and air quality monitoring station.

Continuous measurement was used, and every exposure interval was continuously measured using Casella CEL-633C1 & 1/3 Octave Band Sound Level Meter. It was impossible to measure the noise level of all households due to several families and COVID 19 pandemic restrictions. It was appropriate to select two or more homes to represent a group (Theyry et al., 1994). Therefore, there is a need for homogenous

exposure groups (HEG). All the households at each of the five monitoring sites with similar postcodes and locations were grouped (HEG). The investigator in each monitoring site undertook repeated measurements but represented a different homogenous exposure household group at a time.

Sound level measurement: To assess the degree of noise exposure, measures were taken at places usually occupied by the household persons in the areas identified to cause noise pollution. This was made possible after surveying to designate the areas with hazardous noise. A dBadge2 IS Pro Personal Noise Dosimeter was used. Noise levels were measured at the position of the household's collar of the dress while they kept their normal posture. Again, to ensure that noises from the road traffic were accurately measured, the microphone of the sound level meter was Omnidirectional. Different types of road traffic along the various households were studied in each community. The road traffic types are widely used and are known to cause noise pollution. For each of the selected families in the study, three measurements were taken for 5 minutes to make the accuracy margin wide. This has proved sufficient with approximately 0.2dB accuracy (Bruel, 1986).

The unit employed for expressing the values in the decibel was (dBA) set at the A-weighting network. Again, the meter was placed at the slow "response throughout the measurements due to the steady and intermittent noise (Bruel, 1986). Since the primary purpose of the measures was to assess the hazards to the hypertension of the persons of the household who stay in a community, measurements covered all homes in the same postcode around the neighbourhood. The spectral characteristics of the noise measured in the community could not be analysed because an instrument for that purpose could not be secured.

Therefore, the Casella dBadge2 IS Pro Personal Noise Dosimeter with a measurement range of 30–130 decibels (dB) were set up on the collar of the investigator who moved

to and from to represent a homogenous exposure household group on the household size along the roadside. The measurement took 1 hour of time-weighted-average (TWA) continuous equivalent sound levels (L_{eq}) for the entire frequency spectrum and specific components at 31.5, 63, 125, 250, 500, 1000, 2000, 4000 and 8000 Hz. The measurement was conducted for 3 to 6 days that included 15 homogenous exposure household group each from five monitoring locations.

The community noise measurement processes and the setup of noise monitoring at various sites followed the UK Calculation of Road Traffic Noise (CRTN) method and CNOSSOS-EU standard method of exposure noise mapping for major roads considering agglomeration to check environmental noise standards (Kephalopoulos et al., 2012 and Kephalopoulos et al., 2014). The study defines community noise calculations in the range of 16Hz to 16 kHz, and frequency band results were provided at the corresponding frequency interval.

An analysis was performed in octave bands for road traffic [8]. For road traffic noise, based on these octave band results, the A-weighted long-term average sound pressure level for the day, evening, and night period, as defined in Annex I and referred to in Art. 5 of Directive 2002/49/EC, is computed by summation over all frequencies:

$$L_{Aeq, T} = 10 \times \lg \sum_{(i=1)} 10^{((L_{eq, T, i} \pm A_i)/10)}$$

where A_i denotes the A-weighting correction according to IEC 61672-1

i = frequency band index and

T is the period corresponding to daytime, evening or night.

The CEL-63x instruments calculated the community noise parameters according to the most widely adopted time intervals and penalties. During daily measurement, corrections were required due to intervals at different times in the morning, afternoon and evening. The period was recorded at a helpful time interval of one hour, and the

‘Synchronise Time’ option was enabled. Once the LAeq was established for each hour of the day, the appropriate penalty was added at the level. The overall measurement was calculated within a spreadsheet using various periods, during the daytime at 14 hours, evening time at 2 hours at the penalty of +5 and nighttime at 8 hours at a correction of +10 by the Directive 2002/49/CE and UK Calculation of Road Traffic Noise (CRTN) method and CNOSSOS-EU standard method. The community noise level was calculated using the noise meter app.

$$L_{den} = 10 \log[(d \times 10^{L_d/10}) + (e \times 10^{(L_e + P_e)/10}) + (n \times 10^{(L_n + P_n)/10})]$$

d = number of daytime hours

L_d = LAeq measurement of daytime hours (dB)

e = number of evening hours

L_e = LAeq measurement of evening hours (dB)

P_e = penalty during evening hours (dB)

n = number of nighttime hours

L_n = LAeq measurement of night-time hours (dB)

P_n = penalty during night-time hours (dB)

Using the following equation, the 1-h TWA Leq was applied to calculate the Leq,24h.

Leq,24h

$$= 10 \times 10 \log \{ [(L \text{ measured during the morning rush hour} \times 2) + (L \text{ measured during the afternoon rush hour} \times 2) + (L \text{ measured in the daytime} \times 9) + (L \text{ measured in the evening} \times 3) + (L \text{ measured at night} \times 8)] \div 24$$

After the actual road traffic noise measurement was assessed, the annual average exposures to road traffic noise (L_{day}(day time), L_{eve}(evening time) and L_{night}(night time)) for five locations (latitude x, longitude y) centroids in Greater Glasgow were modelled using QGIS software and openNoise plugins.

3.10 Noise Level Monitoring

3.10.1 Design of measurement

The CEL-63x instrument is an octave or 1/3 octave band analyser with a single measurement range of 0–140 decibels (dB). It was set up to measure one-hour time-weighted-average (TWA) continuous equivalent sound levels (Leq) with centre frequencies from 12.5 Hz to 16 kHz.

During the experimental tests at the five locations, the meteorological conditions, including temperature, humidity, and wind speed, were monitored.

Information on traffic flow rates, road width in front of each site, speed limits and meteorological factors were also collected from the noise Scotland website and air quality network, specifically in Glasgow.

The study design on noise survey referenced the CNOSSOS-EU method, which is valid for determining noise in the frequency range from 125 Hz to 4 kHz for road traffic noise. Calculations were performed in octave bands for road traffic (Kephalopoulos, 2014).

3.10.2 Sound meter and Personal dosimeter

The most convenient instrumentation for sound measurement was the Casella CEL-63x & 1/3 Octave Band Sound Level Meter, which digital signal processing technology provides a full range of functions, including integrating and real-time octave and 1/3-octave band analysis.

Conform to international standards for acoustic measurement. The measurements are saved automatically in high-capacity internal Flash memory. You can transfer the measurement results to a PC where you can manage the results and create reports by

using the Casella insight data management software. The instrument is small, and a wrist strap was attached to a stand near the bottom of the device.

3.10.3 Sound Meter Characteristics

The CEL-63x instrument is designed to allow easy operation. The Sound pressure level (SPL), Integrating and Octave band noise

IEC 61672-1:2013 (Electro-Acoustics – Sound Level Meters) Group ‘X’ instruments.

Performance of Class 1 or 2 as relevant to the instrument model.

IEC 60651: 1979, IEC 60804: 2000, ANSI S1.4 1983, ANSI S1.43-1997(R2007)

1/1 Octave and 1/3 Octave Filters comply with EN61260: 1996, Class 0 and ANSI S1.11 1986, Order-3 Type 0C.

The experimental equipment setup components are represented schematically as follows:

Figure 3:4: Sound Meter instrument

1 Windshield (to cover the removable microphone)

2 Pre-amplifier (removable – pull the knurled body of the pre-amplifier connector away from the instrument body)

3. ON/OFF key

4. Soft keys

5. Navigation keys

6. Run/Stop key

3.10.4 Personal Dosimeter

The Casella dBadge2 IS Pro Personal Noise Dosimeter is an inexpensive, easy-to-use device worn by the subject. It is dispensable in instances where the households' activities, including when work is done in a confined space and highly mobile. Still, a sound meter was used if the exposure characteristics were unpredictable. The Casella dBadge2 IS Pro Personal Noise Dosimeter is an easy-to-use device that estimates the octave band's noise level and alerts the user to the risk of overexposure. The dBadge2 conforms to EMC emissions and immunity requirements as IEC610004-2/6-1, 61000-4-6/6-2, 61000-4-3/CISPR 61000-6-3.

The dBadge2 was tested with a pink noise acoustic source of 85dB and complied with the immunity requirements of clause 15 (IEC 61252). No additional devices are connected during everyday use. This device conforms to the technical characteristics specified in standard IEC 61260:2014 Electro acoustics, Octave-Band and Fractional-Octave-Band Filters; Class 2

ANSI/ASA S1.11-2014 Octave-Band and Fractional-Octave-Band Analog and Digital Filters; Class 2 for dosimeters and sound exposure meters.

The experimental equipment setup components are indicated schematically as follows:

Figure 3:5: Personal Noise dose meter instrument

Sound levels produced from the road traffic at various communities were measured. It consists of a microphone that detects minor air pressure variations associated with sound and changes them into electrical signals. The electronic circuitry of the instrument processes these signals. The readout displays the sound levels in decibels, and the device picks up sound levels in a particular location at one instance. A-Weighting was used for measurements since it simulates the human ear and measures sound levels from musical materials.

3.11 Environmental Noise Data Collection and Modelling Approaches

3.11.1 Simulation of road traffic noise pollution

QGIS 3.10.2 simulated road traffic noise pollution in the Greater Glasgow territory. This software is a cross-platform desktop geographic information system application

that facilitates viewing, editing, and analysing geographical data. It is free and open source.

The importing of the shapefile map of Scotland into a suitable coordinate system is the first step in simulating road traffic noise pollution. EPSG:27700-OSGB36/ British National Grid– Projected is the coordinate reference system in this situation.

Building two essential layers (Pavlović et al., 2021) to represent the ambient noise caused by vehicle activity in Greater Glasgow is the second step: Buildings and Roads. The initial layer defines the polygonal buildings and the design of structures using the existing blueprints.

Buildings were labelled with different colours based on the amount of noise they were exposed to. The maximum noise level of residential facilities located at the intersection was recorded. The noise level from road was assigned to building (Figure 4:5).

According to the UK's regulatory standards, noise on the facade of evaluated facilities should not exceed 65 dB(A).

The initial layer defined the polygonal buildings that were produced. Making receiver points is the initial stage in noise modelling, and the software automatically selects these points for you. Receiver points can be generated for each façade or central receiver location along the facade. The façade is a polygonal layer that represents buildings. Receiver points were found on half of each building's junctions that was examined.

The noise level at reception sites caused by road sources must then be determined (a line layer). The sound pressure level for each road is determined using the previously provided data (noise level, traffic load, road slope, type of terrain, etc.). The outcomes are stored in the property.

This layer indicates the source of traffic noise emission, and the road layer's type is a line type. The attribute table defined the traffic load for each direction when defining the second layer.

The structures were drawn using a shapefile map of Greater Glasgow already entered. The building's purpose was not considered during the design. The second stratum was identified as the roads. This layer indicates the source of traffic noise emission, and the road layer's type is a line type. The noise level at reception sites caused by road sources (a line layer) was determined.

QGIS offers many plugins. One is *opeNoise*, which allows users to compute the noise level produced by a point source or a road source at fixed receiver spots and structures. Another processing tool will enable you to interpolate the air quality index in a location by point source or road source at improved interpolation density Weight (IDW) to form raster layers and structures central to receiver spots.

Making receiver points is the initial stage in noise modelling, and the software automatically selects these points for you. Receiver points can be generated for each façade or central receiver location along the facade. The façade is a polygonal layer representing buildings, and receiver points were found on half of each building's show at the examined junctions in this scenario.

The noise level at reception sites caused by road sources must then be determined (a line layer). The sound pressure level for each road is determined using the previously provided data (noise level, traffic load, road slope, type of terrain, etc.). The results are recorded in the receiver point layer's attribute table and expressed in decibels (dB) (A). The value -99 is assigned if the level is not calculated or is less than zero (QGIS., 2021). The noise levels for each receiver point to the matching building are determined in the final stage. The maximum value among all the receiver points for that building is the value assigned to it.

Simulations were run for various periods, more specifically for data collected during the daytime at 14 h, evening time at 2 h at the penalty of +5, and night-time at 8 h at the

detriment of +10 by Directive 2002/49/CE and UK Calculation of Road Traffic Noise (CRTN) method and CNOSSOS-EU standard method. The plugin automatically calculates the value of Lden when data referred to the three reference periods are set (Daytime, Evening time, and Night-time).

The research ray is the maximum distance of influence of the source to the receiver in meters—receivers' points beyond the research ray return a -99 value. A smaller research ray reduces the calculation time with consequent loss of precision in sound-level estimates. The research ray was set to 1000 m. Therefore, the relative humidity to 70 and the air temperature to 20 degrees Celsius by the ISO 9613-1.

The following additions were made; data on the annual daily road traffic flow of Car and taxi vehicles, Two-wheeled motor vehicles, Light-goods vehicles (lgvs), Buses and coaches, and all heavy goods vehicles (all hgvs) at each of the sites during the monitoring period from the department of transportation (road traffic statistics) (DfT, 2019).

Secondary data on annual daily road traffic flow of Car and taxi vehicles, Two-wheeled motor vehicles, Light-goods vehicles (lgvs), Buses and coaches and all heavy goods vehicles (all hgvs) at each of the sites (Figure 3:1) during the monitoring period was taken from the department of transportation (road traffic statistics) on road traffic flow. The total traffic flow rate was the annual daily traffic flow of Car and taxi vehicles, Two-wheeled motor vehicles, and Light-goods vehicles (lgvs) in this study. The air pollution data was collected from the Scottish air quality only limited to urban city areas.

3.12 Air pollution Data Collection and Modelling Approaches

Air quality data on pollution was obtained from the Scottish air quality network (2020) from a harmonised European Land Use Regression (LUR) model at 100x100m. Daily average concentrations of NO₂, PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} were accessed in five different urban locations in Scotland. Estimated Background Air Pollution Maps (2018) was downloaded from (DEFRA, 2020). Total annual mean concentrations based on 1 km x

1 km grid squares are provided (DEFRA, 2020). This data from DEFRA consists of several coordinates in all regions of Scotland.

This study used the annual daily average air concentration (NO₂, PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}) from November 23, 2020, to November 24, 2021, for this modelling. Data were obtained from the Openair LAQM Data Download Site (DEFRA, 2020). Air quality is monitored under the operating principles of automatic analysers using tapered element oscillating microbalance (TEOM) equipment (Gray et al., 2017). The monitoring was completed using automatic analysers reference techniques of measurement, except for the automatic PM₁₀/PM_{2.5} analysers, which are those that are outlined in the EU Directives. The standard procedure for measuring NO₂, PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} levels was completed using chemiluminescence, flow dynamic measurement system (FDMS), beta attenuation monitor (BAM), and gravimetric sampler respectively (Gray et al., 2017).

3.12.1 Modelling of Road Traffic Air Quality

In a text editor, open the openaq.csv file and inspect it. Data from one monitoring station is contained in each row of data. The station coordinates are in the latitude and longitude columns, while the value column includes the average daily PM_{2.5}, P.M 10 and NO₂ concentration. Files were downloaded in excel and edited and saved in CSV format when necessary for editing.

Delimited Text files, such as this, come into tabular data in text files and can be imported into QGIS via Data Source Manager. Open the Data Source Manager by clicking the button.

Open the openaq.csv file by navigating to it. Select Point coordinates because we want to import this file as points. Choose the X Field for longitude and the Y Field for latitude. In Geometry CRS, select EPSG 4326 - WGS 84. Select Add from the drop-down menu.

The tabular data has now been loaded as a spatial data layer in the QGIS canvas. Click on any of the points using the Identify button. The attribute data associated with each issue will be visible now.

Since the same location from the simulation of road traffic noise was used, the OpenStreetMap (OSM) and shapefile will clearly show the point and location. However, the noise level was represented by points, so it will be appropriate to have air quality as a raster layer. Inverse density weight (IDW) was applied to air pollutants to build spatial weight matrices for spatial autocorrelation studies.

A geoprocessing tool called IDW is used to interpolate the air quality. Under the IDW, interpolation requires the vector layer consisting of the PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀ and NO₂ concentration in form points.

Firstly, the interpolation attribute is selected and the actual pollutant data of NO₂, PM₁₀, and PM_{2.5} was inserted at the original coordinate of X and Y (Latitude and Longitude). The interpolation was run, and the raster layer produced by the interpolation was edited. The editing was made by opening the Layer Styling Panel by clicking it. Select and change the single band grey to single band pseudocolour renderer from the drop-down menu. Select Cumulative count cut from the Min / Max Value Settings section. Choose a spectral colour ramp. The spectral colour was inverted to match the pollutant and renamed the contaminant level according to the national air quality index to interpret the air pollutant. After applying the style, the air quality index in legend form, among other layers could be seen. The air quality index was layered according to the Committee on the Medical Effects of Air Pollutants (COMEAP, 2011).

This work used the hourly mean concentration for each air pollutant including nitrogen dioxide. The latest 24-h running mean for the current day is based on the daily mean concentration for secondary data for PM_{2.5} particles. The present day's 24-h running mean is calculated using the daily mean concentration for secondary data for PM₁₀

particles. This study used the annual daily average air concentration (NO₂, PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}) from 23 November 2020 to 24 November 2021 for this modelling.

3.13 Modelling Approaches for Prevalence of Hypertension using Secondary data

This study phase targeted the prevalence of hypertension cases among community households from the Scottish Health Survey data (UK data service) commissioned by the Scottish Government Health Directorates.

To avoid bias (misclassification) and promote using quality assurance data, Patients with hypertension who were on treatment may have low SBP and DBP, so this method was inappropriate for identifying hypertensive cases. The best approach was to complement the blood pressure measurement with a questionnaire data (the questionnaire) asking if the participant has ever been diagnosed with hypertension and taking an antihypertensive drug. Various cases were defined as participants with a medical history of hypertension.

Secondly, those having a previous history of taking an antihypertensive drug were classified as having hypertension (Unger et al., 2020).

Secondary data gathered from the SHeS interview were used. The SHeS interview was specifically carried out for participants aged 16 years and above in their private households. According to the survey, most participants were not older because the scope did not look out for participants in institutions or workplaces, making the participant, not in the more senior class and poorer health conditions but private households in the communities.

Participants were interviewed during the same periods of road traffic noise measurements. Due to the COVID 19 pandemic, most participants were at their current locations due to the lockdown. Fortunately, this scenario aided in assessing the realities of the implications of traffic noise and air pollution emissions in the area.

The data collected from questionnaire during the survey was used to get the respondents' views on knowledge regarding hypertension. The study used data on additional risk factors for hypertension. These factors included age, gender, height, weight, smoking history, diet, self-reported size and weight, physical activities, history of hypertension, medication history in the past seven days and family history of hypertension.

The subjects' lifestyle habits were defined in detail to avoid information bias. For instance, Subjects' knowledge of smoking status intake was considered if they reported: "regularly exposed to other people's tobacco smoke in any of these places based on their own home or at work or in other people's homes or cars, vans or outside of buildings (e.g., pubs, shops, hospitals) or in other public places or no, none of these". A history of hypertension was taken to know if the subject had been doctor-diagnosed with hypertension. In addition, body mass index (body weight (kg)), general health, cardiovascular disease, asthma, and diabetes was taken.

All the data were obtained anonymously, and data confidentiality was maintained throughout the research. The data on hypertension was used in these study, when A participant was considered as a case of hypertension if they answered affirmatively to questions like: "doctor diagnosed high BP, the doctor diagnosed hypertension (excluding pregnant), ever had high BP (excludes only had high BP during pregnancy), the doctor diagnosed hypertension (excluding pregnant), hypertension condition present, pregnant when told had high BP and high BP other than when pregnant?"

Database from the Scottish Health Survey series commissioned by the Scottish Government Health Directorates on general health survey was accessible to provide the prevalence of hypertension outcomes.

3.13.1 Modelling methodology for prevalence of hypertension

The prevalence of hypertension also focuses on the patient register of reported hypertension cases and the rate of hypertension. Data visualisation was enabled by opening the `openaq.csv` file with a text editor, and each row of data contains the information from a single monitoring station. The latitude and longitude columns include the hospital coordinates, while the value column has the average hypertension register cases and rate. When necessary for modification, the files were downloaded into Excel, modified by removing all disease prevalence except hypertension register and hypertension rate, and saved in the CSV format. The delimited CSV format files are text files containing tabular data and may be imported into the QGIS using the Data Source Manager. By clicking the button, one may access the Data Source Manager. The steps include the following: Navigate to the `openaq.csv` file and open it. Then, import this file as points, and choose the point coordinates—X Field for longitude and Y Field for latitude. Choose EPSG 4326—WGS 84 in the Geometry CRS. From the drop-down option, choose Add. The tabular data are input in the QGIS canvas as a spatial data layer, where clicking on any of the points reveals the attribute information related to each issue. By opening the Layer Styling Panel (left click), selecting, and changing the single band grey to single band pseudocolour renderer from the drop-down menu. Choose and add a hospital symbol from the drop-down option. To model the data into multiple shapefiles' maps, spatial analysis on joint road traffic noise and air contaminants with hypertension was undertaken. This kind of map comprises a vector layer and a raster layer with attribute information. Some attribute information is indicated in (Table 3:5). The geospatial analysis in geometric locations includes information on noise, air contaminants, residential structures, and roads. The report comprises data on individual characteristics (i.e., demographics, medical history, and lifestyle) and registered hypertension cases for each monitoring site.

Table 3:5: Parameters for creating a 3D scatterplot for the vector layers

Label	Name	Type	Description
Input layer	INPUT	[vector: any]	Input vector layer
X attribute (air pollution)	XFIELD	[table field: NO ₂ , PM ₁₀ , PM _{2.5}]	Field to use for the x-axis: [NO ₂ , PM ₁₀ , PM _{2.5}]
Y attribute (noise frequency)	YFIELD	[table field: LOW, MID, HIGH]	Field to use for the y-axis: [LOW, MID, HIGH]
Z attribute (hypertension rate)	ZFIELD	[table field: Hypertension rate]	Field to use for the z-axis: [Hypertension rate]
Histogram	OUTPUT	[html] Default: [Save to temporary file]	Specify the HTML file for the plot. Choose one of the options. Save to File
Histogram	OUTPUT	[html]	HTML file with the plot. Available in the Processing ► Result Viewer.

The python plugin called Plotly in the QGIS enables the development of 3D clustering charts (multivariate scatterplots) with the help of the Plotly library and the Python API. The plots are completely interactive (Sievert et al., 2020). The algorithm used to create the clusters can be seen as being graphically correlated with the features and identified. However, there are spatial outliers and regional multivariate clusters (Oxoli et al., 2020). Therefore, a multivariate scatter matrix analysis was used to examine if one significant cluster is visible.

3.14 Canonical Correlation Methods

The relationships between the combined exposure to road noise and air pollution, hypertension registers, and hypertension rate were examined using non-linear canonical correlation (NLCC). NLCC process is used to compare different collections of categorical variables against one another.

The steps for the NLCC approach are as follows: Finding one or more non-linear canonical functions, also referred to as canonical variables, that describe the various data dimensions is the first stage in the NLCC approach (Akhvlediani et al., 2019). The highest correlation that could be determined from the sets of qualitative variables is

represented by the first canonical variable. The ideal scaling level for the qualitative variables under consideration in the analysis determines the maximum number of canonical variables. The matching eigenvalue for each canonical variable is determined. The percentage of the total variance explained by a specific canonical variable is represented by an eigenvalue, which is an index of variance in the range of 0 to 1. The fit value and the loss value are evaluated to assess how well the NLCC solution matches the qualitative data in terms of the relationship between the sets. The loss value indicates the discrepancy between the maximum fit value (the number of canonical variables) and the fit value, which represents the sum of the eigenvalues. In real life, percentages (0% to 100%) are used to express each of these values (Akhvlediani et al., 2019).

Finding the most pertinent variables regarding each canonical variable comes next after obtaining the variables. To perform this step, the NLCC approach calculates the canonical loading, also known as the structural correlation coefficient, for each research variable. A canonical loading, like principal component and factor analysis, shows the relationship between the input variable and the output canonical variable (Akhvlediani et al., 2019). Like the Pearson's correlation coefficient, this is interpreted. Any research variable with a canonical loading of 0.30 or higher is chosen as a significant variable for inferring the exposure–outcome relationship (Akhvlediani et al., 2019).

A canonical loading of less than 0.30 shows that a variable has little to no effect on the canonical variable.

The direction of the association is shown by the positive or negative sign of the canonical loading, much like in a traditional correlation study.

3.14.1 Two Sets of Categorical Variables

Set-1. Pollution: nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}), coarse particulate matter (PM₁₀), high-noise-frequency component, low-noise-frequency component, and mid-noise-frequency component.

Set-2. Hypertension: hypertension registers and hypertension rate

3.15 Analysis and presentation

The data obtained by physical instruments and the data from respondents was illustrated by percentages and proportions (for categorical data) and mean, minimum, maximum, and interquartile range (for continuous data) in tables and graphs. It involved the descriptive and inferential statistics of respondents regarding demographics and prevalence of hypertension. All statistical analysis was performed using SPSS 23.0, Jamovi and Jasp, R analysis, Python Consoles and QGIS 3.24.3-Tisler.

An analysis of spatial autocorrelation using Moran's I was used to assess whether a registered hypertension case was an isolated case or was clustered, utilising several 100 simulations together with the number of neighbours (nearest) in a contiguous polygon. Moran's I was used to analyse the spatial autocorrelation of combined noise level and air pollutants (Lden, NO₂, PM₁₀, and PM_{2.5}), using 100 simulations and a range of neighbours (nearest neighbourhoods) of 10 to 100 km and 1 km × 1 km grid squares in the QGIS.

Inverse density weighting (IDW) interpolation of NO₂, PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} were aggregated. An analysis of noise level (Lden) at road traffic and residential buildings during the daytime, night, and evening was simulated and analysed at monitoring sites.

An openoise analysis of noise level (Lden) at road traffic and residential buildings during the daytime, night, and evening was simulated and analysed at monitoring sites. To analyse the traffic noise level at different frequency component ranges and measured periods at five monitoring, the spatial 'ggplot' simulation at coordinates of three variables was done using a ternary plot.

A multivariate scatterplot relationship analysis was used to assess the mutual association between noise level, air concentration, hypertension rate, and registered cases.

A 3D scatterplot relationship analysis was used to assess the mutual association between noise levels at different frequency components, air concentration, and hypertension rate.

The distance correlation of vectors with values of the joint noise level at different frequency components and air concentration and hypertension rate were analysed using a proximity matrix (measure).

Using the multiple logistic regression, we examined the relationships between combined exposure to road noise at different components of frequencies, air pollution, and hypertension rate were examined.

The relationships between combined exposure to road noise at different components of frequencies, air pollution, and hypertension registered cases were examined using a multiple logistic regression.

We examined the relationships between combined exposure to road noise, air pollution, and joint hypertension register and hypertension rate using canonical correlation.

To analyse the traffic noise level at different frequency ranges, the temporal and frequency-component variations, the Shapiro test, Friedman's test (nonparametric and parametric measurement) one-way repeated measure analysis of variance test were applied to assess significant differences in the noise levels between different measured periods (i.e., daytime, evening and nighttime) and other frequency components (i.e., low, mid, high) for nonnormally and normally distributed variables, respectively. Since Friedman's test was statistically significant, Conover's post hoc test was applied.

Subjects were categorised into age, length of noise exposure, and noise exposure level groups. Between groups (age, exposure time, levels of noise comparison for numerical values) were done by the chi-square test. A similar analysis was done separately to determine whether the variable (age, exposure time, and noise levels) significantly influenced hypertension among household persons.

If a high frequency (2kHz) is found among the exposed group, an association between the disease and the noise exposure was inferred (Lilienfield et al. 1984).

A multivariate analysis was also performed to determine the simultaneous effect on developing HBP of age, gender, and exposure time. This was done with logistic regression analysis to determine the odds of developing or not developing HBP. Odds ratios and 95% confidence intervals with p-values were determined.

A multivariate analysis of factors influencing hypertension among the respondents was done. These were done with a multinomial logistic regression to assess the factors influencing the exposure period of noise, the noise level at different frequency components and years of air pollution exposure to hypertension.

To evaluate the associations of noise and air pollution with hypertension, road traffic noise and concentration of NO₂, PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} from the air quality network with the prevalence of hypertension will be estimated using binary logistic regression. Here, the regression model was adjusted for potential risk factors for hypertension such as age, gender, family history, lifestyle and metabolic factors, whose information were collected in the administered questionnaire. Also, potential effect modification of the individual and joint associations of road traffic noise and air pollution with risk of hypertension by age (<65 vs 65+ years) were assessed by incorporating interaction terms into the regression model.

3.16 Pre-testing

Data collection tools were pre-tested at Springburn communities since it shares similar characteristics with other communities studied such as an urban area with high traffic flow daily. This allowed the researcher to make the necessary corrections in the data collection tools before actual data collection in order not to commit errors, waste resources and incur costs. The measurement in the field of noise and possibly pollution levels present a potential risk to the investigator- this is acknowledged; risk assessments

have been conducted and were approved by the health and safety department of the University of the West of Scotland.

3.17 Expected results and dissemination

Data was prepared for PhD completion and conferences. The finding from the study was disseminated through peer review journals. The Environmental pollution and health journal and a copy was made available to the community centre unit for households involved in the study. After the data was analysed and prepared, a note was given to the families in the community. After considering the impact of the research and its significance, the data was disseminated to the community household.

3.18 Ethical Approval

The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and approved by the Ethics Committee of the School of Computing, Engineering and Physical Sciences SEC, University of the West of Scotland. (Approval Code: 2021-13206-13793 (application number13206) and date of approval: 17 June 2021).

Chapter 4

RESULTS

4.1 Literature search results

The second phase of our study demonstrated the relationship between air quality, environmental noise and cardiovascular health outcomes. The conceptual framework for an Environmental Health Tracking System (EHTS) for UK. Literature search was undertaken using search terms relevant to education, government, information technology, computing, engineering, environmental science, physical science, health and social science sectors. The search was carried for suitable conceptual framework on link between air quality, environmental noise and hypertension for an EHTS. The databases searched were Barbour Index, EBSCO, SpringerLink, ETHOS, Web of Science, CambridgeCore, Construction Information Service, Emerald, ScienceDirect, Scopus, Henry Stewart Journals, JSTOR, Sage Journal and World-CAT.

The literature search was restricted to the following:

- English language
- publication in any year

The search strategy was formulated by combining a series of keywords (the exact structure varied according to the search structure in each database):

‘road AND traffic AND noise AND air AND pollution AND with AND hypertension’.

The literature search in step one identified 706 articles. Furthermore, the review of article focused on titles and abstracts with two aspects. The reason for exclusion of reports was in two aspects.

- Did the article report on any process that develop and harmonize UK legislation and policy implementation in road traffic noise and air quality in an urban area?

- Did the article report exposure and health data, assessment and joint cause-effect on public health, in the framework of exposure to road traffic air-noise pollution and hypertension action plan in an urban area?

The screening questions with corresponding positive responses from articles were then added to the final sample. As a result, 135 articles were identified as appropriate to include in the review.

Figure 4:1: Flowchart illustrating selections of studies included in this review using PRISMA diagram (Prisma, 2020)

4.2 Demographic background characteristics of respondents\

4.2.1 Summary of background characteristics of respondents of SHeS Survey

Table 4:1: Gender, Age 16+ in 3 groups, Marital status - grouped, Current employment situation, household size and years of exposure

Variable	Frequency	Percentage%
Gender	n = 1920	
-Male	813	42.3
-Female	1107	57.7
Age 16+ in 3 groups	n = 1920	
16-44	448	23.3
45-64	703	36.6
65+	769	40.1
Marital status - grouped	n = 1917	
Married / civil partnership	17	0.9
Living as married	1188	62.0
Single	318	16.6
Married / civil partnership – separated	40	2.1
Divorced / dissolved civil partnership	149	7.8
Widowed / surviving civil partner	205	10.7
Don't know	2	
- Refused	1	

Current employment situation	n = 1920	
Employed and working full time	465	24.2
Employed and working part time	241	12.6
Employed but on furlough	42	2.2
Employed but on paid leave (not including furlough)	17	0.9
Employed and on unpaid leave	6	0.3
In unpaid/voluntary work	17	0.9
Self-employed and currently working	72	3.8
Self-employed but not currently working and receiving government support	8	0.4
Self-employed but not currently working and not receiving government support	8	0.4
Unemployed and seeking work	37	1.9
Unemployed and not seeking work	15	0.8
Permanently sick or disabled	59	3.1
Looking after home or family	60	3.1
In education at school/college/university	17	0.9
Retired	856	44.6
Household size recoded 10+	n = 1920	
1	565	29.4
2	882	45.9
3	215	11.2
4	195	10.2
5	52	2.7
6	8	0.4
7	3	0.2
Year(s) at home	n = 1920	
< 5	960	50.0
5-10	787	41.0
> 5	173	9.0

Health Exposure factors		
D) Valid BMI (grouped)	<i>n = 1846</i>	
Under 18.5	35	1.9
18.5 to less than 25	814	44.1
25 to less than 30	619	33.5
30 to less than 40	331	17.9
40 and over	47	2.5
No vigorous physical activities in the last 7 days	<i>n = 1920</i>	
Not mentioned	482	25.1
Mentioned	1438	74.9
Exposure to Chemical	<i>n = 1920</i>	
(D) Smoking status		
Current smoker	148	7.7
Ex-smoker	735	38.3
Never smoked	1037	54.0

There were 1920 population in our study who were at least 19 years old who were included. Missing values were not included in the study (Table 4:1). Only information pertaining to hypertension instances are included here for simplicity's sake. Nearly 40.1% of the individuals were 65 years or older because the elderly was oversampled. Additionally, Small percentage of individuals reported whiles there were large missing values in the SHeS (5.7% versus 94.3% in the general population). You can find more details on the study population elsewhere (UK data service, 2020).

Table 4:1 shows a summary of the background characteristics of respondents involved in the study has shown, majority of respondents were females (57.7%).

Four hundred forty-eight respondents representing (23.3%) were between 16-44 years and 36.6% were between 45-64 year and 40.1% were above 65+ years.

Among the current employment situation of various groups, majority have retired at 44.6% but 24.2 % is employed and working full time. 12.6% is employed and working part time. Only 17 is in education at school/college/university at 0.9%.

Also, majority of participants 62.0% had marital status as living as married. Among the various group with marital status, 16.6 % is single, 10.7% is widowed / surviving civil partner, 7.8% is divorced / dissolved civil partnership, 2.1% is married / civil partnership – separated and 0.9% is only married / civil partnership.

The Table 4:1 above presents a summary of the respondents and how they relate to the environment. As shown, majority of the respondents mentioned no vigorous physical activities in the last 7 days (74.9%). Hundred and forty-eight (7.7%), seven hundred and thirty-five (38.3) and thousand and thirty-seven (54.0 %) respondents were current smoker, ex-smoker and never smoked. Exactly 44.1% of the respondents self-reported BMI, followed by 33.5%. Exactly 17.9% of the respondents of group self-report BMI of 30 to less than whiles 1.9% of the respondents experienced severe hearing loss.

4.3 Chi-square test of the difference between the two groups (Case group and Control)

Table 4:2: Summary of background characteristics of respondents

Characteristics			Case group ^a n=177	Control group n=1742	Total subjects N=1920	p-value
Gender of respondent	Male	%	95(53.7)	718(41.2)	813(42.4)	0.001 ^c
	Female		82(46.3)	1024(58.8)	1106(57.6)	
Age16+ groups	16-44	%	6(3.4)	442(25.4)	448(23.3)	0.000 ^c
	45-64	%	52(29.4)	651(37.4)	703(36.6)	
	65+	%	119(67.2)	649(37.3)	768(40.0)	

Marital status grouped	Married / civil partnership	%	2(1.1)	15(0.9)	17(0.9)	0.002 ^c
	Living as married	%	111(62.7)	1076(61.9)	1187(62.0)	
	Single	%	16(9.0)	302(17.4)	318(16.6)	
	Married / civil partnership – separated	%	2(1.1)	38(2.2)	40(2.1)	
	Divorced / dissolved civil partnership	%	13(7.3)	136(7.8)	149(7.8)	
	Widowed / surviving civil partner	%	33(18.6)	172(9.9)	205(10.7)	
Current employment situation	Employed and working full time	%	18(10.2)	447(25.7)	465(24.2)	0.000 ^c
	Employed and working part time	%	21(11.9)	220(12.6)	241(12.6)	
	Employed but on furlough	%	3(1.7)	39(2.2)	42(2.2)	
	Employed but on paid leave (not including furlough)	%	1(0.6)	16(0.9)	17(0.9)	
	Employed and on unpaid leave	%	1(0.6)	5(0.3)	6(0.3)	
	In unpaid/voluntary work	%	0(0.0)	17(1.0)	17(0.9)	
	Self-employed and currently working	%	6(3.4)	66(3.8)	72(3.8)	
	Self-employed but not currently working and	%	2(1.1)	6(0.3)	8(0.4)	

	receiving government support					
	Self-employed but not currently working and not receiving government support	%	1(0.6)	70(0.4)	8(0.4)	
	Unemployed and seeking work	%	0(0.0)	37(2.1)	37(1.9)	
	Unemployed and not seeking work	%	1(0.6)	14(0.8)	15(0.8)	
	Permanently sick or disabled	%	3(1.7)	56(3.2)	59(3.1)	
	Looking after home or family	%	1(0.6)	59(3.4)	60(3.1)	
	In education at school/college/university	%	0(0.0)	17(1.0)	17(0.9)	
	Retired	%	119(67.2)	736(42.3)	855(44.6)	
Whether had COVID-19	Yes diagnosed and recovered	%	0(0.0)	5(0.3)	5(0.3)	0.330 ^c
	Yes diagnosed and still ill	%	0(0.0)	3(0.2)	3(0.2)	
Sugary snack or drink once a day or more	Once a day or more	%	124(70.1)	1157(66.4)	1281(66.8)	0.328 ^c
Frequency of eating sweets or chocolates	Once a day or more	%	51(29.0)	467(26.8)	518(27.0)	0.543 ^c
Whether ever smoked	Yes	%	86(48.6)	796(45.7)	882(46.0)	0.462 ^c

**cigarette / cigar
/ pipe**

Any depression symptoms	One or more depression symptoms	%	32(18.2)	302(17.4)	334(17.5)	0.485 ^c
Any anxiety symptoms	One or more depression symptoms	%	30(17.0)	345(19.9)	375(19.6)	0.372 ^c
No vigorous physical activities in the last 7 days	Mentioned	%	151(85.3)	1286(73.8)	1437(74.9)	0.001 ^c

^a Subjects had the previous diagnosis of hypertension while living at the current address and ^cChi-square test of the difference between the two groups.

Table 4:2 depicts, age, gender, marital status, current employment situation and no vigorous physical activities in the last 7 days were all significantly different between the case and control groups. The case group's subjects were noticeably older and had higher no vigorous physical activities in the last 7 days than the control group's subjects. The case group also included a greater percentage of female and those with higher no vigorous physical activities in the last 7 days.

4.4 Prevalence and characteristics of hypertension

4.4.1 Medical History

Table 4:3: Medical history of respondents

Variable	Households	Percentage (%)	p-value
Hypertension			
No condition presents	1742	97.9 %	< .001
Has condition	177	2.1 %	
Ever had high BP			
Yes	598	31.2 %	< .001
No	1320	68.8 %	
Doctor diagnosed high BP			
Yes	590	98.7 %	< .001
No	8	1.3 %	
Pregnant when told had high BP			
Yes	61	21.0%	< .001
No	229	79.0%	

High BP other than when pregnant			
Yes	35	58.3%	< .001
No	25	41.7%	
(D) Doctor diagnosed hypertension (excluding pregnant)			
Yes	561	29.3 %	< .001
No	1355	70.7 %	
(D) Ever had high BP (excludes only had high BP during pregnancy)			
Yes	573	29.9 %	< .001
No	1345	70.1 %	

Source: UK data service, 2020

Only a small proportion of the participants in our study indicated having hypertension condition 2.1%, (Table 4:3). High number of participants reported to ever had high BP and doctor diagnosed high BP of exactly 598 and 590 out of 1920 for each group, although doctor diagnosed hypertension (excluding pregnant) and ever had high BP (excludes only had high BP during pregnancy) participant were slightly higher (561 and 573 of population for each group).

As shown in Table 4:3, there was not much difference in the household's group in terms of their history of doctor diagnosed high BP and those with hypertension condition. Similarly, in terms of their history of doctor diagnosed hypertension (excluding pregnant) and ever had high BP (excludes only had high BP during pregnancy), there was not much difference among the household group.

97.9 % have no condition present of hypertension among respondent, but 98.7 % have been diagnosed high BP by doctor among respondents. 29.3 % and 29.9 % of doctor diagnosed hypertension (excluding pregnant) and ever had high BP (excludes only had high BP during pregnancy) suffered among respondents respectively.

Five hundred and ninety-eight (31.2 %) respondents were reported ever to have had high BP. 21.0% were reported to have been pregnant when told they had high BP while 58.3% claimed to have high BP when they were not pregnant. History of ever had high BP and doctor diagnosed high BP, were significantly higher among the households in the community. As

shown in Table 4:3 compared to doctor diagnosed hypertension (excluding pregnant) and those that ever had high BP (excludes only had high BP during pregnancy), 98.7 % of households reported that doctor diagnosed high BP ($p < 0.001$). As indicated by respondents, ever had high BP, doctor diagnosed high BP, doctor diagnosed hypertension (excluding pregnant) and ever had high BP (excludes only had high BP during pregnancy) was mostly reported with high BP. The results for participant hypertension were only tangentially related to one another; p values ($p < 0.001$) are significant across all the prevalence of hypertension (Table 4:3).

. In comparison to participant with condition of hypertension were less, the prevalence of hypertension was twice as high in those who reported not having condition. As a result, we chose to use “Hypertension” as our main model, which includes adjustments for the age, gender, and lifestyle. This is because it shows clearly those with hypertension condition and those with no hypertension condition.

4.5 Prevalence of hypertension among household’s persons (those of the 5 sampling locations) and control group

The table 4:4 below represent the prevalence of hypertension among household’s persons from the five monitoring location and control group using secondary data.

Table 4:4: Prevalence of hypertension among various groups of respondents

Category of household’s persons	Hypertension		Chi square /p- value
	No condition present(N%)	Has condition(N%)	
SITES EDB	89(89)	10 (10.1)	4.36 (p= 0.50)
EDK	139 (90.8)	14 (9.2)	
GHS	66 (91.7)	6 (8.3)	
GK	72 (90.0)	8 (10.0)	
GT	39 (86.7)	6 (13.3)	
Control group	95 (96.0)	4 (4.0)	
Total	500 (91.2)	48(8.8)	

Comparatively, as shown in Table 4:4, a higher prevalence was observed among household's persons at EDK followed by EDB. With respect to the no hypertension condition present, more than 50% of respondents from all the household persons do not have hypertension condition diagnosed by the doctor (89.0%, 90.8%, 91.7%, 90.0%, 86.7%, 96.0%) respectively. Percentage respondents with hypertension were comparatively lower among respondent with no condition of hypertension. The control group respondent with hypertension has the lowest percentage (4%) compared to the other groups. These differences in the hypertension among respondents from various private households' environment was not statistically significant ($\chi^2=4.36$, $p=0.50$), indicating slight influence of the household environment on the hypertension of the respondent.

Table 4:5: Relationship between household's environment and hypertension

Household's persons environment		Hypertension		Total	OR (95%CI)
		No condition presents N (%)	Has condition N (%)		
Air pollution exposure	Households' persons	146 (95.4)	7 (4.6)	153	
	Control group	1596 (90.4)	169 (9.6)	1765	2.21(1.02,4.79) **
Total		1742 (90.8)	176 (9.2)	1918	

**P<0.05 CI=Confidence interval

As shown in Table 4:5, there was statistically significant association between levels of pollutants (PM_{2.5}, NO₂ and PM₁₀) and hypertension. Households' persons who were recruited from the households near road who had been exposed to air concentration beyond tolerable levels were 2.21 times more likely to have hypertension (OR=2.21; 95% CI=1.02,4.79; $p<0.05$). The percentage of persons with hypertension among the households' persons was 4.6% as against 9.6% among control group. There is a positive association between exposure

to air pollution and hypertension. The findings show that, it is likely that household environment exposed to road traffic air pollution will have hypertension.

Table 4:6: Relationship between household’s environment and hypertension

Household’s persons environment		Hypertension		Total	OR (95%CI)
		No condition presents N (%)	Has condition N (%)		
Noise exposure	Households’ persons	146 (95.4)	7 (4.6)	153	2.20(1.01,4.79) **
	Control group	1596 (90.4)	169 (9.6)	1765	
Total		1742 (90.8)	176 (9.2)	1918	

**P<0.05 CI=Confidence interval

As shown in Table 4:6, there was statistically significant association between air pollution exposure and hypertension. Households’ persons who were recruited from the households near road who had been exposed to noise at different component frequencies beyond tolerable levels were 2.2 times more likely to have hypertension (OR=2.20; 95% CI=1.01,4.79; p<0.05). The percentage of persons with hypertension among the households’ persons was 4.6% as against 9.6% among control group. This means increased likelihood, positive association. There is a positive association between exposure to noise at different frequency and hypertension. The findings show that, it is likely that household environment exposed to road traffic noise will have hypertension.

4.6 Road Annual Daily Traffic Flow

Figure 4:2 below depicts the difference in the monitoring sites concerning the annual daily traffic flow. The maximum and the minimum number of traffic flows were 12,902 (cars and taxis) at GT and 20 (two-wheel motor) at GHS, respectively. Car and taxi vehicles in all the monitoring sites have the highest traffic flow, from 5,004 to 12,902 vehicles. Afterwards, low goods vehicles (lgvs) similarly had the following highest number of traffic flow in all the monitoring sites, from 722 to 2,387 vehicles. The two-wheel motor had the minimum annual traffic flow at all the monitoring sites, from 18 to 89 vehicles. The findings clearly show a high daily traffic flow at all the monitoring sites.

latitude	longitude	link_length	link_length_estimation	r_estimation	r_estimation_us	pedal_cycles	two_wheeled	cars_and_taxis	buses_and_coaches	lgvs	hgvs_2_rigid	hgvs_3_rigid	hgvs_4_or_more	hgvs_3_or_4	hgvs_5_artic	hgvs_6_artic	all_hgvs	all_motor_vehicle_traffic_sites
55.865488	-4.2355045	0.3	0.19	Estimated	Estimated us	272	41	9,829	374	1,703	263	20	8	3	11	6	311	12,259 EDB
55.856522	-4.2589577	0.2	0.12	Estimated	Estimated us	442	89	11,377	74	1,318	122	49	21	5	6	8	212	13,069 GK
55.867183	-4.2362412	0.6	0.37	Estimated	Estimated us	24	18	5,576	153	722	68	7	10	7	8	3	103	6,571 GHS
55.870681	-4.2690032	0.3	0.19	Estimated	Estimated us	97	67	12,902	194	2,387	143	34	21	7	10	38	252	15,801 GT
55.862368	-4.1586162	2.8	1.74	Estimated	Estimated us	61	20	5,004	140	1,028	128	32	8	4	10	3	186	6,378 EDK

Figure 4:2: Annual daily traffic flow of the type of vehicles in various monitoring sites

Table 4:7: Spearman correlations between frequency components of road noise levels, air pollutants, and traffic flow rates.

Type of Vehicle	Annual Daily Traffic Flow	Low Freq 31.5Hz	63 Hz	125 Hz	Mid Freq 250 Hz	500 Hz	1 KHz	High Freq 2 KHz	4 KHz	8 KHz	NO ₂ µg/m ³	PM ₁₀ µg/m ³	PM _{2.5} µg/m ³
two wheels motors	235	0.000	0.600	0.600	-0.103	0.410	0.335	0.400	0.400	0.700	0.300	0.447	0.224
Car and taxi	4468	0.000	0.900 *	0.900 *	-0.205	0.821	0.671	0.500	0.500	0.800	0.300	0.224	0.447
buses	935	-0.707	0.000	0.600	0.205	0.718	0.783	0.600	0.600	0.500	-0.700	-0.894 *	-0.447
Igvs	7158	-0.354	0.500	0.900 *	-0.205	0.821	0.894 *	0.900 *	0.900 *	1.000 **	-0.300	-0.224	-0.112
All hgvs	1064	-0.707	0.200	0.800	0.205	0.718	0.783	0.800	0.800	0.900 *	-0.500	-0.447	-0.447

¹ Igvs-low goods vehicles hgvs-heavy goods vehicles, * Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed), ** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

All hgvs had high-frequency traffic noise components at 8KHz substantially (all *p* values 0.050) but strongly correlated ($\rho = 0.900$). There was a positive correlation across the frequency range. Only the buses were significant with PM₁₀ and had a negative strong correlation coefficient $\rho = -0.894$.

The total traffic flow rate was significant (all *p*-values 0.050) although strongly correlated (ρ ranged from 0.900 to 1.000) with most high and low-frequency traffic noise components.

From Table 4:7, it was observed that the correlation between PM₁₀ and NO₂ spearman's ρ (R) value of 0.380 was statistically significant since the results showed a smaller *p*-value of 0.001. The correlation between (PM_{2.5} and NO₂) and (PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀) (spearman's ρ value 0.345) and 0.897 respectively was statistically significant since results showed a smaller *p*-value of 0.001.

4.7 Noise frequency range measurements at community study (Primary data)

Figure 4:3: Community noise levels (LAeq) measured at different frequency component at urban areas in central belt of Scotland (30/11/2020-3/03/2021)

Table 4:8: Normality in distribution of annual noise levels(dB) at different frequency range in five monitoring sites (23/11/2020-24/11/2021)

	Low (31Hz-250Hz)					Mid(250Hz-2KHz)					High(2KHz-16KHz)				
	EDB	EDK	GHS	GK	GT	EDB	EDK	GHS	GK	GT	EDB	EDK	GHS	GK	GT
Mean	41.98	50.40	51.03	53.28	45.25	45.42	50.62	53.22	51.56	47.39	30.33	34.74	37.85	36.32	31.01
Std. Deviation	8.20	14.85	10.79	6.05	9.11	9.73	13.11	10.27	8.94	8.78	7.80	15.02	8.66	7.59	8.41
Shapiro-Wilk	0.92	0.90	0.92	0.93	0.89	0.95	0.93	0.86	0.95	0.98	0.97	0.84	0.91	0.95	0.78
P-value of Shapiro-Wilk	0.210	0.098	0.243	0.290	0.068	0.455	0.331	0.028	0.558	0.936	0.786	0.015	0.135	0.576	0.003
Minimum	27.11	34.74	30.90	44.49	34.04	24.19	32.01	26.13	34.42	33.45	18.90	20.68	15.90	25.33	23.81
Maximum	53.40	83.62	67.81	66.34	69.26	64.08	76.19	66.73	67.79	65.96	45.24	63.12	48.08	49.87	54.68

Various community households have different frequency component with different noise level.

Table 4:8 displays the noise levels at different frequency component among household persons at various communities. At low frequency noise measurement values at five monitoring sites values range from 27.111 dB to 83.619dB. At mid frequency noise measurement values at five monitoring sites range from 24.186 dBA to 76.186 dBA. Also, at high frequency component measurement values at five monitoring sites range from 18.895 dBA to 63.118dBA. In all the household in community visited, it was realised that they all produced an excessive amount of noise with risk of hypertension of the households. Again, at all the frequency component noise level was intermittent, hence the maximum and the minimum values quoted.

Noise levels have a significant effect between different frequency component $\chi^2(2) = 109.00$, $p < .001$ at all the five monitoring sites using Kendall's Wallis test.

Table 4:9: Relationship between joint annual average road traffic noise frequency component and concentration of NO₂, PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} in all the five monitoring sites

		NO ₂	PM ₁₀	PM _{2.5}	LOW	MID	HIGH
NO ₂	Spearman's rho	-					
	<i>p</i> -value	-					
PM ₁₀	Spearman's rho	0.380 ***	-				
	<i>p</i> -value	<0.001	-				
PM _{2.5}	Spearman's rho	0.345 ***	0.897 ***	-			
	<i>p</i> -value	<0.001	<0.001	-			
LOW	Spearman's rho	-0.083	0.042	0.098	-		
	<i>p</i> -value	0.114	0.517	0.127	-		
MID	Spearman's rho	-0.012	0.081	0.145 *	0.852 ***	-	
	<i>p</i> -value	0.823	0.208	0.024	<0.001	-	
HIGH	Spearman's rho	-0.054	0.063	0.119	0.864 ***	0.976 ***	-
	<i>p</i> -value	0.308	0.328	0.063	<0.001	<0.001	-

Note. * $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.001$

Table 4:9 also shows that the relationship between the mid-frequency component and PM_{2.5} spearman's rho value 0.145 was statistically significant because their *p*-values were lesser

than the significance level of 5%. On the other hand, the relationship between mid and low noise frequency component spearman's rho value of 0.852 was statistically significant since results showed a smaller p -value of 0.001. Additionally, the relationship between high, and low noise frequency component spearman's rho value of 0.864 was statistically significant due to a smaller p -value of 0.001. Similarly, the relationship between high, and mid noise frequency component spearman's rho value 0.976 was statistically significant since results showed a smaller p -value of 0.001. The correlation is high and significant since there was a smaller p -value of 0.001 across air concentration and noise at different frequency components.

This implies that the risk of hypertension is significantly associated with (mid noise frequency component and PM_{2.5}), (PM₁₀ and NO₂), (PM_{2.5} and NO₂), (PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀), (mid and low), (high and low), (high and mid noise frequency component) respectively.

4.8 Geospatial results of data at five locations

Data results from an air quality index (AQI) description and noise levels in a spatial view were joined. The data contains the number of air pollutants in each particulate matter less than 10 microns (PM₁₀), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), particulate matter less than 2.5 microns (PM_{2.5}), and noise level in Lden, which was computed from daytime, night-time, and evening time noise level dB(A).

The population of cases on hypertension register and hypertension rate on patients for hospital in 2020 utilising an external database. The database includes all hypertension register and hypertension rate that are covered by hospital nationwide as part of the disease prevalence at GP offices in Scotland.

The NO₂, PM₁₀, and PM_{2.5} concentration($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) and noise level in Lden, calculated from daytime, nighttime, and evening noise level dB(A), are all included in the data. In this study, the data on hypertension prevalence were used for "Data Visualization", as displayed below in Figure 4:7.

For hypertension registrations, the Scottish NHS Board, HSCP, Cluster, and GP practice levels are presented in Figure 4:7. Hypertension registrations aggregated at the HSCP level (and occasionally at the Cluster level) were not used since these data are not accessible for all practices. This result description contains the 2019 hypertension prevalence at the GP offices based on their identification number, the total population of hypertension register, and the rate. The joint annual average of air pollutants ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), noise pollution at Lden, and hypertension register were examined.

4.9 A model of road traffic noise level(Lden) at five specific monitoring areas (23/11/2020)

The simulation of annual road traffic noise pollution in Greater Glasgow is exhibited in five different locations (23/11/2020-23-11/2021).

(a)

(b)

(c) **Figure 4:4: A model of road traffic annual average noise level (Lden) at monitoring areas at five monitoring locations (23 November 2021): (a) road traffic noise (Lden) at GHS, GK, and GT; (b) road traffic noise (Lden) at EDK; (c) road traffic noise (Lden) at EDB.**

The simulation of annual road traffic noise pollution in Greater Glasgow is in five different locations (23 November 2020–23 November 2021).

It carried out a comparison of measured and modelled data. In that situation, it might be determined that there are various buildings affected by road traffic noise. The simulation enables traffic noise to be assigned to facilities that enhance the clarity of how noise affects residents and be recommended for noise assessment and planning.

Buildings are labelled with different colours based on the amount of noise produced by the road. Maximum noise level is recorded at the various locations of the facades of buildings located at the intersection and areas along the route. Our findings show that the annual (Lden) noise level of some of these structures is at the highest level at GK, GHS, and EDB, exceeding 80dB(A), in Figure 4:4a,c. Furthermore, as shown in Figure 4:4b, the EDK max noise level was between 65 to 69 dB(A), and during peak hours. This depicts that buildings near crossings are subject to noise levels exceeding 80 dB(A). This finding concludes that the residents in the areas are exposed to noise beyond recommended limit, and noise on the facade of evaluated facilities should not exceed 65 dB(A) according to Scotland's regulatory standards. Due to their

location along the city's busiest roadways, the analysed buildings are the most endangered by noise.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 4:5: A model of annual road traffic noise levels (Lden) at monitoring areas at five monitoring locations (23 November 2021): (a) Community noise level (Lden) at GHS, GT, and GK; (b) Community noise level (Lden) at EDK; (c) Community noise level (Lden) at EDB.

Figure 4:5 depicts the structure at a specific site in the Lden (day, evening, and night). The noise levels at the receiver points on one system are noticeably different. For example, in the building depicted in Figure 4:5a–c, there are two receiver locations with noise levels greater than 80 dB(A), one receiver point with annual noise levels of 75–79 dB(A), and one receiver point with noise levels of 65–69 dB(A), and one receiver point with an annual noise level of 50–54 dB(A). It was observed in Figure 4:5c that, the EDB area shows a high noise level. Therefore, EDK (b) is the second most endangered building.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Index	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	Legend:
P.M10	Low	Low	Low	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	High	High	High	Very High	○ No level
Band	Low	Low	Low	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	High	High	High	Very High	○ < 35 dB(A)
μgm^{-3}	0-16	17-33	34-50	51-58	59-66	67-75	76-83	84-91	91-100	101 or more	● 35 - 39 dB(A)
P.M2.5	0-11	12-23	24-35	36-41	42-47	48-53	54-58	59-64	65-70	71 or more	● 40 - 44 dB(A)
μgm^{-3}	0-11	12-23	24-35	36-41	42-47	48-53	54-58	59-64	65-70	71 or more	● 45 - 49 dB(A)
NO2	0-67	68-134	135-200	201-267	268-334	335-400	401-467	468-534	535-600	601 or more	● 50 - 54 dB(A)
μgm^{-3}	0-67	68-134	135-200	201-267	268-334	335-400	401-467	468-534	535-600	601 or more	● 55 - 59 dB(A)
											● 60 - 64 dB(A)
											● 65 - 69 dB(A)
											● 70 - 74 dB(A)
											● 75 - 79 dB(A)
											● >= 80 dB(A)

Legend: Building noise levels from road

○ < 35 dB(A)	■ 45 - 49 dB(A)	■ 60 - 64 dB(A)	■ 70 - 74 dB(A)
■ 35 - 39 dB(A)	■ 50 - 54 dB(A)	■ 65 - 69 dB(A)	■ 75 - 79 dB(A)
■ 40 - 44 dB(A)	■ 55 - 59 dB(A)	■ 70 - 74 dB(A)	■ >= 80 dB(A)

Road noise

Figure 4:6: Joint annual average NO₂, PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} concentration($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), and noise level (Lden) at five monitoring locations (23 November,2021): (a) Joint air-noise pollution (Lden)/($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) at GHS, GT and GK; (b) Joint air-noise pollution (Lden)/($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) at EDB; (c) Joint air-noise pollution (Lden)/($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) at EDK.

Figure 4:6a shows joint air and noise pollution levels. The air quality index number is one, and two offer leading (band). The annual average PM_{2.5} concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) regarding air pollution levels at all five monitoring areas was between 0–11 except in three monitoring areas (GHS, GT, and GK) Figure 4:6b, annual average PM_{2.5} concentration was 12–23 ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) respectively. According to actionable recommendations and health advice, it is recommended that individuals in that areas can enjoy their usual outdoor activities with no risk. Coincidentally, Figure 4:6a,b shows, noise levels exceeding 65 dB(A), especially among EDB, GHS, and GK residents. There are unsafe levels of road traffic noise, making individuals in the building highly endangered and prone to the risk of hypertension.

The annual average NO₂ concentration regarding air pollution levels at all five monitoring areas was between 0 and 159 ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$), respectively. According to actionable recommendations and health advice, it is recommended individuals in that areas can enjoy their usual outdoor activities with low risk.

As shown in Figure 4:6b, the model was statistically significant because their *p*-values were lower than the significance level of 5%, and the *p*-value was 0.009901. The findings indicate that there was clustering in the map. If autocorrelation exists in a map, the condition that observations are independent of one another is violated. The plot shows the distribution of Moran's I values; the red vertical line shows our observed Moran's I value of 0.20637. The *p*-value provided by the Monte-Carlo (MC) simulation was 0.01, indicating a 1% risk of rejecting the null hypothesis incorrectly or a 1% chance that our observed pattern is consistent with a random process. There is a similar observation of values from road traffic noise (Lden) and NO₂, PM₁₀, and PM_{2.5} at the EDB monitoring area. There was a positive spatial autocorrelation association between noise levels (Lden) and air pollution concentrations (NO₂, PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}) $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$. This means that there was clustering in the map.

On the other hand, as shown in Figure 4:6c, there was a negative spatial autocorrelation but not statistically significant because their *p*-values were not lesser than the significance level of 5%.

The p -value is 0.6535, indicating there was dispersion in the map. The plot shows the distribution of Moran's I values, and the red vertical line shows our observed Moran's I value of -0.10214 . The p -value provided by the MC simulation was 0.65, indicating a less than 1% risk of rejecting the null hypothesis incorrectly or a less than 1% chance that our observed pattern is consistent with a random process. Negative spatial autocorrelation shows the neighbours of sites with large values have small values, the neighbours of locations with intermediate values have intermediate values, and the neighbours of locations with small values have large values. Therefore, road traffic noise (Lden) is influenced by NO_2 , PM_{10} and $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ at the EDK monitoring locations. Dissimilar values tend to group together on a map.

From Figure 4:6a it was observed that the model was statistically significant because their p -values were lower than the significance level of 0.1%. The p -value is 0.09901, which indicates that there was clustering in the map. The p -value provided by the MC simulation was 0.1 and our observed Moran's I value of 0.0267, indicating a 1% risk of rejecting the null hypothesis incorrectly or a 1% chance that our observed pattern is consistent with a random process. There was a positive spatial autocorrelation association between noise levels (Lden) and air pollution concentrations (NO_2 , PM_{10} and $\text{PM}_{2.5}$).

Road traffic noise (Lden) is associated positively with NO_2 , PM_{10} and $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ at the GK monitoring locations.

From Figure 4:6a, it was observed that, the model was statistically significant because their p -values were lower than the significance level of 5%, and the p -value was 0.009901. Findings indicate that there was clustering in the map. The plot shows the distribution of Moran's I values; the red vertical line shows our observed Moran's I value of 0.15667. The p -value provided by the MC simulation was 0.01, indicating a 1% risk of rejecting the null hypothesis incorrectly or a 1% chance that our observed pattern is consistent with a random process. There is a similar observation of values from road traffic noise (Lden) and NO_2 , PM_{10} and $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ at the GT monitoring area. There was a positive spatial autocorrelation association between noise

levels (Lden) and air pollution concentrations (NO₂, PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}). That is, road traffic noise (Lden) is being influenced by NO₂, PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} at the GT monitoring area significantly.

(a)

(b)

(c)

	Index	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
P.M10	Band	Low	Low	Low	Moderate	Moderate	Moderate	High	High	High	Very High	Legend: ○ No level ● < 35 dB(A) ● 35 - 39 dB(A) ● 40 - 44 dB(A) ● 45 - 49 dB(A) ● 50 - 54 dB(A) ● 55 - 59 dB(A) ● 60 - 64 dB(A) ● 65 - 69 dB(A) ● 70 - 74 dB(A) ● 75 - 79 dB(A) ● >= 80 dB(A)
	µgm ⁻³	0-16	17-33	34-50	51-58	59-66	67-75	76-83	84-91	91-100	101 or more	
P.M2.5	µgm ⁻³	0-11	12-23	24-35	36-41	42-47	48-53	54-58	59-64	65-70	71 or more	Legend: Building noise levels from road □ < 35 dB(A) □ 45 - 49 dB(A) □ 60 - 64 dB(A) □ 70 - 74 dB(A) □ 35 - 39 dB(A) □ 50 - 54 dB(A) □ 65 - 69 dB(A) □ 75 - 79 dB(A) □ 40 - 44 dB(A) □ 55 - 59 dB(A) □ 70 - 74 dB(A) □ >= 80 dB(A)
NO2	µgm ⁻³	0-67	68-134	135-200	201-267	268-334	335-400	401-467	468-534	535-600	601 or more	

Figure 4:7: Joint annual average NO₂, PM₁₀, and PM_{2.5} concentrations (µg/m³) and noise level (Lden) at five monitoring locations (23 November 2021): (a) joint air-noise pollution and hypertension at GK, GT, and GHS; (b) joint air-noise pollution and hypertension at EDK; and (c) joint air-noise pollution and hypertension at EDB.

The model is statistically significant, as shown in Figure 4:7a-c, because its *p*-values are below the 5% significance level. A value of 0.009901 is the *p*-value. The results suggest that

hypertension is a clustered condition rather than an isolated one, meaning there is clustering on the map. The assumption that the observations are independent of one another is not supported if there is clustering in a map. The red vertical line on the plot represents the distribution of the Moran's I values and the value of 0.4136 observed. The MC simulation gave a p -value of 0.01, representing a 1% risk of mistakenly rejecting the null hypothesis or a 1% possibility that our observed pattern is consistent with a random process. The Moran's spatial autocorrelation is positive. Therefore, the value of 0.4136 is closest to one.

Our findings depict that hypertension is significantly influenced by NO_2 , PM_{10} , $\text{PM}_{2.5}$, and L_{den} at all monitoring locations. The positive association between pollution and hypertension increases with increasing pollution by NO_2 , PM_{10} , $\text{PM}_{2.5}$, and noise level L_{den} .

Figure 4:8: Clustering map of air pollutant, noise level and hypertension register at Greater Glasgow in central belt of Scotland

4.10 RELATIONSHIP OF NOISE LEVEL AT DIFFERENT PERIODS AND FREQUENCY COMPONENT USING TERNARY PLOT COORDINATES

NOISE LEVEL AT MEASURED PERIODS

NOISE LEVEL AT FREQUENCY

GHS

GK

EDK

Figure 4:9: Ternary plot using percentage of noise level at frequency component for each monitoring sites for each measured period

The Figure 4:9 depict the three attractors in the model at both sections are daytime, evening

time, night time and low frequency component, mid frequency component and high frequency component respectively.

There seem to be a strong and perfect linear relationship of noise level across all the daytime, evening time and night time. There is a general perfect positive linear correlation in all monitoring areas. The strength of the correlation is strong relationship across all measured period of the daytime. Across all the measured period they seem to have a perfect strong relation of noise level. Therefore, there is a strong association of noise level at all measured periods at all the monitoring area. As shown in Figure 4:9, a ternary diagram has three apexes at average noise level at measured period. Thus, night time noise level (23:00-7:00 hr) is on the lower right, noise level at day time (7:00-19:00 hr) is in the lower left, and noise level at evening time (19:00-23:00 hr) is at the top.

Since all monitoring sites are all near the triangle's centre, they are all clustering, just like in the Moran index model. The point plotted inside the triangle or on one of the side lines, however, denotes made up of a mixture of average noise level at different measured periods. In a ternary plot, see how the shading of noise level at daytime into evening time and evening time into night time is depicted in the drawing in Figure 4:9 at GT monitoring site. This plot depicts relationship of noise level at any period of the 24hrs in a day. Clockwise of the time in day is equal to 100%. Otherwise, 24hrs is equal to 100%. The daytime is 12hrs. Therefore 12 hrs will be equal to 50% proportion of the whole day. Noise level for 12hrs is equal to 50% proportion of the day. At the evening time is 4hrs. This depicts that 4hrs is equal to 17% proportion of the day. The night time is 8hr and equal to 33% in a day. The monitoring sites GT has the following composition:

40% evening time | 35% night time | 25% daytime = 100%.

If 12hrs is equal to 100% for daytime, therefore 25% is 3hrs. This means that maximum average noise level was 64.8 dBA at the 3rd hour of the daytime, exactly 10am. Noise level of the colour indicates the strength of the effects. If 4hrs is equal 100% proportion, then 40% is 1hrs. This means the maximum average noise level was 44.4 dBA at the 1st hour of the evening at around

8:00pm.

One the other hand, the Figure 4:9 also shows on the right section that, the noise level at different frequency component can be represented as a single point that is positioned in relation to each of the three vectors to the dimensions low-mid, mid-high, and high-low triangular representation. This fundamental pattern can be enhanced and altered, in a wide variety of ways. The five monitoring sites has five systems that predominates, with noise level. The triangle at all monitoring shows a positive relationship between low (31.5Hz-125Hz) frequency component, mid (250Hz-2KHz) frequency component and high (2KHz-16Hz) frequency component at 99 dBA of noise level. They move at the same direction. There is clustering effect.

The triangle at shows a general positive linear correlation in all monitoring areas. Across all the measured period they seem to have a perfect strong relation of noise level. Therefore, there is a strong association between low (31.5Hz-125Hz), (250Hz-2KHz), and (2KHz-16Hz) frequency component noise level at all the monitoring area.

Table 4:10: Relationship of noise level within the different frequency component

Cases	Sphericity Correction	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p	η^2	η^2_p	ω^2
Noise level	Greenhouse-Geisser	10788.744	1.418	7608.821	280.552	< .001	0.798	0.798	0.316
Residuals	Greenhouse-Geisser	2730.330	100.673	27.121					

Table 4:10 shown that Mauchly's test of sphericity indicates that the assumption of sphericity is violated ($p < .05$). Since Mauchly's test of sphericity was significant, the Greenhouse-Geisser correction was used. This showed that noise levels differed significantly between the different frequency component. $F(1.418, 100.673) = 280.552, p < .001, \omega^2 = 0.316$.

Table 4:11: Comparing of noise level at low, mid and high frequency component

	Mean Difference	95% CI for Mean Difference		p _{bonf}	p _{holm}
		Lower	Upper		
Low Mid	-1.243	-3.013	0.528	0.274	0.091
High	14.332	12.561	16.103	< .001 ***	< .001 ***
Mid High	15.575	13.804	17.345	< .001 ***	< .001 ***

*** p < .001

According to Table 4:11, Pairwise comparisons showed that low-high and mid-high frequency component is significantly different between each noise level (p<0.001) except low-mid frequency component (p = 0.319) at all the five monitoring sites.

Figure 4:10: The magnitude of noise level at the three-frequency component (low, mid, and high) in all five monitoring sites.

From Table 4:11, Post hoc testing using the Bonferroni correction revealed that noise level decreased significantly as frequency component increase, at low-high frequency component (mean difference=14.332units, p<.001) and mid-high frequency component (mean difference = 15.575 units, p<.001) but between low-mid frequency component (mean difference = -1.243units, p = 0.274) noise level increases significantly as frequency component increase.

4.11 Noise exposure period

Comparing noise levels between different measured periods was significant across all hours of the day, night, and evening.

			Statistic	p
DAYTIME	-	EVENING	Inf	<.001
DAYTIME	-	NIGHT-TIME	Inf	<.001
EVENING	-	NIGHT-TIME	Inf	<.001

4.11.1 Average noise level at different measured periods (primary data)

The figure 4:11 below is the average road traffic noise level measured at various periods (day,night and evening) at the monitoring sites.

Figure 4:11: Average noise exposure at different measured periods at five monitoring sites for respondents

The Figure 4:11 above shows the average road traffic noise exposure periods for the respondents. It is shown that the respondents at GK are being exposed to 89dBA, 74dBA and 84dBA during daytime and night-time respectively. This was followed by respondents from GHS being exposed to between 6 and 8 hours. With those being exposed to traffic for daytime and night-time being the majority at all monitoring sites.

Noise levels have a significant effect between different frequency component $\chi^2 (2) = 10.0$, $p < .007$ at all the five monitoring sites.

χ^2	df	P
10.0	2	0.007

Figure 4:12: Relationship of average noise level within different measured periods at five monitoring sites

The Figure 4:12 shows a general perfect positive linear correlation in all monitoring areas. It depicts a strong positive correlation (or relationship) across all measured period of the daytime. They move in the same direction. Across all the measured period they seem to have a perfect strong relationship of noise level across measured periods. Therefore, there is a strong association of noise level at all measured periods at all the monitoring area. This means that while noise level increase during the daytime, noise level also increases during the night-time.

4.12 Multivariate Analysis and Scatter Matrix Analysis of Joint Air Concentration and Noise Level at Frequency Component Range with Hypertension Rate and Registered Hypertension Cases

Figure 4:13: Relationship between joint air concentration and noise level at different frequency component range and hypertension rate at the five monitoring sites: (a) Joint air-noise pollution (dBA)/($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) with hypertension rate at GT; (b) Joint air-noise pollution (dBA)/ ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) with hypertension rate at GK; (c) Joint air-noise pollution (dBA)/($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) with hypertension rate at EDB; (d) Joint air- noise pollution (dBA)/($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) with hypertension rate at GHS; (e) Joint air-noise pollution (Lden)/ ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) hypertension rate at EDK.

The Figure 4:13a–e shows a positive relationship between joint air concentration and noise level at different frequency component range and hypertension rate. As shown in Figure 4:13a–e, it moves in the same direction at all monitoring sites. Figure 4:13a–e seems to be a bell curve showing a Pearson correlation and a normal distribution at all the monitoring sites, except for EDB in Figure 4:13c. Figure 4:13a–e also shows a general nonlinear correlation at all monitoring areas, except for EDB in Figure 4:13c. From Figure 4:13a–e there is a clustering of data across all the monitoring sites, except for EDB in Figure 4:13c. A cluster is a collection of dots that exhibit the same overall pattern. They move in a straight line or a curved line. Numerous points can be found in clusters. On the other hand, as shown in Figure 4:13a–e, there are also outliers at all monitoring sites. The strength of the correlation is strong because there is clustering across all monitoring areas. This means hypertension is not an isolated case but a clustered one. This indicates that there is clustering on the map. Therefore, a mutual association exists between joint air concentration and noise level at the frequency component range and hypertension rate.

Figure 4:14: Relationship between joint air concentration and noise level at different frequency component range and registered hypertension cases at the five monitoring sites:
(a) Joint air-noise pollution (dBA)/(µg/m³) with registered hypertension cases at EDB;
(b) Joint air-noise pollution (dBA)/(µg/m³) with registered hypertension cases at GK;
(c) Joint air-noise pollution (dBA)/(µg/m³) with registered hypertension cases at EDK;
(d) Joint air- noise pollution (dBA)/(µg/m³) with registered hypertension cases at GHS;
(e) Joint air-noise pollution (Lden)/(µg/m³) with registered hypertension cases at GT.

The Figure 4:14a–e depicts a positive association between air concentration, noise level at different frequency components, and registered hypertension cases. Figure 4:14a–e shows this relationship moves in the same direction at all monitoring sites. From Figure 4:14a–e, there seems to be moderate clustering at all monitoring sites. Figure 4:14a–e also depicts a linear correlation at all monitoring areas, except for EDB in Figure 4:14a. As shown in Figure 4:14b–

e, there are outliers at all monitoring sites. Figure 4:14a–e shows some outliers also exhibit clustering features at all monitoring sites. The strength of the correlation is moderate because there is moderate clustering across all monitoring areas. This means the registered hypertension cases are not isolated cases but clustered ones. This suggests a unique collection of registered hypertension cases reported to GP practices that are clustered together in time and geography. This indicates that there is clustering on the map. Therefore, a moderate relationship exists between joint air concentration and noise level at the frequency component range and registered hypertension cases.

4.13 Multiple Regression Analysis of Joint Air Concentration and Noise Level at Frequency Component Range with Registered Hypertension Cases

Table 4:12: The regression coefficients of joint noise level at low-, mid-, and high-frequency components and air concentrations of NO₂, PM₁₀, and PM_{2.5} (µg/m³) showing impact on registered hypertension cases

Variables	B	SE	t	Sig.	95.0% CI
Constant	151.41	79.09	1.91	0.057	(-4.40,307.22)
NO ₂	5.12	1.50	3.41	<0.001	(2.16,8.08)
PM ₁₀	-28.86	8.88	-3.25	0.001	(-46.35,-11.37)
PM _{2.5}	33.98	13.32	2.55	0.011	(7.75,60.21)
LOW	-2.28	1.53	-1.49	0.137	(-5.29,0.73)
MID	11.32	2.95	3.83	<0.001	(5.50,17.14)
HIGH	-10.82	3.01	-3.59	<0.001	(-16.75, -4.88)

Note: CI = Confidence Interval.

Table 4:12 shows the impact of noise level at low-, mid-, and high-frequency components and air concentrations of NO₂, PM₁₀, and PM_{2.5} µg/m³ on registered hypertension cases. The R² value of 0.14 reveals that the predictors explain 14% of the variance in the outcome variable, with F (1, 238) = 11.63, 10.57, 6.51, 14.70, and 12.89 and $p < 0.001, 0.001, 0.011, <0.001,$ and $<0.001,$ respectively. The findings reveal that NO₂, PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, mid-, and high-frequency component positively and negatively predict registered hypertension cases ($\beta = 0.24, -0.40,$

0.30, 0.75, and -0.72 and $p < 0.001$, 0.001 , 0.011 , <0.001 , and <0.001 , respectively). However, noise level at the low-frequency component has a non-significant effect on registered hypertension cases ($\beta = -0.17 > 0.05$). NO_2 is likely to increase the risk of hypertension.

Q-Q Plot

Residuals Plots

Figure 4:15: Linear regression of noise level at low, mid and high frequency component and air concentration of NO_2 , PM_{10} and $\text{PM}_{2.5}$ $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ on hypertension register

Table 4:13: The regression coefficients of joint noise level at low-, mid-, and high-frequency components and air concentrations of NO₂, PM₁₀, and PM_{2.5} µg/m³ showing impact on hypertension rate.

Variables	B	SE	t	Sig.	95.0% CI
(Constant)	145.615	62.434	2.332	.021	(22.46,268.77)
PM _{2.5}	-22.159	10.934	-2.027	.044	(-43.73, -.59)
HIGH	6.996	2.539	2.755	.006	(1.99, 12.01)
NO ₂	-2.000	1.237	-1.617	.107	(-4.44, .44)
PM ₁₀	17.470	7.304	2.392	.018	(3.06, 31.88)
LOW	1.655	1.233	1.343	.181	(-.78, 4.09)
MID	-7.225	2.405	-3.004	.003	(-11.97, -2.48)

Note: CI = Confidence Interval

Table 4:13 shows the impact of noise level at low-, mid-, and high-frequency components and air concentrations of NO₂, PM₁₀, and PM_{2.5} (µg/m³) on the hypertension rate. The R² value of 0.09 reveals that the predictors explain 9% of the variance in the outcome variable, with $F(6, 190) = 3.17, p < 0.05$. The findings reveal that PM_{2.5} and noise at the mid-frequency component negatively predict the hypertension rate, with ($\beta = -0.29, p < 0.05$) and ($\beta = -0.66, p < 0.05$). The findings also reveal that noise at the high-frequency component and PM₁₀ positively predict the hypertension rate, with ($\beta = 0.61, p < 0.05$) and ($\beta = -0.37, p < 0.05$). In contrast, noise level at the low-frequency component and NO₂ have a non-significant effect on the hypertension rate ($\beta = -0.17 > 0.05$).

Table 4:14: Correlation Matrix of noise level at low, mid and high frequency component and air concentration of NO₂, PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} µg/m³

Variable	Zero-order	Partial	Part
PM _{2.5}	-0.007	-0.145	-0.140
HIGH	0.110	0.196	0.191
NO ₂	-0.049	-0.117	-0.112
PM ₁₀	0.053	0.171	0.165
LOW	0.129	0.097	0.093
MID	0.041	-0.213	-0.208

Table 4:14 shows the correlation between PM_{2.5} and hypertension rate are -0.007. The correlation between noise level at high frequency component and hypertension rate is 0.110. The correlation between NO₂ and hypertension rate is -0.049. The correlation between PM₁₀ and hypertension rate is 0.053. The correlation between noise level at low frequency component and hypertension rate is 0.129. The correlation between noise level at mid frequency component and hypertension rate is 0.041. Each of these correlations is a zero-order correlation. Because we are not accounting for the potential impact of a third variable, this would be regarded as the zero-order correlation between the two variables. However, in practise, additional variables might have an impact on how these two variables relate to one another.

It was discovered that the partial correlation between PM_{2.5} and hypertension rate is -0.145. When we assessed the correlation between PM_{2.5} and hypertension rate after adjusting for the impact of NO₂, PM₁₀, noise level at high and low frequency component (Table 4:14).

This indicates that even after adjusting for the impact of the population's present age in the areas, there is still negative association between the air concentration of PM_{2.5} studied, and the hypertension rate result obtained. The correlation between noise level at high frequency component and hypertension rate is -0.145 showing negative association. The correlation between NO₂ and hypertension rate is -0.117. The correlation between PM₁₀ and hypertension rate is 0.171 showing a positive association. The correlation between noise level at low frequency component and hypertension rate is 0.097. The correlation between noise level at mid frequency component and hypertension rate is -0.213. Each of these correlations is a partial correlation.

The desired result is -0.140, which accounts for the effects of NO₂, PM₁₀, noise levels at both high and low frequencies, and the part connection between PM_{2.5} and hypertension. We can infer from the t-test that the correlation is meaningful. It's intriguing that while the simple correlation is similarly negative ($r = -0.007$), this part correlation is negative. Therefore, there is a negative correlation between PM_{2.5} and hypertension rate, but this correlation only applies

to the portion of PM_{2.5} that is unrelated to NO₂, PM₁₀, or noise levels at high and low frequencies. This indicates that higher rates of hypertension are associated with pollution that has lower levels of NO₂, PM₁₀, and noise at both high and low frequencies.

Figure 4:16: A 3D scatterplot showing the correlation between air concentration and noise level at different frequency components and hypertension rate.

The 3D scatterplot shows the impact of joint air concentration and noise at different frequency components (low-, mid-, and high-frequency components) on pollution and the hypertension rate identified in the areas. Noise level at different frequency component results in hypertension. However, pollution from road traffic noise at different frequencies combined with air concentration also increases the hypertension rate.

Figure 4:16A shows a positive relationship between joint NO₂ and mid-frequency component and hypertension rate. The correlation strength is strong across all the scatterplots, except for

the joint noise level at the low-frequency component and NO₂, which has a weak correlation with the hypertension rate. The standard noise level at the mid-frequency component and NO₂ increase when the hypertension rate also increases. These findings mean that when joint NO₂ and mid-frequency component rises for a year, the rate of hypertension will also increase. These findings show that an annual increase in daily pollution from joint NO₂ and mid-frequency components from road traffic will cause the hypertension rate to increase annually.

Figure 4:16B shows a general positive linear correlation between joint noise level at the high-frequency component and PM₁₀ with hypertension. Across all the scatterplots, there seems to be a strong relationship between joint noise level at the high-frequency component and PM₁₀ and hypertension rate. These findings mean that the standard noise level at the high-frequency component and PM₁₀ increase when the hypertension rate increases.

Figure 4:16C depicts a general negative linear correlation of joint noise level at the mid-frequency component and PM_{2.5} with hypertension rate. These findings connote that the hypertension rate also decreases when the communal noise level at the mid-frequency component and PM_{2.5} decrease. Therefore, a strong association between PM_{2.5} and noise level at the mid-frequency predicts the outcome of hypertension rate.

4.14 Proximity Measure for Attributes between Vectors of Values

Table 4:15 below shows that the correlation between distance using the proximity measure and nearest neighbours shows clustering, illustrating a correlation between the vector values and similarities. There is a similarity matrix between noise level at different frequency components, air concentration, and hypertension rate. This means a stronger correlation between noise level at different frequency components, air pollutant and hypertension rate. Therefore, a strong association between PM_{2.5} and noise level at the mid-frequency, combined with noise level at the high-frequency component and PM₁₀, predicts the outcome of hypertension rate. The similarities across all the scatterplots show that the data groups are very close, indicating a correlation between the vector values across all the scatterplots.

Table 4:15: Distance Correlation of vectors of values of joint noise level at different frequency component and air concentration and hypertension rate using proximity matrix

SECTION A			
	NO ₂	LOW	Hypertension Rate
NO ₂	1.000	-0.131	0.122
LOW	-0.131	1.000	0.012
Hypertension Rate	0.122	0.012	1.000

	NO ₂	Hypertension Rate	MID
NO ₂	1.000	0.122	-0.082
Hypertension Rate	0.122	1.000	-0.016
MID	-0.082	-0.016	1.000

	NO ₂	Hypertension Rate	HIGH
NO ₂	1.000	0.122	-0.107
Hypertension Rate	0.122	1.000	0.033
HIGH	-0.107	0.033	1.000

¹ Similarity matrix

SECTION B			
	Hypertension Rate	PM ₁₀	LOW
Hypertension Rate	1.000	0.053	0.129
PM ₁₀	0.053	1.000	0.014
LOW	0.129	0.014	1.000

	Hypertension Rate	PM ₁₀	MID
Hypertension Rate	1.000	0.053	0.041
PM ₁₀	0.053	1.000	0.023
MID	0.041	0.023	1.000

	Hypertension Rate	PM ₁₀	HIGH
Hypertension Rate	1.000	0.053	0.110
PM ₁₀	0.053	1.000	0.001
HIGH	0.110	0.001	1.000

¹ Similarity matrix

SECTION C			
	Hypertension Rate	PM _{2.5}	LOW
Hypertension Rate	1.000	-0.007	.129
PM _{2.5}	-0.007	1.000	.118
LOW	0.129	0.118	1.000

	Hypertension Rate	PM _{2.5}	MID
Hypertension Rate	1.000	-0.007	0.041
PM _{2.5}	-0.007	1.000	0.159
MID	0.041	0.159	1.000

	Hypertension Rate	PM _{2.5}	HIGH
Hypertension Rate	1.000	-0.007	0.110
PM _{2.5}	-0.007	1.000	0.133
HIGH	0.110	0.133	1.000

¹ Similarity matrix.

4.15 Canonical correlation between noise at different frequency component and air concentration with hypertension register and hypertension rate

The canonical correlation analysis explored the correlation between combined noise at different frequency components and air concentration and combined registered hypertension cases and hypertension rate.

Table 4:16: Canonical correlation and Eigen values

	Correlation	Eigenvalue	Wilks Statistic	F	Num D.F	Denom D.F.	Sig.
1	0.342	0.132	0.869	2.160	12.000	356.000	.013
2	0.127	0.016	0.984	0.590	5.000	179.000	0.707

Table 4:17: Variance and Eigen values

	Eigen Value	Variance %
1	0.132	89
2	0.016	11
Total	0.148	100

Figure 4:17 and Table 4:16 shows that the canonical correlation is 0.342. Figure 4:17 shows the independent canonical variables, the canonical loading of NO₂, PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, low-, mid-, and high-frequency component is 0.206, -0.221, 0.003, -0.400, -0.154, and -0.363, respectively. The total variance of the six independent variables is 6%. The canonical loading of registered hypertension cases and hypertension rate is -0.129 and -0.938, respectively. The total variance of the two dependent variables is 45%. These findings mean that when PM₁₀ and noise at the low-, mid-, and high-frequency components decrease, the registered hypertension cases and hypertension rate will also reduce. In addition, as NO₂ and PM_{2.5} increase, the

registered hypertension registered cases and hypertension rate will also increase. This is because the NO₂ and PM_{2.5} canonical loading (0.206 and 0.003) have positive correlation.

Figure 4:17: Canonical correlation between joint noise at different frequency components combined with air concentration, registered hypertension cases, and hypertension rate.

From Figure 4:17 and Table 4:17 the variance explained by the canonical independent variable at a canonical correlation of 0.342 is 89%. Therefore, the correlation is significant at $p < 0.05$. This indicates significant correlations between joint air pollutant and noise at different frequency components, registered hypertension cases, and hypertension rate.

4.16 Multivariate analysis of factors influencing the hypertension among the respondents

This section presents results of a multinomial logistic regression to assess the influence of gender, age, body mass index, smoking habit and physical activity on hypertension.

Table 4:18: Model Fitting Information

Model	Model Fitting Criteria		Likelihood Ratio Tests	
	-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Intercept Only	2208.157			
Final	599.178	1608.979	1128	0.000

Table 4:19 : Likelihood Ratio Tests

Effect	Model Fitting Criteria		Likelihood Ratio Tests	
	-2 Log Likelihood of Reduced Model	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Intercept	599.178 ^a	.000	0	.
Gender	608.732 ^b	9.555	1	0.002
ag16g3	659.816 ^b	60.638	2	0.000
bmi_sr	1918.741	1319.563	1117	0.000
SmokEver	599.179 ^b	.002	1	0.969
Lst7Vig	622.060 ^b	22.882	7	0.002

*5% significance level

From Table 4:18 above it was observed that, the model was statistically significant since we had a smaller p-value of 0.000. This implies that, the variables significantly improved the model by predicting the dependent variable better than the intercept alone.

Table 4:19 above also shows that, smoking habit of respondents was not statistically significant because $p = 0.969$. On the other hand, gender, age, body mass index and physical activity was statistically significant because their p-values were lesser than significance level of 5%. That is, hypertension is being influenced by gender, age, body mass index and physical activity.

This section presents results of a multinomial logistic regression to assess the influence of air pollution and noise at different component of frequencies gender, age, smoking habit and on hypertension.

Table 4:20: Model Fitting Information

Model	Model Fitting Criteria		Likelihood Ratio Tests	
	-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Intercept Only	283.601			
Final	167.373	116.228	72	0.001

Table 4:21: Likelihood Ratio Tests

Effect	Model Fitting Criteria		Likelihood Ratio Tests	
	-2 Log Likelihood of Reduced Model	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Intercept	167.373 ^a	.000	0	.
NO ₂	167.423	.050	1	0.823
PM ₁₀	167.546	.173	1	0.677
PM _{2.5}	168.894	1.522	1	0.217
Lowfreq	167.752	.379	1	0.538
Midfreq	169.661	2.289	1	0.130
Highfreq	171.732	4.359	1	0.037
Gender	174.550	7.177	1	0.007
age90	264.439	97.066	63	0.004
SmokeStat	174.008	6.635	2	0.036

*5% significance level

From Table 4:20 above, it was observed that, the model was statistically significant since we had a smaller p-value of 0.001. This implies that, the variables significantly improved the model by predicting the dependent variable better than the intercept alone.

Table 4:21 also shows that, NO₂, PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, Low and mid noise frequency component of respondents was not statistically significant because $p = 0.823, 0.677, 0.217, 0.538$ and 0.130 respectively. On the other hand, high noise frequency component, gender, age, and smoking status was statistically significant because their p-values were lesser than significance level of

5%. That is, hypertension is being influenced by high noise frequency component, gender, age, and smoking status.

Table 4:22: Model Fitting Information

Model	Model Fitting Criteria		Likelihood Ratio Tests	
	-2 Log Likelihood	Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Intercept Only	10.364			
Final	0.000	10.364	6	0.110

Table 4:23: Likelihood Ratio Tests

Effect	Model Fitting Criteria		Likelihood Ratio Tests		
	-2 Log Likelihood of Reduced Model		Chi-Square	df	Sig.
Intercept	11.277		11.277	1	0.001
Lowfreq	0.000 ^a		0.000	1	1.000
Midfreq	0.000 ^a		0.000	1	1.000
Highfreq	0.000 ^a		0.000	1	1.000
NO ₂	7.579		7.579	1	0.006
PM ₁₀	7.933		7.933	1	0.005
PM _{2.5}	0.000 ^a		0.000	1	0.999

*5% significance level

From Table 4:22, it was observed that, the model was not statistically significant since we had a smaller p-value of 0.110. This implies that, the variables did not significantly improve the model by predicting the dependent variable better than the intercept alone.

Table 4:23 also shows that PM_{2.5}, Low, Mid and High noise frequency component of respondents was not statistically significant because $p = 0.999, 1.000, 1.000, 1.000$ and 1.000 respectively. On the other hand, NO₂ and PM₁₀ concentration was statistically significant because their p-values were lesser than significance level of 5%. That is, hypertension is being influenced by NO₂ and PM₁₀.

This section presents results of a logistic regression to assess the extent of influence, gender, age, body mass index and smoker status.

Table 4:24: A logistics regression of influence of gender, age, body mass index and smoker status on hypertension

Co-variates	Odd ratio (95% CI)	p-value
Gender		
Male/female	0.638 (0.513,0.793)	0.000
Age		
16-44		0.000
45-64	12.322 (8.144, 18.644)	0.000
Age 65+	2.422 (1.914, 3.064)	0.000
body mass index		
	0.906 (0.888,0.925)	0.000
Smoking status		
Current smoker		0.35
Ex-smoker (1)	0.752 (0.496, 1.141)	0.180
Never smoked (2)	1.022 (0.812, 1.287)	0.850
<hr/>		
N	1835	
Log likelihood	1948.194	
Prob>chi2.	0.000	

Main outcome = Hypertension

The regression model gave a log likelihood ratio (LR) statistic which is significant at one percent. This implies that the variables jointly influence hypertension among respondents. As shown in Table 4:24. There was a positive association between age of respondents and hypertension increased with increasing age. This implies that, the likelihood of having a hypertension increased with increasing age of respondents. Respondents who were in the 45–64year group were 12.3 times more likely to have hypertension and this relationship was statistically significant (OR=12.3; p=0.000), with all variables remaining constant. Respondents who were 65 years and above were also significantly 2.4 times more likely to have hypertension (OR=2.4; p=0.000), with all other variables remaining constant.

Gender at community household also showed strong positive relationship with the hypertension among respondents. As shown in Table 4:24, the extent of influence of gender on hypertension increased with increasing age of respondents.

Respondents who were male/female were 0.6 times more likely to have hypertension (OR=2.5; p=0.000), holding all variables constant. The body mass index showed strong positive relationship with hypertension among respondents. This indicates that as the body mass index increased the likelihood of hypertension. Respondents with body mass index were 0.9 times more likely to have hypertension holding all variables constant (OR=0.9; p=0.000).

4.17 Relationship between Years of Noise and Air pollution Exposure and Hypertension

Figure 4:18: Influence of years of noise and air pollution exposure on hypertension

Figure 4:18 above depicts the difference in hypertension with respect to the years of noise and air pollution exposure. The minimum and maximum length of noise exposure was 1 year and 14 years respectively. Among 960 respondents who were exposed to noise and air pollution for less than 5 years, 50% had hypertension. 43.33% had hypertension for respondents who were exposed to noise 5-10 years. For respondents who were exposed to noise for 11-15 years 75% had hypertension. This clearly shows a high tendency of having a hypertension when you are being exposed to noise and air pollution for longer years.

Chapter 5

DISCUSSION

5.1 Background characteristics of respondents

The prevalence of hypertension from SHeS survey in urban communities in Glasgow among household persons are being reported in this study. Majority of the households' persons interviewed in SHeS survey were females 57.6% than males 42.4%. The higher number of females to male is contrary to studies done among community households' persons in some developed countries where more males participated than females (Molenaar et al., 2007; Zhou et al., 2019 and Tormo et al., 2000). The Scottish Health Board mid-year population estimates in Scotland for private households was 32% of women and 29% of males for 2019. This could therefore be assumed as the most probable reason for the higher population of women in the study. Majority of ages of the SHeS respondents were between 45 and 65 years and 40.1% were 65 years or above. This age group of household persons constituted the mode of the age distribution because they were observed to be the age group from the Scottish Health Board mid-year population estimates in Scotland for private households who were 60 or older, which was a higher percentage of older women than older men. This could be the reason why majority of the respondents (44.6%) are retired from work.

In this study, the prevalence of hypertension was 98.7 % for (Doctor diagnosed high BP). According to a previous study carried out in the same Scotland regions 13.9% of people in Scotland had high blood pressure between 2015–2016 (ScotPHO, 2016). Similarly, data from a health survey estimating the prevalence of hypertension around areas in England revealed that about 11.8 million adults had hypertension, equating to 22.6% of the population (Scholes et al., 2020). Even though the data was self-reported, prevalence of hypertension from SHeS survey accurately reflects the severity of the condition.

According to SHeS survey, it was found that the history of no condition present (hypertension) was significantly higher among the households' persons as compared to respondent that reported hypertension condition was present (97.9 % versus 2.1 %; $p < 0.001$). In the case of those doctor diagnosed high BP was high, prevalence is rising, which is not similar with data from previous SHeS survey (ScotPHO, 2016) in Glasgow urban areas.

The women pregnant when told had high BP, doctor diagnosed hypertension (excluding pregnant) and ever had high BP (excludes only had high BP during pregnancy) respectively were significantly lower. However, those reported to have high BP other than when pregnant was high. Previous studies agree with this finding. A cohort study by Montes-González et al. (2018), shows an association of traffic-related air and noise pollution with maternal blood pressure and hypertensive disorders of pregnancy. They believe this may increase the risk for cardiovascular disorders, especially among susceptible populations like pregnant women when exposed to traffic-related air and noise pollution.

On the otherhand, this study findings shows that households' persons who self-reported hypertension from the SHeS survey were exposed to air pollutant and noise at different component of frequencies beyond tolerable levels, and were more likely to have hypertension. According to earlier research, women who maintain normal blood pressure during pregnancy may have a lower risk of developing hypertension than women with no live birth (Wilson et al., 2003) and a lower incidence of hypertension later in life, which is unrelated to pregnancy (Wilson et al., 2003). Overall, our findings support this hypothesis.

There was a positive association between exposure to noise at different frequency and air pollutant ($PM_{2.5}$) with the incidence of self-reported hypertension.

Similarly, according to a study done by Fuks et al. (2017), they investigated whether traffic-related air pollution and noise are associated with incident hypertension in

European cohorts. They assessed self-reported hypertension. Incidence of self-reported hypertension was positively associated with PM_{2.5}. Road traffic noise was weakly positively associated with the incidence of self-reported hypertension.

5.2 Suitable conceptual framework as well as the application of the conceptual framework for an Environmental Health Tracking System that link road traffic noise and air pollution with hypertension

This work has demonstrated that a conceptual framework model can be used to review the joint cause-effect relationship of environmental noise and air quality monitoring link to public health in the UK. This work findings suggests that indicators such as Driving force, Pressure, State, Exposure, Effect and Action (DPSEEA) may be suitable for building a conceptual framework model to review public health assessment and integrating related factors. The review summarizes the process of the implementation of indicator system based on internationally agreed legislation, methodology and comparable data.

Our finding shows that DPSEEA can be applied to develop understanding of links between air quality, environmental noise and health outcomes. Application of DPSEEA is ideal to develop a conceptual framework for UK environmental health tracking system and suitable conceptual framework component that fits the model UK Environmental health tracking system. Previous work from WHO have recommended components of conceptual framework linking environment and health (WHO, 2010). This work compared to previous studies shows that Pressure-State-Response (PSR), Driving Force-Pressure-State-Impact-Response (DPSIR), and Driving Force- State- Response DSR, are the three frameworks that are primarily concerned with the environment and were created to create environmental indicators (Niemeijer et al., 2008; Eriksson et al., 2017). Comparative study between DPSEEA and DPSIR framework, shows that DPSIR is the only one of these that considers how the environment may affect people's health, however this is not its main objective. These frameworks do not go into detail about the exposure pathway (the connections between cause and effect), and only the DPSIR framework does so by adding elements for driving force and pressure. Also, previous studies show that the PSR and DSR frameworks

are unable to recognise numerous entry points for activities because of the incomplete definition of the exposure path (the connections between cause and effect), and only the DPSIR framework does so by adding elements for driving force and pressure (Hambling et al., 2011). The PSR and DSR frameworks are unable to recognise numerous entry points for activities because of the incomplete definition of the exposure path (Edokpolo et al., 2019; Frank et al., 2019; Harwell et al., 2019). These frameworks' propensity to emphasise the connection between human activity and other factors is another criticism and the environment in a straight line. The PSR, DSR, and DPSIR frameworks are seen to be inappropriate for articulating the links between the environment and health in detail because of these shortcomings (Hambling et al., 2011) compared to DPSEEA. The MEME paradigm also acknowledges contextual elements and their impact on exposures and health consequences (such as social environment, economic development, and demographics) (Regoniel et al., 2015). Previous studies have proved that the MEME and DPSEEA frameworks are similar, making it reasonably easy to transition between them as needed. The DPSEEA and MEME frameworks and the Environmental public health indicators (EPHI) framework both make use of the idea of the environmental health chain (Eisenberg et al., 2007; McGeehin et al., 2004; Kyle et al., 2006).

5.3 Annual average residential exposure to air pollutant ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) and noise at different frequency components (low, mid and high) (Lden) and its association Using QGIS

The noise measurements at locations in Greater Glasgow suggest that communal noise levels are high. Both noise and air pollution showed different spatial patterns, and correlations across monitoring areas varied substantially depending on the unit of analysis: Greater Glasgow, neighbourhoods, and $1 \text{ km} \times 1 \text{ km}$ grid cells. Auto spatial correlations across all monitoring areas in Greater Glasgow were moderately strong.

A similar study illustrated how to use a spatial unit and local characteristics to analyse the relationship between air pollution and road traffic noise in London between 2003 and 2010 (Chang et al., 2019) but slightly different findings.

This work findings shows that the maximum and annual average noise level in a number of buildings in GK and GHS, EDB is more than 80 dB(A). The annual average NO₂, PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} concentrations regarding air pollution levels at all five monitoring areas were between 0–35, 0–50, and 0–200 (µg/m³), respectively. This form of simulation is not always appropriate because it implies that all building residents are subjected to the same maximum levels of traffic noise and air pollution, which is not always the case. According to actionable recommendations and health advice on the low band, it recommended individuals in that area can enjoy their usual outdoor activities with low risk.

Even though the air pollution level was low, some exceeded recommended level (WHO, 2021 and Gray et al., 2017). Annual average PM_{2.5} concentrations should not exceed 5 g/m³, and 24-h average exposures should not exceed 15 g/m³ more than 3–4 days per year, according to the new guidelines.

Interim targets have been established to aid in planning incremental milestones towards cleaner air, particularly for cities, regions, and countries with significant levels of air pollution. In the case of PM_{2.5}, they are an annual mean of 35 g/m³, a 24-h standard of 75 g/m³, a yearly mean of 25 g/m³, a 24-h mean of 50 g/m³, an annual mean of 15 g/m³, 24-h mean of 37.5 g/m³ and yearly mean of 10 g/m³, 24-h mean of 25 g/m³.

The PM₁₀ concentrations 15 g/m³ every year and 45 g/m³ on a 24-h basis. NO₂ concentrations of 10 g/m³ every year and 25 g/m³ on a 24-h basis.

When considering the current policy and air quality index, WHO and EU air quality standards were appropriate (Gray et al., 2017).

From our findings, residents at several locations may subject to excessive noise and air pollution. Prolonged exposure may have long-term and short-term health repercussions such as physiological stress responses. Most temporary and short-lived symptoms include hypertension, digestive and immune system illnesses, impaired concentration and memory, and a restricted visual field. They can also become chronic (insomnia,

high blood pressure, anxiety, depression). Therefore, it was necessary to look at the risk of hypertension.

This work demonstrates the joint association of air concentration and frequency components of road traffic noise. According to the findings, those who live in areas with heavy traffic noise at (mid and high frequencies of 250, 500, 1000, 2000, 4000, and 8000 Hz) and high concentrations of PM₁₀ µg/m³ are much more likely to develop hypertension.

The results at 63 and 125 Hz are consistent with the idea that exposure to low-frequency (10–200 Hz) traffic noise may cause hypertension by irritating cortical or subcortical areas via the neuroendocrine system (Chang et al., 2019).

Additionally, there was a strong correlation between exposure to low-frequency noise and Car and taxi, light goods vehicles traffic. There was a strong correlation between exposure to mid-frequency noise and light goods vehicle traffic. Additionally, there was a strong correlation between air pollutant exposure to PM₁₀ and bus traffic. Motorcycles were the main cause of traffic noise and air pollutants in Greater Glasgow because they had the highest correlation coefficients, with noise levels at 63 Hz, 125 Hz, 1000 Hz, 2000 Hz, 4000 Hz, and 8000 Hz.

Due to their notable hearing sensitivity at roughly 1000 Hz, people with normal hearing may be one explanation for the greater risk seen at this frequency (Helzner et al., 2011).

Another possibility is that isolated auditory brainstem responses to noise exposure of more than 30 dB at 1000 Hz were found to be 100% in young adult research (Grose et al., 2017). However, evidence of a significant correlation was found at PM₁₀ and NO₂.

The strong association between noise exposure and total traffic flow rate, is not unexpected. The total traffic flow rate was significant (all *p*-values 0.050) although strongly correlated (rho ranged from 0.900 to 1.000) with mostly high and low-frequency components of traffic noise.

This may lead to hypertension by irritating cortical or subcortical areas via the neuroendocrine system. Hypertension may be influenced by combined (mid noise frequency component and PM_{2.5}), (PM₁₀ and NO₂), (PM_{2.5} and NO₂), (PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀), (mid and low noise frequency component), (high and low noise frequency component) and (high and mid noise frequency component) respectively.

A similar study has been conducted in Taichung, Taiwan (Davies et al., 2009). Results showed that the annual average LAeq, 24 h in Taichung was 66.4 ± 4.7 dBA.

This study finding shows annual average LAeq, 24 h in five monitoring urban area in Glasgow was 18.9 dB(A) ± 83.6dB(A). This study findings reveals that noise levels have a significant effect between different frequency component (all *p*-values < 0.001) at all the five monitoring sites with highest at low frequency component being 83.6 ± 27.1 dB(A) at 125 Hz. In contrast, according to Davies et al. significant differences in LAeq, 24 h, and frequency components were observed between land-use types (all *p*-values < 0.001), but with the highest frequency component being 61.4 ± 5.3 dBA at 1000 Hz.

This study total traffic flow rate was significant (all *p*-values 0.050) although strongly correlated (rho ranged from 0.900 to 1.000) with most high and low-frequency traffic noise components. Like (Davies et al., 2009), noise levels at 125 Hz had the highest correlation with total traffic (Spearman's coefficient = 0.795) and the highest prediction in the multiple linear regression (R² = 0.803; adjusted R² = 0.765).

Like (Davies et al., 2009), this study reported noise levels higher than the permissible levels of 65 dB.

It is limiting to combine the effects of noise exposure with air pollution exposure in this study because of the substantial correlation.

Additionally, it was more effective to monitor various frequency components of road traffic noise and air pollution to demonstrate the relationship between combined exposures.

The noise measures only consider a person's immediate exposure to road traffic noise and extrapolates to their long-term exposure. A 1 h LAeq at the five sampling sites is likely to be a reliable indicator of long-term noise levels (Davies et al., 2009).

The use of ternary diagrams broadens our comprehension of the actual contribution of three apexes at average noise level at measured period and different frequency component, particularly road noise.

This study findings show that noise level at night time showed high levels than evening time. This finding support evidence that night noise increases levels of stress hormones and vascular oxidative stress, which may lead to arterial hypertension (Münzel et al., 2018). Noise may be high at night time due to the COVID 19 lock down because there was less traffic at evening than night time. People may want to stay indoor during the day and move out during the night when the number of people outdoor have decrease (Paital, 2020). Noise at different frequency component (low, mid and high) are influenced by road traffic flow and noise level can be changed by road traffic peak hours (Mak et al., 2021). Additionally, Road traffic peak hours impacts the low, mid and high frequency component of noise and exposure factors (Mak et al., 2021), including the catalysis of noise during daytime, (Chang et al., 2019), and operates as an environmental co-exposure for air pollution. Low and high noise frequency level have been found to be positively correlated. Since Low noise level (31.5Hz-125KHz) mix with high noise level (2KHz-16Hz), this correlation suggests most low and high-frequency traffic noise components have relationship with total traffic flow. This finding is like previous study (Davies et al., 2009), where noise levels at 125 Hz had the highest correlation with total traffic (Spearman's coefficient = 0.795). Low and high-frequency traffic noise components may serve as sensitive indicators of hypertension-related issues reported (Wang et al.,2016) and the results at 63 and 125 Hz are consistent with the idea that exposure to low-frequency (10–200 Hz) traffic noise

may cause hypertension by irritating cortical or subcortical areas via the neuroendocrine system (Chang et al., 2019). Exposure to low-frequency noise from 10 to 200 Hz has been recognized as an environmental pollutant that is associated with annoyance in previous studies (Chang et al., 2012). Furthermore, there is a mixture of low-mid, low-high, mid-low, mid-high, high-low, high-mid, low-mid-high, high-mid-low, mid-low-high of noise frequency component at all the monitoring sites. The use of ternary diagrams makes it possible to rank and evaluate immediately observable differences. There are three main noise level at frequency components range for all five monitoring sites representing low (31.5Hz-125Hz), mid (250Hz-2KHz) and high (2KHz-16Hz). The frequency component indices allow one to not only assess the current state of a given process but also to pinpoint key variables that could be altered to enhance the environmental exposure of the traffic road noise. For instance, it is evident from the ternary diagram's that the percentages for low (31.5Hz-125Hz), (250Hz-2KHz), and (2KHz-16Hz) frequency component are the three variables that are plotted consequently. We can see any changes in the mixing of noise level at different frequency range for the resident by charting the three variables over time on a ternary diagram.

This study findings shows pattern of agglomerative clustering. The ternary plot and scatter plot exhibit characteristics of agglomerative clustering and balanced iterative reducing clustering feature. This clustering effect in this study is like previous studies that used ternary plot in their analysis (Kumarasamy et al., 2014, Podani et al., 2011, Baraer et al., 2015, Shilar et al., 2022). Both previous and current studies point out that the goal of cluster analysis is to group together variables that are near in proximity and belong to the same cluster, whereas items that are unlike one another belong to different clusters (Baraer et al., 2015, Shilar et al., 2022). This also involves constructing a tree structure from which cluster centroids are extracted.

This work finding shows noise level measured at day, night, evening, by positioning the point on the 3-way graph axis, each point on the graph reflects the percentage of noise level for each of the three measured periods. This depicts a three-dimensional relationship in two dimensions. This research found a positive correlation between day, night and evening noise levels. Similarly, previous research by Pierrette et al. (2012), the findings demonstrate the relationship between the period of noise levels measured. The results show a positive association between noise level measured during the day and evening or for longer lengths of time at night. In contrast, according to (Ross et al., 2011), the correlation of noise at mid-high frequency was generally stronger at night. Correlations with night-time high frequency noise were particularly high for car traffic (Spearman $r = 0.84$).

5.4 Noise and air pollution exposure and prevalence of hypertension in the communities.

In this study, it sought to determine the influence of noise and air pollution exposure on hypertension among community household persons and the prevalence of hypertension among community household persons.

Comparatively, the prevalence of hypertension among household persons at EDK was higher than most reported prevalence among community household persons in other settings. The control group respondent with hypertension condition was lower compared to the other groups. These differences in the hypertension among respondents from various private households' environment was not statistically significant ($\chi^2=4.36$, $p=0.50$). This supports results from previous epidemiological studies that compared the prevalence of the hypertension in different categories of communities (Montes-González et al., 2018, Fuks et al., 2017), Khan et al., 2020), Danciulescu et al., 2015). Conclusion drawn from results considering possible bias of exposure misclassification and a bias from using diagnosed hypertension suggested that exposure to road traffic noise at low and hearing-sensitive frequencies may be associated with hypertension and

exposure to noise at 125 Hz may have the greatest risk for hypertension. Results from this study indicate that all communities show different noise frequency component at different communities with the values measured at noise level ranging from 17.3dB at 31.5Hz to 247dB at 16Hz respectively. This reveals that all the road traffic used at the various communities produced sound that exceeded the minimum noise level of 55dB thereby having the potential of causing hypertension among household persons. These noise frequency levels measure among the community household persons also exceed the limit set by the Environmental Protection Act 1990, which permit community areas 70dB during day and 60dB noise at night. Also, noise frequency level exceeds the limiting value of 56dB as recommended by World Health Organization (WHO, 2018). These noise levels are however potentially hazardous and might result in hypertension among community households in that environment.

These study results are consistent with other studies from different countries. The study reported exposure to high levels of noise pollution at the community. A similar study has been conducted in Taichung, Taiwan (Wang et al., 2016). Results showed that the annual average LAeq,24h in Taichung was 66.4 ± 4.7 A-weighted decibels (dBA). Significant differences in LAeq,24h and frequency components were observed between land-use types (all p-values < 0.001), but not between seasons, with the highest two noise levels of 71.2 ± 1.0 dBA and 70.0 ± 2.6 dBA measured in stream-channel and areas, with the highest component being 61.4 ± 5.3 dBA at 1000 Hz. Road width, traffic flow rates, and land-use types were significantly associated with annual average LAeq,24h (all p-values < 0.050). Noise levels at 125 Hz had the highest correlation with total traffic (Spearman's coefficient = 0.795) and the highest prediction in the multiple linear regression ($R^2 = 0.803$; adjusted $R^2 = 0.765$). The study reported noise levels higher than permissible levels of 55dB. Furthermore, the findings reveal the spatial variation in road traffic noise exposure in Taichung. The highest correlation and predictive capacity were observed between this variation and noise levels at 125 Hz.

They recommend that governmental agencies should take actions to reduce noise levels from traffic vehicles (Wang et al., 2016).

The results further revealed exposure in some of the communities that may not see risk of hypertension per traffic flow of exposure but then the issue of variations in susceptibility to hypertension becomes a factor in such cases, such that even when a group of individuals are exposed to the same noise intensity. It will result in the development of significant hypertension in some and little or no hypertension at all in others as suggested by Chang et al. (2019) and Wang et al. (2016).

Group of scientists conducted a study in the metropolitan of Taichung, Taiwan on the temporal and spatial variations in road traffic noise for different frequency components (Wang et al., 2016).

According to them, road traffic noise exposure has been associated with health effects, but few studies report noise characteristics. Therefore, the impetus to assess 24-h noise levels and analyse their frequency components to investigate associations between seasons, meteorology, land-use types, and traffic. Information on land-use types, road parameters and traffic flow rates, was also collected for analysis with the annual averages of road traffic noise and its frequency components.

The study investigated the prevalence of HBP across all the frequencies (31.2 Hz to 16KHz). The prevalence rate ranged from 7.89% -11.5% from the low (31.2 Hz-125 Hz) to mid frequencies (250Hz-1KHz). This was indicative of low prevalence rate at these frequencies. At the high frequencies (1KHz-8KHz), the prevalence ranged between 17.11% - 25.33% (maximum at 4KHz) which was indicative of a sharp increase in prevalence rate at the high frequencies. The rise in prevalence of hypertension at high frequencies suggests that indeed noise from road traffic may be the probable cause of hypertension in the community's household persons since noise mostly affects the high frequencies. This trend is consistent with studies conducted by

Chang et al., 2019; Wang et al. (2016), where the highest prevalence of hypertension in household persons were mostly reported at 4KHz and 125Hz.

However, in assessing other self-reported cases of HBP in these household persons, ever had high BP, pregnant when told had high BP, high BP other than when pregnant, doctor diagnosed hypertension (excluding pregnant) and ever had high BP (excludes only had high BP during pregnancy) were observed among the household persons. In respect to this, high noise frequency was observed at 3KHz, 4KHz in this study with highest prevalence of the HBP occurring at 4KHz. Although various studies have proven that the classic frequency affected by high intensity noise is 4KHz, the notch may be noted elsewhere. This is because the frequency range of the noise influences hypertension. This may be the reason why other studies among community across Europe, UK, Asia, and America observed most hypertension at high noise frequency range (Chang et al., 2019, Wang et al., 2016, Ross et al., 2011, Liu et al., 2016).

The study's results were however like noise frequency obtained in the community population (Chang et al., 2019, Wang et al. (2016), Ross et al. (2011), Liu et al., 2016). This could imply that frequency range of community noise by household persons in this study were in close range of community noise hence the similar noise frequency range. High frequency and mid frequency were 20(6.6%) and 21(6.9%) respectively. High frequency noise with HBP may have been observed among participants because, with continued exposure noise frequency may eventually become indistinguishable from the changes of aging, where a gradual deterioration of HBP at the low frequencies is shown (Chang et al., 2019 and Ross et al., 2011).

There will be significant association between age and hypertension in household persons across frequencies.

5.5 Joint relationship between air pollutant and noise level at different frequency components on hypertension rate and registered cases using QGIS

This study aimed to investigate the joint relationship between air pollutant and noise level at different frequency components and hypertension rate and registered cases.

In this study, it first mapped the spatial patterns of the prevalence of hypertension (registered cases) as well as the average NO₂, PM₁₀, and PM_{2.5} pollutant and noise level at different frequency components on the urban Glasgow in five monitoring areas. To confirm the already-existing spatial autocorrelation of the three indicators, Moran's I was further calculated, which agreed with earlier research. Based on information from the most recent China Hypertension Survey, which comprised 451,755 participants, Pei et al. found the high incidence of hypertension in areas of eastern China, particularly the northeast (Lijun et al., 2020). In their analysis of the prevalence of hypertension among middle-aged and elderly people, Yin et al. found that there were significant regional variations in the prevalence of hypertension in China, with a relatively higher prevalence in Shanghai, Beijing, and Inner Mongolia and a relatively lower prevalence in Fujian (Yin et al., 2016).

The noise readings in Greater Glasgow show significant noise levels across the neighbourhoods monitored in this study. Practically every measuring point shows that the noise levels are higher than the values established for the designated study areas of research, which include the city centre; workshop, commercial, and administrative areas with housing; and zones along highways, main roads, and city traffic arteries; the road traffic noise levels are 65 dB(A) for day/evening/night. At the measuring point of the specified locations of GHS, EDK, and GK in the Lden (day-evening-night), the equivalent road traffic noise level reaches values of 86.8 dB(A) 83.4 dB(A) and 87 dB(A), respectively which was consistent with a previous study conducted by Davies et al. (2009), the study reported noise levels of 90 dB higher than the permissible levels. The WHO commissioned systematic review that was published in 2018 (Kempen et al., 2018) assessed the epidemiological evidence of a link between exposure to transport

noise and the risk of cardiovascular and metabolic disorder. The WHO report's main objective was to assess the consequences of daily exposure to Lden levels of transportation noise. Exposure to road traffic noise starting at 53dB(A) may have adverse effect on public health causing cardiovascular health related issues like hypertension (Kempen et al., 2018).

The study finding of road traffic noise level reaches values of 86.8 dB(A) 83.4 dB(A) and 87 dB(A) beyond the recommended limit of the new WHO guidelines.

Road traffic causes high noise levels that exceed the safe limits advised by the new WHO guidelines, the Environmental Protection (Act) of 1990, the Noise and Statutory Nuisance Act of 1993, and local noise regulating organisations.

The air quality index shows low for one, two, and three (band). At all five monitoring sites, the yearly average NO₂, PM₁₀, and PM_{2.5} pollutant for air pollution levels ranged from 0–35, 0–50, and 0–200 (µg/m³, respectively). Recommendations and health guidance for these low bands advise that people in those locations may engage in their typical outdoor activities without increased risk from air pollution (COMEAP, 2010) but this is not same case in terms of WHO guidelines and recommendation for air quality (WHO, 2021). Despite the low air pollution levels, some levels exceed the acceptable amount. The annual average PM_{2.5} concentrations should not exceed 5 g/m³, and the 24-hour average exposures should not exceed 15 g/m³ and more than 3–4 days per year, according to the new guidelines (WHO, 2021).

It is appropriate to use the WHO and EU air quality criteria while considering the present policy and air quality index (WHO, 2021 and COMEAP, 2011).

The spatial associations were studied between the modelled traffic-related noise, air pollution levels, and prevalence of hypertension. Both noise and air pollution showed different spatial patterns, and the correlations across the monitoring areas varied substantially, depending on the unit of analysis: Greater Glasgow, nearest

neighbourhoods, and 1 km × 1 km grid squares. They varied depending on the exposure metrics between NO₂, PM₁₀, and PM_{2.5}, and the noise level (Lden) at a Moran's I value of 0.413 is closest to one.

A related study with somewhat different results (Fecht et al., 2016) shows how to use a spatial unit and local features to analyse the association between air pollution and road traffic noise in London between 2003 and 2010. This is similar to this study findings because both study correlations varied depending on the spatial unit. According to (Fecht et al., 2016), they considered spatial unit of postcodes stratified by London Boroughs (~240,000 people), neighbourhoods and 1 km grid squares.

Comparably, this study finding shows that the auto spatial correlations between noise level (Lden) and NO₂, PM₁₀, PM_{2.5} across all monitoring areas in Greater Glasgow were slightly strong, but it was observed that across all London postcodes moderate correlations between model noise (LAeq,24 h, Lden, LAeq,16 h, Lnight) and air pollutant (NO₂, PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}) is stable over time (Spearman's rho range: 0.34-0.55).

Furthermore, this spatial analysis showed that air pollutant (NO₂, PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}) and noise level at different frequency components was strongly linked to a higher prevalence of hypertension registered cases.

This work findings reveal that mutual associations air pollutant (NO₂, PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}) and noise level at different frequency components with hypertension were positive and statistically significant, but this was different compared to the findings of Wolfgang et al. (2014). Mutually adjusted associations with hypertension were positive but no longer statistically significant (Wolfgang et al., 2014). Moreover, compared to previous studies which fail to investigate into traffic noise at different frequency for spatial mapping related to diseases.

In combined effect analyses, the largest incident risk was found in those who were exposed to the highest levels of both air pollution and road traffic noise, suggesting that

the effects of road traffic noise on incident primary hypertension may be enhanced in places where air pollution levels are high.

This study findings indicates that hypertension is being influenced significantly by NO₂, PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, and noise level at different frequency (Lden) at all monitoring locations. It means that hypertension increases with increasing pollution by NO₂, PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, and noise level at different frequency (Lden). This could be the reason for higher registered hypertension cases in those study locations.

Previous research has looked at the relationships between exposure to traffic noise and hypertension (Chang et al., 2019, Wang et al., 2016) but not the combined association between exposure to traffic noise at different frequency, air pollutant and hypertension.

It is currently unclear if exposures to each have additive or synergistic effects, or whether they might confuse one another, given that road transport causes both road traffic noise and air pollution (Münzel et al., 2017). In a few studies, the estimation of correlations with hypertension incorporated both exposures (De Kluizenaar et al., 2013, Ross et al., 2011, Montes-González et al., 2018) as well as some variation in the outcomes. Our findings indicated that when noise was analysed on a categorical scale, the significant connections discovered in the noise groups with the highest levels did not seem to be affected by air pollution. In addition, even accounting for air pollution, the relationships with continuous measurements of road traffic noise remained strong. In this study investigation, the effects of road traffic noise on the connections between air pollution (i.e., PM_{2.5}) and incident hypertension were related. This study's key discovery is that air pollution and road traffic noise may together influence the prevalence of primary hypertension. Subjects exposed to high levels of both traffic noise at (low or mid or high frequency component) and PM_{2.5} or PM₁₀ or NO₂ in the combined effects showed the highest relationships ($p < 0.05$).

It makes sense that prolonged exposure to air pollution makes the body more vulnerable to the harmful effects of noise from traffic, and the opposite is also true. There are a few possible pathways for the synergistic effects. Air pollution and noise from traffic are both thought to be hypertension causes (Stansfeld et al., 2015), and they share some similar mechanisms, such as activating the hypothalamus-pituitary-adrenal axis, peripheral vasoconstriction, systemic inflammation, and irritating cortical or subcortical areas via the neuroendocrine system, which may cause elevated blood pressure and eventually lead to hypertension (Chang et al., 2019, Münzel et al., 2017, Brook et al., 2009). The study findings show a positive association between joint PM_{2.5} and noise level at the mid-frequency component and hypertension rate. As the joint noise level at the mid-frequency component and PM_{2.5} increase, the hypertension rate also increases and moves in the same direction. The findings show a general positive linear correlation of joint noise level at the high-frequency component and PM₁₀ with hypertension rate. The findings also depict a general negative linear correlation of joint noise level at the mid-frequency component and PM_{2.5} with hypertension rate. There is a strong correlation across all the scatterplots. Furthermore, joint noise level at the low-frequency component, and NO₂ correlates with the hypertension rate. In contrast, after accounting for PM_{2.5} in previous study analysis, the association between road traffic noise and self-reported hypertension was reduced. According to Babisch et al. (2014), in the cross-sectional analysis of the KORA trial showed a slight reduction and loss of statistical significance for the connection between road traffic noise and hypertension upon adjustment for PM_{2.5}. This study findings compare to earlier studies, the air pollutants in the current study included not just PM_{2.5} but also NO₂, and PM₁₀ in addition to noise at mid, low and high frequency component. This research analysis also found a substantial correlation between the prevalence of hypertension, noise at high and low frequency component and PM_{2.5}, NO₂, and PM₁₀. The variations in the spatial

variability of the sources and components of air pollutants and traffic noise could be the cause of the findings in our investigation.

In contrast, a study was previously carried out (Coogan et al., 2017). A higher incidence of hypertension was linked to increased NO₂ levels in a large cohort of African American women. Although the incidence of hypertension decreased with higher NO₂ levels, higher NO₂ levels were not linked to increased rates of hypertension (Coogan et al., 2017). This research finding shows otherwise from this work.

Furthermore, the correlation of distance using the proximity measure and nearest neighbours shows clustering, illustrating a correlation between the vector values and similarities. The similarities across all the scatterplots show that the data groups are very close, indicating a correlation between the vector values across all the scatterplots. A conventional way to present statistical visualisation is the 3D scatterplot. It uses a cloud of points to represent the joint distribution of two variables, with each point denoting a dataset observation. From this representation, one may deduce a lot about whether there is a significant relationship between them.

The 3D scatter plot in this study shows the relationship between joint air pollutant and noise at different frequency components and the hypertension rate identified in the areas. The noise levels at different frequency components result in hypertension. However, pollution from road traffic noise at different frequency combined with air pollutant also increases hypertension rate.

A scatter matrix is made up of numerous pairwise scatterplots displayed as a matrix. The matrix reveals a positive correlation between joint air pollutant and noise level at different frequency components and hypertension variables. It assists us in estimating whether there is a correlation between various factors. It allows us to plot a selected scope over two metrics with their corresponding aggregation.

Scatterplots can only show two factors, although data are frequently clustered using numerous variables. Multiple ways have been considered to visualise more than three variables, but each has drawbacks.

The size of the markers is used to create a bubble chart, but that is not the best option. Since the variables would have different encodings, the third variable could not be compared with the others. For instance, noise level or air pollutant has a higher or no effect by glancing at the chart previously created. In this study, hypertension rate or registered hypertension cases as a third variable were included and compared to the other two.

In addition to encoding the third variable, 3D charts can be confusing and occasionally even deceptive. Nevertheless, 3D scatterplots can be helpful, particularly if they are dynamic. Current technologies can fully support the analysis and visualisation of differential expressions. Furthermore, 3D plots are typically non-static and permit interaction to comprehend the many components of the data using different parameters, which increases the effectiveness of data exploration. Therefore, a multivariate scatter matrix analysis was used to examine if one significant cluster was visible. Here, there was a lot of clustering effect on all the monitoring sites, except for the EDB monitoring site, showing that the hypertension rate is dispersed and not clustered cases.

This work is the first to explore an association of joint air pollutant and frequency components of road traffic noise with the prevalence and rate of hypertension. The findings revealed that $PM_{2.5}$ and noise at the mid-frequency component negatively predicted hypertension rate. In addition, noise at the high-frequency component and PM_{10} positively predicted registered hypertension cases. In contrast to measured hypertension, self-reported hypertension cases vary less and will lead to fewer false positive cases. This can potentially explain the positive effects for self-reported hypertension as well as measured hypertension cases which causes some of the

inconsistencies between prior studies, some of which have reported positive associations of air pollution and traffic noise with hypertension (Fecht et al., 2016; De Kluizenaar et al., 2013), while others found null effects (Fuk et al., 2011, Babisch et al., 2014, Sørensen et al., 2012). The effects of PM_{2.5} air pollution on incident hypertension remained stable after adjustment for road traffic noise. These findings are similar to current studies on the association between traffic noise and hypertension have rarely considered air pollution as a covariate in their analyses, in which adjustment for road traffic noise did not affect the cross-sectional associations between air pollution and hypertension (Huang et al., 2023). Furthermore, previous study show traffic noise and PM_{2.5} were both associated with a higher prevalence of hypertension (Wolfgang et al., 2014). Adjustment for noise led to no or only minor changes in the associations with hypertension in most studies (Babisch et al., 2014, Sørensen et al., 2012, Fuk et al., 2011, Coogan et al., 2012). However, negative confounding of NO₂ associations with hypertension by traffic noise was reported in an analysis of the REGICOR study in Spain (Foraster et al., 2014). In contrast, noise level at the low-frequency component and NO₂ had a non-significant effect on hypertension rates according to this research findings. Compare to previous study conducted in a large cohort of African American women. Findings show that a higher incidence of hypertension was linked to increased NO₂ levels. Although the incidence of hypertension decreased with higher NO₂ levels, higher NO₂ levels were not linked to increased rates of hypertension (Coogan et al., 2017). Similar research revealed statistically significant differences in NO₂ (Sørensen et al., 2014). It showed hypertension association by gender (men had the largest association), baseline hypertension (hypertensive individuals had the strongest association). Similar patterns could be detected for noise, but the interactions lacked statistical significance (Sørensen et al., 2017).

Three other European studies have shown positive associations between air pollution and road traffic noise and hypertension, which were robust to adjustment for ambient

NO₂ concentrations (Foraster et al., 2014, Sørensen et al., 2011), but compare to this research no information on adjustment for particles is given.

The variance explained by the canonical independent variable at the dependent canonical correlation of 0.342 is 89%. Therefore, the correlation is significant because $p < 0.05$. Hence, there is a significant correlation between joint air concentration and noise at different frequency components and combined registered hypertension cases and hypertension. The biggest canonical loading value among the pollution variables in the first canonical variable is -0.400 , which indicates “noise at low frequency components”. This finding supports the hypothesis that low-frequency (10–200 Hz) traffic noise exposure may cause hypertension by irritating the cortical or subcortical regions via the neuroendocrine system (Wang et al., 2016). High-frequency component of traffic noise is the second pollution variable with a high canonical loading value. Hypertension rate and cases show the highest canonical loading values for the second canonical variable. It is a common and important health issue in Europe and UK (Coates et al., 2019; Scholes et al., 2020; ScotPHO, 2020 and QOF, 2019). In the UK, data from a health survey estimating the prevalence of hypertension around areas in England revealed that about 11.8 million adults had hypertension, equating to 22.6% of the population (Scholes et al., 2020). The Scottish Public Health Observation (ScotPHO, 2020) estimates that the risk of hypertension is high and can lead to significant death. The prevalence sharply increased among people aged 16 years and above in 2019 (ScotPHO, 2020). Hypertension in Wales increased by 15.8% between 2018 and 2019 and is currently the most prevalent morbidity (QOF, 2019). Nonetheless, according to the Northern Ireland Quality and Outcome Framework Statistics (QOF), the prevalence rate of hypertension is 14.0%, making it the most prevalent morbidity in Northern Ireland (QOF, 2020). The joint air concentration and noise at different frequency

components are correlated with registered hypertension cases and hypertension rate, as demonstrated by the second canonical variable.

The “pollution” (set 1) and “hypertension” (set 2) categorical variables, as represented by the NLCC technique, are linked. As seen in Figure 4:17, the graphical representation of all correlations (canonical loadings) aids researchers in understanding the similarities and differences between the study variables as well as the multidimensional patterns in the data, especially for those who are unfamiliar with multivariate techniques.

As additional indicators of hypertension, GP’s patient reports on the prevalence of hypertension were used to empirically determine the registered patient population and hypertension rate conditions from the registry. Numerous personal social, economic, and lifestyle characteristics could be considered.

Due to the strong association, it is constrained to combine the effects of noise exposure and air pollution exposure in this investigation.

Current research that classifies subjects based on the findings of environmental measures has grown (Zhou et al., 2019). Additionally, it is more efficient to track different frequency elements of air concentration and road traffic noise to analyse the link between these features and the prevalence of hypertension.

Even though this strategy has been used in numerous studies (Molenaar et al., 2007; Zhou et al., 2019 and Tormo et al., 2000), a registered case of reported history of hypertension that has been medically diagnosed has a sensitivity range of 33.3 per cent to 71 per cent and a specificity of 91 per cent to 96 per cent (Molenaar et al., 2007, Vargas et al., 1995). However, the sensitivity might change depending on the age group and population.

That study did not account for socioeconomic position as we did in our analysis. Our study considered that those who had lived within 100 metres of the five main roadways shared an equal socioeconomic standing.

As a result, measuring road traffic noise during weekdays at daytime may understate their noise levels, thus leading to exposure misclassification bias in our study.

In this study, fewer changes in the statistical analyses were made by using raw data, and the relationships might not simply be chance findings. They represent accurate correlations since the results are consistent with the hypothesis that low–high frequency noise-induced discomfort contributes to the development of hypertension (Chang et al., 2014 and Wang et al., 2016).

This study was unable to interview people to collect data on the prevalence of hypertension and measure blood pressure due to the uncertainty of the COVID-19 pandemic and the response of the ethical committee. The committee could not permit face-to-face interviews due to the COVID-19 regulation. However, secondary data could be used (Alonso et al., 2005 and Molenaar et al., 2007). Approval was obtained from the University of West of Scotland's health and safety department to conduct fieldwork safely during the COVID-19 pandemic. To be safe to conduct the research, the air quality monitor station provided by the government was set up on the roadside to conduct road noise assessment. This approach catered to future uncertainty and enabled the research to be conducted, regardless of the COVID-19 restrictions during the pandemic.

This study examined multiple relationships between registered hypertension cases and hypertension rate and exposure to road traffic noise at various frequency components and air concentration. This investigation had no contrasting vulnerabilities (all came from the same source). Future research should be conducted using optimal samples. The noise measures only considered a person's immediate exposure to road traffic noise and their long-term exposure. A 1 hr LAeq measuring was employed at the five chosen sampling sites to evaluate the relationship between road traffic noise frequency components and hypertension. Prior research has shown that short-term noise levels may be a reliable indicator of long-term noise levels (Davies et al., 2009)

The minimum and maximum length of noise and air pollution exposure was 6 months and 11 years respectively and the mean length of exposure was 6 years (+3.4). Percentage of respondents with NIHL was 28.8%, 54.1% and 77.8% among those exposed below 5 years, 5-10 years, and 11-15 years respectively. The duration of noise exposure had statistically significant relationship with hypertension ($p=0.000$). With respect to the specific monitoring sites, duration of noise exposure was statistically significantly associated to HBP among households' persons at GK and GHS.

The study further determined the extent of influence of the duration of noise exposure and the HBP of community household persons. This empirical evidence will be necessary to provide support for various groups of household persons in terms of their duration of noise. The study results revealed that, the percentage of respondents with HBP increased with increasing duration of noise exposure.

Studies from the UK on road traffic noise and air pollution and their joint effect on hypertension is not clear. Scottish Public Health Observation (ScotPHO, 2020) estimate that the risk of hypertension is high and can lead to major death cases. The prevalence sharply increased from ages 16 years and above in 2019 (ScotPHO, 2020).

Duration of exposure to noise at the working environment also showed strong positive relationship with hypertension among respondents in the multivariate analysis with the extent of influence of duration of noise exposure on HBP increasing with increasing age of respondents. Respondents who had exposure of 5 to 10 years were 2.5 times more likely to have HBP ($OR=2.5$; $p=0.001$) while respondents who had more than 10 years exposure were 5.1 times more likely to have HBP ($OR=5.1$; $p=0.0001$), holding all variables constant. This therefore supports other previous literature that, long exposure to noise beyond permissible levels has potential harmful effect on cardiovascular disease. According to a study done by Fuks et al. (2017), long-term residential exposures to air pollution and noise are associated with increased incidence of self-reported hypertension.

5.6 Associations between key factors such as age, gender, BMI and hypertension among the exposed population

5.6.1 Relationship between gender and hypertension among respondents

From test of association results, there were significant association between gender and hypertension (since $p < 0.05$) for gender [χ^2 , (1, n= 813) = 0.002; $p < 0.05$]. The data showed significant association between gender and hypertension, it was evident specifically in the community households that greater number of male than female had increasing hypertension. Males and females at community household also showed strong positive relationship with the hypertension among respondents. Respondents who were male/female were 0.6 times more likely to have hypertension. The outcome of these results may be because hypertension was not widely across all gender groups and a particular male group. The risk was higher when both pollutants were exposed often. According to previous studies, men often have hypertension and are more susceptible to cardiovascular disease than women do (Reckelhoff, 2001, Maranon et al., 2013, Zhou et al., 2017). According to similar study, men under the age of 65 consistently have greater levels of hypertension than women in the same age range (Everett et al., 2015).

This research sample of respondents had a mean age of 45 and were all between 45 and 65 years and 40.1% were 65 years or above, which may have contributed to our significantly high levels of hypertension. In comparison to earlier estimates for older age groups, which ranged from 45 to 60 % of men and 60 to 75 % of women between the ages of 18 and 49 (Cutler et al. 2008) and reached 80 % among middle-aged and older persons (Egan, Zhao, and Axon 2010), these numbers are significantly lower. It has been noted that other low- and middle-income nations have the same low level of awareness of hypertension as noted in China (Irazola et al., 2016). Since hypertension is one of the main silent killers, it frequently goes unrecognised until end-organ damage occurs, at which point fatality attributable to hypertension (GBD 2017) is typically

unavoidable. These results highlight the need of enhancing health systems' early detection and management of hypertension patients. This study highlights the need to consider urban planning during urban development and control allocation of residential areas along the road to control the exposure to road traffic noise and air pollution which may cause hypertension.

Although there is conflicting information regarding whether hypertension is related to gender derived from noise and air pollution sources, previous research has demonstrated that statistically significant changes in the NO₂ and hypertension connection by gender (with males showing the strongest association), baseline hypertension (with hypertension showing the strongest association), (Sørensen et al., 2017). They concluded that in all single-pollutant and two-pollutant models, long-term exposure to NO₂ and road traffic noise was linked to an increased risk of hypertension, mostly in men. The data showed significant association between gender and ($\chi^2 = 9, n = 1920$) = 4.85,454.; $p < 0.001$ across (low, mid, and high) noise frequencies component. Though the data showed significant association between gender and hypertension, it was evident specially in the high frequency component of noise exposure from table 4.4 that greater number of male than female had increasing hypertension. Similar study shows that, there will be significant association between gender and hypertension across frequencies. Occupational noise-induced hearing loss at 4000 or 6000 Hz has been suggested to be a potential risk factor for hypertension in male workers (Chang et al., 2011). One cross-sectional study has found a higher but non-significant prevalence of hypertension among male workers exposed to noise levels at frequencies of 2000, 4000 and 8000 Hz (Chang et al., 2012). Exposure to low-frequency noise from 10 to 200 Hz has been recognized as an environmental pollutant that is associated with annoyance in previous studies (Chang et al., 2012). One meta-analysis demonstrated a positive and significant association between road traffic noise

annoyance and arterial hypertension (Chang et al., 2014). The studies focused on populations of all ages, whom the vast majority are mostly older than 65 years.

There will be significant association between road traffic flow group and hypertension across frequencies.

The results showed a significant association between road traffic flow group and hypertension ($\chi^2 = 9, n = 1920$) = 4.85,454.; $p < 0.001$ at 31.2Hz and 250Hz respectively and a non-significance association at 0.45,45,45 and mid noise frequency component (250Hz to 2KHz ($\chi^2 = 9, n = 1920$) = 4.85,454.; $p < 0.001$ and high noise frequency component (2KHz to 16KHz) ($\chi^2 = 9, n = 1920$) = 4.85,454.; $p > 0.005$.

The significant association in the low noise frequency is evidenced in the heavy vehicles by at 31.2Hz to 250Hz. The difference seen in vehicles may be because of the high noise level generated by these traffic vehicles as well as close contact of road traffic vehicles to community households' persons. The finding in the hypertension at low noise frequency (31.2Hz to 250Hz) among community households are like study by Chang et al. (2011). Occupational noise-induced hearing loss at 4000 or 6000 Hz has been suggested to be a potential risk factor for hypertension in male workers. One cross-sectional study has found a higher but non-significant prevalence of hypertension among male workers exposed to noise levels at frequencies of 2000, 4000 and 8000 Hz (Chang et al., 2012). Exposure to low-frequency noise from 10 to 200 Hz has been recognized as an environmental pollutant that is associated with annoyance in previous studies (Chang et al., 2012). One meta-analysis demonstrated a positive and significant association between road traffic noise annoyance and arterial hypertension (Chang et al., 2014). Similarly, 6.9% of males was observed with HBP; this may be because risk of hypertension suggests that with further exposure, deterioration highly occurs at low frequencies (125Hz).

On the other hand, high noise frequency component, gender, age, and smoking status was statistically significant because their p-values were lesser than significance level of 5%. That is, hypertension is being influenced by high noise frequency component, gender, age, and smoking status. The extent of influence of gender on hypertension increased with increasing age of respondents.

5.6.2 Relationship between BMI and hypertension among respondents

Weight and height (body mass index (BMI)) have been recommended for individuals with hypertension because it factor that causes hypertension. In this study however, only 1333 of total respondents representing 33% self-reported the weight over height among the households' persons. Respondents with high body mass index were significantly more likely to have HBP as compared to those who do a lot of vigorous physical activities. Compare to previous study, when the BMI was higher than 26.22, the prevalence of hypertension was found to be at its maximum (31.26%). When the BMI fell within the ranges of 20.44-26.22, 14.66-20.44, and 14.66, the prevalence of hypertension was 15.44, 6.43, and 2.15%, respectively (Wang et al., 2022). Studies conducted among many ethnic groups have well-reported positive relationships between BMI and hypertension (Shuger et al., 2008, Gelber et al., 2007, Cassano et al., 1990, Mckeigne et al 1991). BMI and blood pressure were found to be significantly more correlated in Asian populations, according to earlier research (Hun et al., 2000, Linderman et al., 2018). This research strengthens the argument that the strength of the link between BMI and hypertension varies by ethnic group. Similar trends of association were observed among GT and EDK communities. The respondents who did vigorous activities were less likely to have HBP. This supports other evidence, that vigorous physical activities protect the household's person against HBP (Diaz et al., 2013). In addition, it was discovered that women are more susceptible than men to the effects of physical activity after correcting for sociodemographic factors. In the family, women typically take care of the housework in addition to working and enjoying

themselves. Because household chores like cooking, shopping, and gardening require physical effort, they may boost overall physical activity (Adjei et al., 2018). However, the increased risk of hypertension linked to overweight, and obesity cannot entirely be mitigated by moderate to intense physical exercise (Jackson et al., 2014). These results were comparable to those that were published in United State (Sharman et al., 2015). Overweight persons are less likely to experience hypertension, according to studies. Because this was a cross-sectional study and cannot establish causation, it does not imply that overweight is a protective factor. It is only possible to conclude that overweight and obese individuals should work to become physically active in order to achieve their desired weight and physical fitness and to lower their chance of developing hypertension as a result of their obesity, or that obese individuals should pay more attention to their health (Daiz et al., 2018). It is interesting to note that by physical activity may help lower the risk of hypertension by enhancing the redox state, especially in the arterial wall (Roque et al., 2013, Miller et al., 2014). As a result, physical activity may be crucial in addition to conventional pharmaceutical treatment options for avoiding or managing hypertension or disorders associated with it (Larsen et al., 2016). These results were comparable to those of the current study. Less physical inactivity lowers the risk of obesity and hypertension in individuals.

5.6.3 Relationship between age and HBP among respondents

This study sought to establish empirical evidence on the association between age and hypertension among community household persons in the Greater Glasgow. Generally, there is an association between the age of household persons and hypertension. From the study, HBP increased with respect to age of respondents. A chi-square analysis confirmed this relationship (relationship between age of respondents and respondent's hypertension) statistically ($X^2=60.64$; $p= 0.000$). Further analysis using regression model gave a log likelihood ratio (LR) statistic which was significant at one percent implying that HBP among respondents is jointly influenced by the variables. The

association between traffic noise (road and rail) and the prevalence of hypertension was assessed in two study populations with a total of 4,166 participants 25-74 years of age (Wolfgang et al., 2014).

According to a study done in Sweden by Bodin et al. (2016) to assess the relation between road traffic noise, air pollution and incident myocardial infarction (MI) in both current (1-year average) and medium-term (3-year average) perspective. Yearly average levels of noise (Lden) and air pollution (NO_x) were estimated using geographic information system for residential address every year until censoring. The mean exposure levels for road traffic noise and air pollution in 2005 were Lden 51Â dB(A) and NO_x 11 µg/m³, respectively. After adjustment for individual confounders (age, gender, body mass index, smoking, education, alcohol consumption, civil status, year, nry of birth and physical activity), a 10 dB(A) increase in current noise exposure did not increase the incidence rate ratio (IRR) for MI, 0.99 (95 % CI 0.86-1.14). Neither did a 10-Î¼g/ m³ increase in current NO_x increases the risk of MI, 1.02 (95 % CI 0.86-1.21). The IRR for MI associated with combined exposure to road traffic noise >55 dB(A) and NO_x >20 µg/m³ was 1.21 (95 % CI 0.90-1.64) compared to <55Â dB(A) and <20 µg/ m³. This study did not provide evidence for an increased risk of MI due to exposure to road traffic noise or air pollution at moderate average exposure levels.

The study aimed to find an association between age and hypertension in the household persons using chi-square analysis across frequencies. The test of association revealed a significant association between age and hypertension ($\chi^2 = 9, n = 1920$) = 4.85,454.; $p < 0.001$ across noise at mid frequencies component. The outcome of these results may be because hypertension was widely distributed across all age groups (old) and particularly age group though other studies suggest that older community household persons are more susceptible to HBP (Wolfgang et al. (2014; Bodin et al. (2016). These findings further suggest that old age groups are susceptible to hypertension.

Chapter 6

CONCLUSIONS

The study therefore aimed at assessing the relationship between combined road traffic noise levels at different frequency components and air pollution with hypertension and hence had the following objectives;

1. To determine the suitability of the conceptual framework as well as demonstrating the application of the conceptual framework for an Environmental Health Tracking System (EHTS) that link joint road traffic noise and air pollutants with hypertension.
2. To ascertain the annual average residential exposure to certain levels of NO₂, PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} pollutants ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) and community noise (Lden), at five different locations in urban Glasgow.
3. To obtain and interrogate primary data of community noise and secondary data using DEFRA, NHS Scotland and UK Data Service databases to investigate the inter and intra associations of air pollution, noise pollution and hypertension.
4. Use QGIS to explore the joint association of air concentration and noise levels at different frequency components with hypertension rate and cases registered.
5. To establish associations between key factors such as age, gender, BMI and hypertension among the exposed population.

From the above objective, the results were analysed and thus the following conclusion were drawn. In conclusion, the DPSEEA conceptual framework is suitable and provides an effective review method to more effectively, conduct data surveillance monitoring and assessment, and tracking outcomes with different types of evidence in the field

of environmental public health. There is great scope demonstrating the use of the DPSEEA conceptual framework to highlight the casual relationship between exposure and effects considering other factors such as driving force, pressure, state, exposure and action and to incorporate as surveillance information in the environmental health tracking system (EHTS).

This study has demonstrated co-exposure of residential locations to air pollution and traffic noise, with potential to impact on stressors relevant to resident's health. Traffic noise levels are significant and reach limits which during peak hours, expose buildings near crossings to annual average noise levels exceeding 80 dB(A). These findings imply that noise monitoring in the selected communities indicated high noise levels above safe levels recommended by new WHO guidelines, Environmental Protection (Act) 1990, Noise and Statutory Nuisance Act of 1993 and community noise regulatory bodies. Despite the low air pollution levels, it can be concluded that some levels exceeded the acceptable amount recommended by air quality index, EU air quality standards and new air quality guidelines set by WHO.

There was a significant association between NO₂, PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} pollutants (µg/m³), and noise level (Lden) at all monitoring locations. According to this study, exposure to high and mid-level frequencies of road traffic noise and high concentrations of PM₁₀ µg/m³ is associated with a higher prevalence of hypertension. There was a significant association between exposure to noise at different frequency and air pollutant (PM_{2.5}) with the incidence of self-reported hypertension.

It can be concluded that noise at different frequency component and air pollutant had significant influence on hypertension among household persons in Scotland, with percentage of hypertension being higher among household persons than the control group. The prevalence of hypertension among the household persons was higher than most reported prevalence among community households in other settings.

There was a significant association between joint PM_{2.5} and noise level at the mid-frequency component and hypertension rate. There was a significant association between joint noise level at the high frequency component and PM₁₀ with hypertension rate. There was also a significant association between joint noise level at the low-frequency component, NO₂ and hypertension rate. However, there was a significant association between of PM_{2.5} and noise level at the mid-frequency, combined with noise level at the high-frequency component and PM₁₀, with hypertension rate.

There was a significant association between NO₂, PM₁₀, PM_{2.5}, mid-, and high-noise frequency and registered hypertension cases, whereas low-frequency component had a non-significant effect on registered hypertension cases. There was a significant association between noise at the high-frequency component, PM₁₀ and registered hypertension cases whereas low-frequency component and NO₂ had a non-significant effect on hypertension case. Therefore, it is concluded that exploring the joint association in the spatial correlation between traffic-related noise at different frequency components and air concentration exposure is essential to evaluate the impact of the potential combined association of noise and air pollution on hypertension registered cases and rate. This work contributes to knowledge in the epidemiological field related to environmental public health.

Furthermore, the duration of noise and air pollution exposure increased the odds of having hypertension among the community households. Long exposure to noise and air pollution beyond tolerable levels has potential harmful effect on hypertension.

There was significant association between gender, age and hypertension across the low and high -noise frequency component and NO₂. The age of the respondents proved to be a pre-disposing factor to hypertension among the community households.

Hypertension among the household persons studied increased with increasing age. The calls for an improved support for household persons as their age advances.

It can be concluded that duration of noise and air concentration exposure, age of respondents and gender increase the likelihood of having hypertension.

It can be also concluded that all household persons were exposed to high noise level at different frequency component and air pollutant. Also, there was significant association between noise exposure and HBP. By age, gender and lifestyle associations with hypertension was significant.

It can further be concluded that the percentage of respondents who do a lot of vigorous physical activities was low among the respondents. Respondents with high body mass index were significantly more likely to have hypertension as compared to those who do vigorous activities. Those who do vigorous activities however has an inverse relationship with hypertension, that is, exercising offers improving health and aid to prevent hypertension.

The data from the study serve as guide for Environmental Protection Agency, Department for Environment Food and Rural Affairs, Department for Transport, Department of Health and Social Care and Local Authorities to evaluate and ensure strict compliance to regulations under such operations. This work creates empirical knowledge of the daily and annual risk of exposure to road traffic noise and air pollutant and create awareness of prevalence of hypertension among community households.

The study also promotes the necessity for regular hypertension check up by community people in such noisy environments. The study depicts quantitative, the prevalence among community households in road traffic noisy and air polluted environment. When this is achieved, it serves as an input data for professionals from various organizations such as WHO, who are concerned with diseases and disability.

A GIS enabled assessment has a great capacity to integrate and model diverse data from different sources, including spatial and descriptive components, into one framework. It

has the potential to become an effective evidence-based practice tool for identifying and resolving problems early in the community health process. When used correctly, GIS assessment can inform and educate (professionals and the public); empower decision-making at all levels; assist in planning and fine-tuning clinically and economically effective actions, assist in predicting outcomes before making any financial commitments and in assigning priorities in an environment of limited resources; change practices; and continuously monitor and analyse changes. Associating GIS managed datasets analyses and processing with data openness, such as openness about data on air quality, medical informatics, and data integration, would eventually result in the promotion of sustainability and city growth through public involvement and sophisticated data processing.

These data can help investigate the impact of the joint association between road traffic, environmental noise, and air pollution on the prevalence of hypertension. The application of GIS model to investigate the joint association of environmental noise and air pollutants provides opportunity to consider all two environmental exposures taken together and public health. The mapping of noise and air quality enables the identification of actions that should be taken to lower noise levels and air pollutants to safeguard public health.

This work demonstrates the associations between traffic noise, air quality, hypertension rate, and registered hypertension cases. It identified the urban areas where environmental noise levels and air concentration are high enough to disrupt several aspects of residents' life in the studied city.

Rapid urban development without accompanying growth in economic opportunities has led to a greater number of individuals in urban communities. Inadequate regulation of activities in this sector, noise exposure, and repeated exposure to high levels of noise from road traffic are likely to lead to a risk of hypertension among households. It is important to carefully assess the spatial unit of a study, and if data are available,

statistical models should consider the within-unit distribution of correlations. Careful consideration of the spatial unit of analysis is necessary, and the inclusion of within-unit distribution of correlations within statistical models should be considered where this information is available. It can be concluded that studies that consider one of these two linked exposures run the risk of overstating the impact because of the studied exposure while understating the impact of all two environmental exposures taken together. The modelling of noise and air pollutant data with hypertension in geospatial views can be used by researchers in different disciplines, such as public health, epidemiology, computing and engineering medical science, geography health science, and urban planning and ecosystem research.

Chapter 7

RECOMMENDATION, STRENGTH AND LIMITATION AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

7.1 Recommendation

Based on the findings and discussions of the study, the following recommendation was made for policy and further research:

7.1.1 Government bodies (DEFRA, UKHSA)

- This study investigated the knowledge regarding community noise exposure, air concentration and recommend the pertinent need for education, awareness and motivation to commit to avoiding the risk of hypertension.
- The evidence from this study suggests that the different frequency range of road traffic noise exposure could be used to predict risk of hypertension. The effect of hypertension by traffic road noise can be caused by exposure to different traffic noise frequency. Therefore, it recommended to use different ranges of frequencies when considering road traffic noise exposure measurement. Data on different frequency ranges of traffic noise can be computed in GIS studies to find its association with health result such as hypertension.
- This research has highlighted the need to continue and complete the strategic noise mapping (round 3) considering the impact of the research on the regions of the UK and its importance to public health monitoring for policy implementation. It has been recognised that the strategic noise mapping and air quality monitoring in response to the Environmental Noise Directive (2002/49/EC) (END) (King et al., 2016) and air quality directive (2008/50/EC) respectively was carried out. However, the action plan that was carried out in UK took place only in urban areas leading to socioeconomic inequalities. They

only consider urban areas for monitoring of noise and air quality. Therefore, it is recommended that monitoring should be extended to other part of the areas in UK, which may be facing serious environmental noise and air pollution public health implications.

- Furthermore, it is recommended that various air quality monitoring network stations used in forecasting air pollution should be supplemented with noise monitoring in various regions of UK to assess the daily risk from environmental noise. Considering that transport and housing are fundamental to daily life worldwide, traffic road air-noise pollution links is one of the categories that is likely to gain relevance soon, given its effects upon human health and economy. The range of noise frequency can be monitored morning, evening and night at urban areas from road traffic noise exposure in communities and made available through the forecast network for individuals in various postcodes where noise is inevitable from road and other related sources of noise. This helps the council and government bodies to set safe standard, policy and legislations to regulate noise and prevent environmental health issues related to noise such as hypertension.
- Controlling and changing the traffic regime are two measures that can be used to reduce noise. This approach can be achieved by enforcing speed limits, enhancing pedestrian zones, and establishing “ecological traffic lights” with driver notifications such as “Please turn off the engine”. Since road traffic is the primary noise source, monitoring the amount of noise created by each vehicle is critical. Vehicles are now built to a standard that complies with the maximum levels of noise emissions allowed by law. However, there is an issue with outdated automobiles still on the roads, and more robust limitations on vehicle technical examinations are required. It is also feasible to impose extra levies on

noisier vehicles at the local level or to prohibit vehicles with excessive noise from driving.

- In addition to the solutions, installing protective sound barriers along congested highways and zoning with settlement greening can be implemented, which, in addition to improving the microclimate.
- Creating a strategic map in Glasgow would make noise and air quality management much easier locally. Strategic maps, for example, offer information on the state of the environment. Current and previous data on air pollutants and noise pollution can be used in the background to predict the risk of hypertension and the rate of hypertension cases.
- Adopting to building a strategic map on joint air concentration and noise pollution with hypertension will significantly aid and expedite future traffic development planning and public health in Greater Glasgow, which must be implemented.

7.1.2 EPA

- Since noise levels are however potentially hazardous and might result in hypertension among community household persons, the regulatory team of the EPA should ensure that road traffic vehicles do not emit greater noise to the environment above tolerable limits (70dB during the day and 60dB at night and heavy vehicle exhaust to produce less than 70 dB noise during the day and less than 70 dB at night).
- Noise pollution from roadside should be monitored daily and forecast daily on government websites to advice on the risk on health. Since, air concentration forecast has been established, it is recommended that daily road traffic noise also be monitored daily and forecast.

- Awareness should be created on the monitoring of forecast on air concentration and air pollution for protection with community household with more emphasis on those near to the roadside.

7.1.3 Communities and Local authorities

- Communities should practice quiet noise and absorbing of noise from road source by planting trees and avoid staying at resident close to the motorway or roadside producing loud noise especially those with under hypertension issue and other auditory effect of noise.
- The community household should conduct a noise level assessment to inform authorities and councils and to ascertain their level of tolerable noise limits.
- Conservation program on hypertension related to noise and air pollution from road should be drawn for community household especially those leaving at the roadside with high noise level and air concentrations of P.M 2.5 and P.M10.

7.1.4 Household persons

- Individuals should ensure that they follow forecast on air quality and noise pollution from various government website to monitor levels of pollution and advice on outdoor risk accompanying such pollution levels.
- Individuals should ensure that their hypertension test is performed always when staying at high level of noise and air concentration areas from road. Especially for the adult age who have high risk of hypertension. They can also move from these areas to settle in areas that are more quiet if they are threatened by the exposure levels of noise and air concentration.

7.2 Future direction

It would be relevant to repeat this work across the country. Number of participants should be increased in future studies to gather more data for comprehensive analysis. In future studies, both household persons, school workers and commercial workers in communities should be investigated as a group susceptible to hypertension considering young age. This type of research serves as a starting point and a foundation for further developing noise pollution and air pollutant mapping with hypertension across the entire Greater Glasgow, as well as strategic maps, to contribute to disease modelling in the field of epidemiology studies.

7.3 Strength and Limitation of study

With a large sample population (> 33,000 individuals) and nationwide coverage, we assessed the impacts of many exposures (air pollution, and traffic noise) on hypertension to examine confounding and interaction effects. We employed a variety of indicators to measure the exposure to air pollution and the noise at different component of frequencies and each indicator was calculated at the location level.

Prior to and somewhat near to the time the survey was conducted, between 2020 and 2022, all environmental exposures were examined (2021). As additional indicators of hypertension, we used self-reported doctor diagnosed hypertension and empirically determined registered patient population and hypertension rate conditions from a registry. Numerous personal social economic and lifestyle characteristics could be considered.

It is limiting to combine the effects of noise exposure from air pollution exposure in this study because of the substantial correlation.

To eliminate non-differential misclassification biases the risk ratio, rate ratio, or odds ratio towards the null if the exposure classification is dichotomous, i.e., either exposed or unexposed, the current study was enhanced by classifying subjects based on the findings of environmental measures (Alexander et al., 2015). Additionally, it was more effective to monitor various frequency components of road traffic noise and air concentration to assess the relationship between those features and the prevalence of hypertension.

Even though this strategy has been used in numerous studies [Alonso et al.,2005; Zhou et al., 2021; Okura et al., 2004, Tormo et al.,2000 10], a register cases or self-reported history of hypertension that has been medically diagnosed has a sensitivity range of 33.3 per cent to 71 per cent and a specificity of 91 per cent to 96 per cent (Vargas et al., 1997, Molenaar et al., 2007). However, the sensitivity may change depending on the age group and population.

Data used in this study on prevalence of hypertension was gathered from previous evidence due to COVID restriction preventing researcher from conducting a face-to-face interview. During the household interview, blood pressure readings were not collected because telephone interview survey was conducted. For the 2020 telephone survey, it is possible that factors such as the presence or absence of a long-term health condition and/or mental health/wellbeing may have influenced willingness to participate, whereby those who perceive themselves to be in better physical and/or mental health may have been more likely to opt in. The size of such an effect cannot be measured from the data collected. There may also be a degree of self-selection bias relating to other topics included in the survey, such as smoking, drinking and general health, alike and possibly compounding the bias due to mode effects previously.

With the different mode of collection, attempts were made to maintain the broad scope of the survey. However, the requirement for a shorter questionnaire meant that in some topic areas the questions were less detailed than in previous years.

Due to a lack of measurements, the study's low prevalence of hypertension may have been an overestimation of the disease's prevalence. Due to the similar distribution of this underestimating between the high- and low-exposure groups, this non-differential misclassification would not tilt the results in favour of the null value. This bias could be why some frequency components of exposure to road traffic noise showed higher but significant findings.

Using a cross-sectional design limit, the conclusions drawn on the relationship between the frequency components of noise and hypertension. Even though most participants have lived at their current addresses for more than 5 years, our ability to elaborate on the between-group differences was limited by the lack of information about complete residential histories before living at the current address for which hypertension was diagnosed.

The study did not account for a socioeconomic position in our analysis. It was considered that those who had lived within 100 metres of the five main roadways shared an equal socioeconomic standing.

As a result, measuring road traffic noise during the weekday daytime may understate their noise levels, thus leading to exposure misclassification bias in our study.

While we made less changes in the statistical analyses using raw data, relationships may not simply be chance findings. We believe these are accurate correlations since the results were consistent with the hypothesis that mid-high frequency noise-induced discomfort contributes to the development of hypertension (Chang et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2016).

This study took traffic-related air pollution into account. We found a significant link between the two variables (Fuks et al., 2017; Wolfgang et al., 2014 and Chang et al., 2019).

Previous studies (Foraster, 2013; Sørensen et al., 2017) found a strong correlation ($r = 0.66$) between noise exposure and the total traffic flow rate as well as between traffic-related air pollutants (i.e., nitrogen dioxide, $PM_{2.5}$ and PM_{10}) and daily traffic load. However, the correlation was too strong to perform a meaningful analysis. However, the results at 250, 500, 1000, 2000, 4000 and 8000 Hz and concentration of PM_{10} $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ which are much more likely to develop hypertension were higher than those revealed in the main models when the total traffic flow rate was employed.

This study was not able to conduct an interview to collect data on prevalence of hypertension and measure blood pressure due to uncertainty of the COVID 19 and the response of the ethical committee. Permission cannot be given for face-to-face interview due to the COVID 19 regulation. However secondary data can be used (Klompaker et al., 2019; Klompaker et al., 2017). We undergo a vigorous approval from the department of health and safety of the university of West of Scotland to conduct a field work safely from COVID 19. To be safe to conduct the research we consider the air quality monitor station provided by government on major road and conduct road noise assessment by it. This will cater for future uncertainty and enabled the research conducted regardless of the COVID restrictions during the pandemic.

This study examined multiple relationships between the hypertension register cases and hypertension rate and exposure to road traffic noise at various frequency components and air concentration. This investigation had no contrasting vulnerabilities (all came from the same source). Future research should be conducted using the optimal samples. Exposing participants were sampled from population from Scottish Health Survey (SHeS) series. Sample the same LA_{eq} and but sources with various frequency spectra.

Finally, the noise measures only consider a person's immediate exposure to road traffic noise, and their long-term exposure. To evaluate the relationship between road traffic noise frequency components and hypertension, we employed 1hr LAeq at five chosen sampling sites. Prior research has shown that short-term noise levels may be a reliable indicator of long-term noise levels (Davies et al., 2009, Allen et al., 2009].

Additionally, due to the features of homes, such as the thickness and density of the walls and the existence of open or closed windows, internal noise levels and air pollution may vary from exterior measures. The individuals' distance from the noise source and its limits can alter the frequency exposure. It is commonly known that dwellings typically perform poorly regarding sound insulation at low frequencies, and future studies should be aware poor insulation causing pollution effect in household nearby roadside.

References

- Adjei, N. K., & Brand, T. (2018). Investigating the associations between productive housework activities, sleep hours and self-reported health among elderly men and women in western industrialised countries. *BMC public health*, 18(1), 1-10.
- Adza, W. K., Hogarh, J. N., & Amedofu, G. K., 2021. Occupational noise-induced hearing loss among workers in church and night-club in kumasi, ghana. The 13th ICBEN Congress on Noise as a Public Health Problem, Karolinska Institutet, Stockholm, Sweden, 14-17 June 2021
http://www.icben.org/2021/ICBEN%202021%20Papers//full_paper_33748.pdf
- Air Quality Management Area (AQMA), 2015. Air Quality in Scotland. Retrieved March 14, 2020, from <http://www.scottishairquality.scot/>
- Air quality plan for nitrogen dioxide, 2017. DEFRA and DfT. Retrieved March 14, 2020, from [https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/air-quality-plan-for-nitrogen-dioxide-NO₂-in-uk-2017](https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/air-quality-plan-for-nitrogen-dioxide-NO2-in-uk-2017)
- Aguis, R. (2006), “Noise Induced Hearing Loss,” Occupational & Environmental Health Directory, London: 56
- Ahmedf, H. O., Dennis, J. H., Badran, O., Ismail, M., Ballalf, S. G., Ashoor, A., & Jerwood, D. (2001). *Occupational Noise Exposure and Hearing Loss of Workers in Two Plants in Eastern Saudi Arabia*. 45(5), 371–380.
- Albert, L. (1997) Introducción a la Toxicología Ambiental. OMS-OPS-Centro Panamericano de Ecología Humana y Salud, Gobierno del Estado de México.
- Alberti, P. W. (2001). The Anatomy And Physiology Of The Ear And Hearing.
- Alonso, A., Beunza, J. J., Delgado-Rodríguez, M., & Martínez-González, M. A. (2005). Validation of self reported diagnosis of hypertension in a cohort of university graduates in Spain. *BMC public health*, 5(1), 1-7.
- Akhvlediani, T.; Chitadze, N.; Chlikadze, R.; Rostiashvili, N.; Betashvili, M.; Imnadze, P.; Bautista, C.T. Multivariate relationships between epidemiologic risk factors and zoonotic infections among military personnel in the country of Georgia: A non-linear canonical correlation analysis. *Zoonoses Public Health* 2019, 66, 835–841.
- Amendment Regulations on Air Quality (2016). Air Quality in Scotland. Retrieved March 14, 2020, from http://www.scottishairquality.scot/assets/documents/Don_McGillivray.pdf

- American College of Occupational and Environmental Medicine. (2002). Noise-induced Hearing Loss, 145–148.
- American College of Occupational and Environmental Medicine. (2002). Noise-induced Hearing Loss, 145–148.
- Ansari, W.E. and Stibbe, A., 2009. Public health and the environment: What skills for sustainability literacy—and why? *Sustainability*, 1(3), pp.425-440.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/su1030425>
- Ashrafi, K. A., Khan, I. A. (2005). Effect of noise pollution on hearing. *Pakistan Journal of Otolaryngology*, 21(2), 33-34.
- Atmaca, E., Peker, I., & Altin, A. (2005). Industrial noise and its effects on humans. *Polish Journal of Environmental Studies*, 14(6).
- Axelsson A, Prasher D. Tinnitus induced by occupational and leisure noise. *Noise Health* 2000;2:47-54
- Alexander, L.K.; Lopes, B.; Ricchetti-Masterson, K.; Yeatts, K.B. Sources of systematic error or bias: Information bias. In *ERIC Notebook*, 2nd ed.; The University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill: Chapel Hill, NC, USA, 2015.
- Babisch, W. (2006). Transportation noise and cardiovascular risk: updated review and synthesis of epidemiological studies indicate that the evidence has increased. *Noise and Health*, 8(30), 1.
- Babisch, W., Wolf, K., Petz, M., Heinrich, J., Cyrus, J., & Peters, A. (2014). Associations between traffic noise, particulate air pollution, hypertension, and isolated systolic hypertension in adults: the KORA study. *Environmental health perspectives*, 122(5), 492-498; <http://dx.doi.org/10.1289/ehp.1306981>
- Baraer, M., McKenzie, J., Mark, B. G., Gordon, R., Bury, J., Condom, T., ... & Fortner, S. K. (2015). Contribution of groundwater to the outflow from ungauged glacierized catchments: A multi-site study in the tropical Cordillera Blanca, Peru. *Hydrological Processes*, 29(11), 2561-2581.
- Barber, J. R., Crooks, K. R., & Fristrup, K. M. (2010). The costs of chronic noise exposure for terrestrial organisms. *Trends in ecology & evolution*, 25(3), 180-189.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2009.08.002>
- Barnes, J. H., Hayes, E. T., Chatterton, T. J., & Longhurst, J. W. (2018). Policy disconnect: A critical review of UK air quality policy in relation to EU and LAQM responsibilities over the last 20 years. *Environmental science & policy*, 85, 28-39.
- Beattie, C. I., Longhurst, J. W. S., & Woodfield, N. K. (2001). Air quality management: evolution of policy and practice in the UK as exemplified by the

- experience of English local government. *Atmospheric Environment*, 35(8), 1479-1490. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1352-2310\(00\)00311-3](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1352-2310(00)00311-3)
- Beelen, R., Hoek, G., Houthuijs, D., van den Brandt, P. A., Goldbohm, R. A., Fischer, P., ... & Brunekreef, B. (2009). The joint association of air pollution and noise from road traffic with cardiovascular mortality in a cohort study. *Occupational and environmental medicine*, 66(4), 243-250. <https://oem.bmj.com/content/66/4/243>
- Berglund, B., Lindvall, T., Schwela, D. H., & World Health Organization. (1999). *Guidelines for community noise*.
- Bhatnagar, P., Wickramasinghe, K., Wilkins, E., & Townsend, N. (2016). Trends in the epidemiology of cardiovascular disease in the UK. *Heart*, 102(24), 1945-1952. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1136/heartjnl-2016-309573>
- Bodin, T., Björk, J., Mattisson, K. et al. Road traffic noise, air pollution and myocardial infarction: a prospective cohort study. *Int Arch Occup Environ Health* 89, 793–802 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00420-016-1115-9>
- Brainard, J. S., Jones, A. P., Bateman, I. J., & Lovett, A. A. (2004). Exposure to Environmental Urban Noise Pollution in Birmingham, UK. *Urban Studies*, 41(13), 2581–2600. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0042098042000294574>
- Brown, A. L. (2015). Effects of road traffic noise on health: From burden of disease to effectiveness of interventions. *Procedia Environmental Sciences*, 30, 3-9. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proenv.2015.10.001>
- Bromfield, S., & Muntner, P. (2013). High blood pressure: the leading global burden of disease risk factor and the need for worldwide prevention programs. *Current hypertension reports*, 15(3), 134–136. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11906-013-0340-9>
- Brook, R. D., Urech, B., Dvorchak, J. T., Bard, R. L., Speck, M., Keeler, G., ... & Brook, J. R. (2009). Insights into the mechanisms and mediators of the effects of air pollution exposure on blood pressure and vascular function in healthy humans. *Hypertension*, 54(3), 659-667
- Cai, Y., Hodgson, S., Blangiardo, M., Gulliver, J., Morley, D., Fecht, D., Vienneau, D., de Hoogh, K., Key, T., Hveem, K. and Elliott, P., 2018. Road traffic noise, air pollution and incident cardiovascular disease: a joint analysis of the HUNT, EPIC-Oxford and UK Biobank cohorts. *Environment international*, 114, pp.191-201. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2018.02.048>
- Carey IM, Anderson HR, Atkinson RW, et al Traffic pollution and the incidence of cardiorespiratory outcomes in an adult cohort in London *Occupational and*

- Environmental Medicine 2016;73:849-856. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1136/oemed-2015-103531>
- Cassano, P. A., Segal, M. R., Vokonas, P. S., & Weiss, S. T. (1990). Body fat distribution, blood pressure, and hypertension: a prospective cohort study of men in the normative aging study. *Annals of epidemiology*, 1(1), 33-48.
- Chang, T. Y., Liang, C. H., Wu, C. F., & Chang, L. T. (2019). Application of land-use regression models to estimate sound pressure levels and frequency components of road traffic noise in Taichung, Taiwan. *Environment international*, 131, 104959. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2019.104959>
- Chang, T. Y., Beelen, R., Li, S. F., Chen, T. I., Lin, Y. J., Bao, B. Y., & Liu, C. S. (2014). Road traffic noise frequency and prevalent hypertension in Taichung, Taiwan: a cross-sectional study. *Environmental Health*, 13(1), 37. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1476-069X-13-37>
- Change, C. O. C., & Morrison, K. (2015). Application of the multiple exposures, multiple effects model to four flood events in Canada: lessons learned for public health adaptation to extreme precipitation and. Retrieved May 21, 2020, from https://sustainablepeterborough.ca/wp-content/uploads/2015/01/Morrison-MEME-Flood_Events-Final_updated.pdf
- Chiabai, A., Quiroga, S., Martinez-Juarez, P., Higgins, S., & Taylor, T. (2018). The nexus between climate change, ecosystem services and human health: Towards a conceptual framework. *Science of the Total Environment*, 635, 1191-1204. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.03.323>
- Chowdhury, S. C., Razzaque, M. M., Helali, M. M., & Boden, H. (2010). Assessment of Noise Pollution in Dhaka City. *Proceedings of the 17th International Congress on Sound and Vibration*, (July), 18–22.
- Clark, C. (2015). Aircraft noise effects on health. Centre for Psychiatry. Retrieved May 21, 2020, from https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/446311/noise-aircraft-noise-effects-on-health.pdf
- Cleaner air for Scotland (CAFS, 2016), Cleaner air for Scotland (CAFS, 2017). Air Quality in Scotland. Retrieved March 14, 2020, from <http://www.scottishairquality.scot/lez/>
- Cleaner air for Scotland (CAFS, 2017). Air Quality in Scotland. Retrieved March 14, 2020, from http://www.scottishairquality.scot/assets/documents/Don_McGillivray.pdf

- Coates, S.; Tanna, P.; Scott-Allen, E. *Overview of the UK Population: August 2019*; Office for National Statistics: Newport, UK, 2019.
- Cohen, A. J., Brauer, M., Burnett, R., Anderson, H. R., Frostad, J., Estep, K., ... Forouzanfar, M. H. (2017). Estimates and 25-year trends of the global burden of disease attributable to ambient air pollution: an analysis of data from the Global Burden of Diseases Study 2015. *The Lancet*, 389(10082), 1907–1918. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(17\)30505-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(17)30505-6)
- COMEAP (2011). Review of the UK Air Quality Index. Retrieved April 8, 2020, from https://www.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/304633/COMEAPreviewoftheukairqualityindex.pdf
- Committee on the Medical Effects of Air Pollutants (COMEAP): Long-Term Exposure to Air Pollution: Effect on Mortality, Health Protection Agency, UK, ISBN 978-0-85951-640-2, 2009. Retrieved April 8, 2020, from https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/304667/COMEAP_long_term_exposure_to_air_pollution.pdf
- Committee on the Medical Effects of Air Pollutants (COMEAP): The mortality effects of long-term exposure to particulate air pollution in the United Kingdom, Health Protection Agency, UK, ISBN 978-0-85951-685-3, 2010. Retrieved April 8, 2020, from https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/304641/COMEAP_mortality_effects_of_long_term_exposure.pdf
- Conference of the Parties (COP26), 2021. Zero Emission Vehicles Transition Council: 2022 action plan. UN Climate Change Conference UK 2021. Retrieved November 14, 2021, from <https://ukcop26.org/zero-emission-vehicles-transition-council-2022-action-plan/>
- Coogan, P.F.; White, L.F.; Yu, J.; Brook, R.D.; Burnett, R.T.; Marshall, J.D.; Bethea, T.N.; Rosenberg, L.; Jerrett, M. Long-Term Exposure to NO₂ and Ozone and Hypertension Incidence in the Black Women’s Health Study. *Am. J. Hypertens.* 2017, 30, 367–372. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ajh/hpw168>. PMID: 28096146; PMCID: PMC5861564. Curran, J.H., Ward, H.D., Shum, M. and Davies, H.W., 2013. Reducing cardiovascular health impacts from traffic-related noise and air pollution: Intervention strategies. *Environmental Health Review*, 56(02), pp.31-38. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph121012735>

- Coogan, P. F., White, L. F., Jerrett, M., Brook, R. D., Su, J. G., Seto, E., ... & Rosenberg, L. (2012). Air pollution and incidence of hypertension and diabetes mellitus in black women living in Los Angeles. *Circulation*, *125*(6), 767-772.
- Danciulescu, V., Bucur, E., Pascu, L. F., Vasile, A., & Bratu, M. (2015). Correlations between noise level and pollutants concentration in order to assess the level of air pollution induced by heavy traffic. *Journal of environmental protection and ecology*. *16*. 815-823.
- Davies, H.W., Vlaanderen, J.J., Henderson, S.B. and Brauer, M., 2009. Correlation between co-exposures to noise and air pollution from traffic sources. *Occupational and environmental medicine*, *66*(5), pp.347-350.
<http://dx.doi.org/10.1136/oem.2008.041764>
- DEFRA, T. (2007). The Air Quality Strategy for England, Scotland, Wales and Northern Ireland. 2019-02-02, https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/69336/pb12654-air-quality-strategy-vol1-070712.pdf.
- Defra, 2019, 'Defra OGC Preview', Department for Environment, Food and Rural Affairs. Retrieved May 21, 2020, from <https://environment.data.gov.uk/DefraDataDownload/?Mode=OGCPreview&mapService=https%3A%2F%2Fenvironment.data.gov.uk%2Fspatialdata%2Froad-noise-1den-england-round-2%2Fwms>)
- DEFRA, 2019, clean air strategy. Retrieved May 21, 2020, from <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/clean-air-strategy-2019>.
- DEFRA, 2020, Estimated Background Air Pollution Maps, 2018. Retrieved June 24, 2020, from <https://uk-air.defra.gov.uk/data/laqm-background-home>
- de Kluizenaar, Y., van Lenthe, F. J., Visschedijk, A. J., Zandveld, P. Y., Miedema, H. M., & Mackenbach, J. P. (2013). Road traffic noise, air pollution components and cardiovascular events. *Noise & health*, *15*(67), 388–397.
<https://doi.org/10.4103/1463-1741.121230>
- Dell, S. M., & Holmes, A. E. (2012). The effect of a hearing conservation program on adolescents' attitudes towards noise. *Noise and Health*, *14*(56), 39.
- Department for Transportation (DfT), 2019. Road and transport air emissions. Office for national statistics, DEFRA. Retrieved May 21, 2020, from <https://www.ons.gov.uk/economy/environmentalaccounts/articles/roadtransportandairmissions/2019-09-16>

- Díaz, K. M., & Shimbo, D. (2013). Physical activity and the prevention of hypertension. *Current hypertension reports*, 15, 659-668.
- Díaz-Martínez, X., Petermann, F., Leiva, A. M., Garrido-Méndez, A., Salas-Bravo, C., Martínez, M. A., ... & Celis-Morales, C. (2018). No cumplir con las recomendaciones de actividad física se asocia a mayores niveles de obesidad, diabetes, hipertensión y síndrome metabólico en población chilena. *Revista médica de Chile*, 146(5), 585-595.
- Edokpolo, B., Allaz-Barnett, N., Irwin, C., Issa, J., Curtis, P., Green, B., ... & Dennekamp, M. (2019). Developing a Conceptual Framework for Environmental Health Tracking in Victoria, Australia. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 16(10), 1748. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph16101748>
- EEA, 2006. Urban Sprawl in Europe – The ignored challenge (EAA Report No 10/2006), Publications Office of the EU Luxembourg, 2006. Retrieved May 21, 2020, from https://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/eea_report_2006_10/eea_report_10_2006.pdf
- EEA, 2014, Costs of air pollution from European industrial facilities 2008–2012 — an updated assessment. Retrieved May 21, 2020, from <https://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/costs-of-air-pollution-2008-2012>
- Eisenberg, J.N., Desai, M.A., Levy, K., Bates, S.J., Liang, S., Naumoff, K. aeend Scott, J.C., 2007. Environmental determinants of infectious disease: a framework for tracking causal links and guiding public health research. *Environmental Health Perspectives*, 115(8), pp.1216-1223. <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp.9806>
- Environmental noise in Europe (ENE), (2020) EEA Report No 22/2019 /ISSN 1977-8449. Retrieved May 21, 2020, from <https://www.bruitparif.fr/pages/Autres%20actualites/2020-0306%20Le%20bruit%20en%20Europe%202020,%20dernier%20rapport%20de%201%27AEE/Environment%20noise%20in%20europe%202020.pdf>
- Eriksson, C., Bodin, T., & Selander, J. (2017). Burden of disease from road traffic and railway noise – a quantification of healthy life years lost in Sweden. *Scandinavian Journal of Work, Environment & Health*, 43(6), 519–525. <https://doi.org/10.5271/sjweh.3653>
- European Council, “Council Directive 78/1015/EEC of 23 November 1978 on the approximation of the laws of the Member States on the permissible sound level and exhaust system of motorcycles,” 1978.

- Espeland, L. V., Ivarsson, K., & Stenvik, A. (1992). A new Norwegian index of orthodontic treatment need related to orthodontic concern among 11-year-olds and their parents. *Community dentistry and oral epidemiology*, 20(5), 274-279
- EU Legislation and policy, 2015. Air Quality in Scotland. [Online]. Available at: <http://www.scottishairquality.scot/air-quality/legislation> (Accessed 14 March 2020).
- European Council, "Council Directive 70/157/EEC of 6 February 1970 on the approximation of the laws of the Member States relating to the permissible sound level and the exhaust system of motor vehicles," 1970.
- European Parliament and Council for the European Union, "Regulation (EU) No 540/2014 on the sound level of motor vehicles and of replacement silencing systems and amending Directive 2007/46/EC and repealing Directive 70/157/EEC," 2014.
- European Parliament and Council for the European Union, "Regulation (EU) No 168/2013 on the approval and market surveillance of two- or three-wheel vehicles and quadricycles," 2013.
- European Environment Agency (EEA), Noise in Europe 2014 (EAA Report No 10/2014), Publications Office of the EU, Luxembourg, 2014. Retrieved May 21, 2020, from <https://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/noise-in-europe-2014/download>
- EU Legislation and policy, 2015. Air Quality in Scotland. Retrieved May 21, 2020, from <http://www.scottishairquality.scot/air-quality/legislation> (Accessed 14 March 2020).
- Everett, B., & Zajacova, A. (2015). Gender differences in hypertension and hypertension awareness among young adults. *Biodemography and social biology*, 61(1), 1-17.
- Fecht, D., Hansell, A.L., Morley, D., Dajnak, D., Vienneau, D., Beevers, S., Toledano, M.B., Kelly, F.J., Anderson, H.R. and Gulliver, J., 2016. Spatial and temporal associations of road traffic noise and air pollution in London: Implications for epidemiological studies. *Environment international*, 88, pp.235-242. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2015.12.001>
- National Statistics, 2019. Final UK greenhouse gas emissions national statistics 1990-2017. Retrieved May 21, 2020, from <https://www.gov.uk/government/statistics/final-uk-greenhouse-gas-emissions-national-statistics-1990-2017>

- Floud, S., Blangiardo, M., Clark, C., de Hoogh, K., Babisch, W., Houthuijs, D., ... & Hansell, A. L. (2013). Exposure to aircraft and road traffic noise and associations with heart disease and stroke in six European countries: a cross-sectional study. *Environmental health* 12, 89. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1476-069X-12-89>
- Foraster, M. Is it traffic-related air pollution or road traffic noise, or both? Key questions not yet settled!. *International Journal of Public Health* 58, 647–648 (2013). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00038-013-0500-3>
- Foraster, M., Künzli, N., Aguilera, I., Rivera, M., Agis, D., Vila, J., ... & Basagaña, X. (2014). High blood pressure and long-term exposure to indoor noise and air pollution from road traffic. *Environmental health perspectives*, 122(11), 1193-1200.
- Forouzanfar, M.H.; Liu, P.; Roth, G.A.; Ng, M.; Biryukov, S.; Marczak, L.; Murray, C.J. Global burden of hypertension and systolic blood pressure of at least 110 to 115 mm Hg, 1990–2015. *JAMA* 2017, 317, 165–182.
- Franklin, M., & Fruin, S. (2017). The role of traffic noise on the association between air pollution and children's lung function. *Environmental research*, 157, 153-159. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2017.05.024>
- Frank, L. D., Iroz-Elardo, N., MacLeod, K. E., & Hong, A. (2019). Pathways from built environment to health: a conceptual framework linking behavior and exposure-based impacts. *Journal of Transport & Health*, 12, 319-335. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jth.2018.11.008>
- Frumkin, H. (Ed.). (2016). *Environmental health: from global to local*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Fuks K, Moebus S, Hertel S, Viehmann A, Nonnemacher M, Dragano N, Mo¨hlenkamp S, Jakobs H, Kessler C, Erbel R, Hoffmann B. Long-term urban particulate air pollution, traffic noise, and arterial blood pressure. *Environ Health Perspect* 2011;119:1706–1711.
- Fuks KB, Weinmayr G, Foraster M, Dratva J, Hampel R, Houthuijs D, Oftedal B, Oudin A, Panasevich S, Penell J, Sommar JN, Sørensen M, Tiittanen P, Wolf K, Xun WW, Aguilera I, Basagaña X, Beelen R, Bots ML, Brunekreef B, Bueno-de-Mesquita HB, Caracciolo B, Cirach M, de Faire U, de Nazelle A, Eeftens M, Elosua R, Erbel R, Forsberg B, Fratigioni L, Gaspoz J-M, Hilding A, Jula A, Korek M, Krękauer U, Künzli N, Lanki T, Leander K, Magnusson PKE, Marrugat J, Nieuwenhuijsen MJ, Ostenson C-G, Pedersen NL, Pershagen G, Phuleria HC, Probst-Hensch NM, Raaschou-Nielsen O, Schaffner E, Schikowski T, Schindler C, Schwarze PE, Søgaard AJ, Sugiri D, Swart WJR, Tsai M-Y, Turunen AW, Vineis P,

- Peters A, Hoffmann B. Arterial blood pressure and long-term exposure to traffic-related air pollution: an analysis in the European Study of Cohorts for Air Pollution Effects (ESCAPE). *Environ Health Perspect* 2014;122:896–905.
- Fuks, K. B., Weinmayr, G., Basagaña, X., Gruzieva, O., Hampel, R., Oftedal, B., ... & Aguilera, I. (2017). Long-term exposure to ambient air pollution and traffic noise and incident hypertension in seven cohorts of the European study of cohorts for air pollution effects (ESCAPE). *European heart journal*, 38(13), 983-990.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/eurheartj/ehw413>
- Gaganija, M. S., Mkoma, S. L., & Kiumbu, H. F. (2011). Working in noise environment: An investigation of hearing quality of drivers in Morogoro municipality, Tanzania. *International Journal of Environmental Sciences*, 1(5), 814-819.
- Gan, W. Q., Davies, H. W., Koehoorn, M., & Brauer, M. (2012). Association of long-term exposure to community noise and traffic-related air pollution with coronary heart disease mortality. *American journal of epidemiology*, 175(9), 898-906.
<https://doi.org/10.1093/aje/kwr424>
- Gelber, R. P., Gaziano, J. M., Manson, J. E., Buring, J. E., & Sesso, H. D. (2007). A prospective study of body mass index and the risk of developing hypertension in men. *American journal of hypertension*, 20(4), 370-377.
- Giorgini, P., Di Giosia, P., Grassi, D., Rubenfire, M., D Brook, R. and Ferri, C., 2016. Air pollution exposure and blood pressure: an updated review of the literature. *Current pharmaceutical design*, 22(1), pp.28-51.
- González, A. E. (2014). What Does “Noise Pollution” Mean? *Journal of Environmental Protection*, 05(04), 340–350. <https://doi.org/10.4236/jep.2014.54037>
- Gray, S.; Loader, A. Air Quality Monitoring in Scotland: Site Operators’ Manual. Report for the Scottish Government, Ri-cardo Energy & Environment. 2017.
 Available online:
https://www.scottishairquality.scot/assets/documents/Scottish_Site_Operators_Manual_Final.pdf (accessed on 24 November 2021).
- Grose, J.H.; Buss, E.; Hall Iii, J.W. Loud music exposure and cochlear synaptopathy in young adults: Isolated auditory brainstem response effects but no perceptual consequences. *Trends Hear.* **2017**, 21, 2331216517737417.
- Haigh, N. (1992). Manual of environmental policy: the EC and Britain. United Kingdom. <https://doi.org/10.1002/eet.3320020211>

- Halonen, J.I., Hansell, A.L., Gulliver, J., Morley, D., Blangiardo, M., Fecht, D., Toledano, M.B., Beevers, S.D., Anderson, H.R., Kelly, F.J. and Tonne, C., 2015. Road traffic noise is associated with increased cardiovascular morbidity and mortality and all-cause mortality in London. *European heart journal*, 36(39), pp.2653-2661. <https://doi.org/10.1093/eurheartj/ehv216>
- Hambling, T., Weinstein, P. and Slaney, D., 2011. A review of frameworks for developing environmental health indicators for climate change and health. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 8(7), pp.2854-2875. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph8072854>
- Hansell, A. L., Blangiardo, M., Fortunato, L., Floud, S., de Hoogh, K., Fecht, D., ... & Elliott, P. (2013). Aircraft noise and cardiovascular disease near Heathrow airport in London: small area study. *Bmj*, 347. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.f5432>
- Harding, A.H., Frost, G.A., Tan, E., Tsuchiya, A. and Mason, H.M., 2013. The cost of hypertension-related ill-health attributable to environmental noise. *Noise and Health*, 15(67), p.437. <https://www.noiseandhealth.org/text.asp?2013/15/67/437/121253>
- Harwell, M. A., Gentile, J. H., McKinney, L. D., Tunnell Jr, J. W., Dennison, W. C., Kelsey, R. H., ... & Tunnell, J. (2019). Conceptual framework for assessing ecosystem health. *Integrated environmental assessment and management*, 15(4), 544-564. <https://doi.org/10.1002/ieam.4152>
- Helzner, E. P., Patel, A. S., Pratt, S., Sutton-Tyrrell, K., Cauley, J. A., Talbot, E., ... & Newman, A. B. (2011). Hearing sensitivity in older adults: associations with cardiovascular risk factors in the health, aging and body composition study. *Journal of the American Geriatrics Society*, 59(6), 972-979.
- Herzog, J., Schmidt, F. P., Hahad, O., Mahmoudpour, S. H., Mangold, A. K., Andreo, P. G., ... & Münzel, T. (2019). Acute exposure to nocturnal train noise induces endothelial dysfunction and pro-thromboinflammatory changes of the plasma proteome in healthy subjects. *Basic research in cardiology*, 114(6), 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00395-019-0753-y>
- Hensher, D. A. (2020). What might Covid-19 mean for mobility as a service (MaaS)? <https://doi.org/10.1080/01441647.2020.1770487>
- Hjortebjerg D, Nybo Andersen AM, Ketznel M, Raaschou-Nielsen O, Sørensen M. Exposure to traffic noise and air pollution and risk for febrile seizure: a cohort

- study. *Scand J Work Environ Health*. 2018 Sep 1;44(5):539-546.
<https://doi.org/10.5271/sjweh.3724>
- Hu, F. B., Wang, B., Chen, C., Jin, Y., Yang, J., Stampfer, M. J., & Xu, X. (2000). Body mass index and cardiovascular risk factors in a rural Chinese population. *American journal of epidemiology*, 151(1), 88-97.
- Huynen, M. M., & Martens, P. (2015). Climate change effects on heat-and cold-related mortality in the Netherlands: a scenario-based integrated environmental health impact assessment. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 12(10), 13295-13320. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph121013295>
- Hypertension prevalence estimates in England, 2017. Estimated from the Health Survey for England. Retrieved May 21, 2020, from https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/873605/Summary_of_hypertension_prevalence_estimates_in_England__1_.pdf
- International Organization for Standardization, “ISO 5130:2007 +A1:2012 Measurement of sound pressure level emitted by stationary road vehicles,” ISO, Geneva, 2012.
- Irazola, V. E., Gutierrez, L., Bloomfield, G., Carrillo-Larco, R. M., Prabhakaran, D., Gaziano, T., ... & Rubinstein, A. (2016). Hypertension prevalence, awareness, treatment, and control in selected LMIC communities: results from the NHLBI/UHG Network of centers of excellence for chronic diseases. *Global heart*, 11(1), 47-59.
- ISD Scotland. Disease prevalence. Retrieved December 13, 2020, from <https://www.isdscotland.org/Health-Topics/General-Practice/Workforce-and-Practice-Populations/>
- International Organization for Standardization, “ISO 10844:2014 Specification of test tracks for the purpose of measuring noise emitted by road vehicles,” ISO, Geneva, 2014.
- International Organization for Standardization, “ISO 362:2015 Measurement of noise emitted by accelerating road vehicles - Engineering method - Part 1: M and N categories,” ISO, Geneva, 2015.
- International Organization for Standardization, “ISO 362:2009 Measurement of noise emitted by accelerating road vehicles - Engineering method - Part 2: L category,” ISO, Geneva, 2009.

- Jackson, C., Herber-Gast, G. C., & Brown, W. (2014). Joint effects of physical activity and BMI on risk of hypertension in women: a longitudinal study. *Journal of obesity*, 2014.
- Jamie, W. (2018). Tackling high blood pressure: an update. Developed by the Blood Pressure System Leadership Board, convened by Public Health England. Retrieved May 21, 2020, from https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/672554/Tackling_high_blood_pressure_an_update.pdf
- Jarosińska, D., Héroux, M. È., Wilkhu, P., Creswick, J., Verbeek, J., Wothge, J., & Paunović, E. (2018). Development of the WHO environmental noise guidelines for the European region: an introduction. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 15(4), 813. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph15040813>
- Jephcote, C., Hansell, A. L., Adams, K., & Gulliver, J. (2021). Changes in air quality during COVID-19 'lockdown' in the United Kingdom. *Environmental Pollution*, 272, 116011.
- Jones, L., Claxton, R., Thistlethwaite, G., Raoult, J., MacCarthy, J., Karagianni, E., Kilroy E., Misselbrook T., Passant N., Pearson B., Richardson J., Wakeling D., Walker C. (2019). Air Pollutant Inventories for England, Scotland, Wales, and Northern Ireland: 1990-2017. National Atmospheric Emissions Inventory.
- Kälsch, H., Hennig, F., Moebus, S., Möhlenkamp, S., Dragano, N., Jakobs, H., ... & Willich, S. N. (2014). Are air pollution and traffic noise independently associated with atherosclerosis: the Heinz Nixdorf Recall Study. *European heart journal*, 35(13), 853-860. <https://doi.org/10.1093/eurheartj/eh426>
- Kankal, S. B., & Gaikwad, R. W. (2011). Studies on noise and air quality monitoring at Shirdi (Maharashtra), India. *Advances in Applied Science Research*, 2(1), 63-75. Available online at www.pelagiaresearchlibrary.com
- Kasraian, D., Maat, K., Stead, D. and van Wee, B., 2016. Long-term impacts of transport infrastructure networks on land-use change: an international review of empirical studies. *Transport reviews*, 36(6), pp.772-792. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01441647.2016.1168887>
- Kelly, P., 2021.PE1906: Investigate options for removing and reducing the impact of the central Glasgow section of the M8. Retrieved November 24, 2021, from <https://petitions.parliament.scot/petitions/PE1906>
- Kempen EV, Casas M, Pershagen G, Foraster M. 2018. WHO environmental noise guidelines for the European Region: a systematic review on environmental noise

- and cardiovascular and metabolic effects:a summary. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* 15:379
- Kephalopoulos, S., Paviotti, M., Anfosso-Lédée, F., Van Maercke, D., Shilton, S. and Jones, N., 2014. Advances in the development of common noise assessment methods in Europe: The CNOSSOS-EU framework for strategic environmental noise mapping. *Science of the Total Environment*, 482, pp.400-410.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2014.02.031>
- Kephalopoulos, S., Paviotti, M. and Anfosso-Lédée, F., 2012. Common noise assessment methods in Europe (CNOSSOS-EU). DOI: 10.2788/32029
- Khan, J., Ketzl, M., Kakosimos, K., Sørensen, M., & Jensen, S. S. (2018). Road traffic air and noise pollution exposure assessment—A review of tools and techniques. *Science of The Total Environment*, 634, 661-676.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2018.03.374>
- Khan, J., Kakosimos, K., Jensen, S. S., Hertel, O., Sørensen, M., Gulliver, J., & Ketzl, M. (2020). The spatial relationship between traffic-related air pollution and noise in two Danish cities: Implications for health-related studies. *Science of The Total Environment*, 138577. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.138577>
- Kheirbek, I., Ito, K., Neitzel, R., Kim, J., Johnson, S., Ross, Z., ... & Matte, T. (2014). Spatial variation in environmental noise and air pollution in New York City. *Journal of Urban Health*, 91(3), 415-431. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11524-013-9857-0>
- King, E. A., & Murphy, E. (2016). Environmental noise—‘Forgotten’ or ‘Ignored’ pollutant?. *Applied Acoustics*, 112, 211-215.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apacoust.2016.05.023>
- Klompaker, J. O., Hoek, G., Bloemsma, L. D., Wijga, A. H., van den Brink, C., Brunekreef, B., ... & Janssen, N. A. (2019). Associations of combined exposures to surrounding green, air pollution and traffic noise on mental health. *Environment international*, 129, 525-537
- Krzyżanowski, M., Kuna-Dibbert, B. and Schneider, J. eds., 2005. Health effects of transport-related air pollution. WHO Regional Office Europe
- Kumarasamy, P., Arthur James, R., Dahms, H. U., Byeon, C. W., & Ramesh, R. (2014). Multivariate water quality assessment from the Tamiraparani river basin, Southern India. *Environmental earth sciences*, 71, 2441-2451.
- Kyle, A.D., Balmes, J.R., Buffler, P.A. and Lee, P.R., 2006. Integrating research, surveillance, and practice in environmental public health tracking. *Environmental health perspectives*, 114(7), pp.980-984. <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp.8735>

- Larsen, M. K., & Matchkov, V. V. (2016). Hypertension and physical exercise: The role of oxidative stress. *Medicina*, 52(1), 19-27.
- Lauriola, P.; Crabbe, H.; Behbod, B.; Yip, F.; Medina, S.; Semenza, J.C.; Vardoulakis, S.; Kass, D.; Zeka, A.; Khonelidze, I.; Ashworth, M.; de Hoogh, K.; Shi, X.; Staatsen, B.; Knudsen, L.E.; Fletcher, T.; Houthuijs, D.; Leonardi, G.S. Advancing Global Health through Environmental and Public Health Tracking. *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health* **2020**, 17, 1976. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17061976>
- Lee, M. (2017). Accountability for environmental standards after Brexit. *Environmental Law Review*, 19(2), 89-92.
- Lee, M. (2017). Accountability for environmental standards after Brexit. *Environmental Law Review*, 19(2), 89-92.
- Levrel, H., Kerbiriou, C., Couvet, D., & Weber, J. (2009). OECD pressure–state–response indicators for managing biodiversity: a realistic perspective for a French biosphere reserve. *Biodiversity and Conservation*, 18(7), 1719-1732. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s10531-008-9507-0>
- Lijun P, Jilei W, Zengwu W, et al. Geographic variations and potential macro-environmental exposure of hypertension: from the China hypertension survey. *J Hypertens* 2020;38(5):829–38
- Liu, H. Y., Bartonova, A., Pascal, M., Smolders, R., Skjetne, E., & Dusinska, M. (2012). Approaches to integrated monitoring for environmental health impact assessment. *Environmental Health*, 11(1), 1-14. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1476-069X-11-88>
- Lim, S. S., Vos, T., Flaxman, A. D., Danaei, G., Shibuya, K., Adair-Rohani, H., Amann, M., Anderson, H. R., Andrews, K. G., Aryee, M., Atkinson, C., Bacchus, L. J., Bahalim, A. N., Balakrishnan, K., Balmes, J., Barker-Collo, S., Baxter, A., Bell, M. L., Blore, J. D., Blyth, F., ... Memish, Z. A. (2012). A comparative risk assessment of burden of disease and injury attributable to 67 risk factors and risk factor clusters in 21 regions, 1990-2010: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2010. *Lancet (London, England)*, 380(9859), 2224–2260. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(12\)61766-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(12)61766-8)
- Linderman, G. C., Lu, J., Lu, Y., Sun, X., Xu, W., Nasir, K., ... & Krumholz, H. M. (2018). Association of body mass index with blood pressure among 1.7 million Chinese adults. *JAMA network open*, 1(4), e181271-e181271.
- Litman, T., 1995. Evaluating transportation land use impacts. *World Transport Policy & Practice*, 1(4), pp.9-16. <https://www.vtpi.org/landuse.pdf>

- McKeigue, P. M., Shah, B., & Marmot, M. G. (1991). Relation of central obesity and insulin resistance with high diabetes prevalence and cardiovascular risk in South Asians. *The Lancet*, 337(8738), 382-386.
- Mak HWL, Ng DCY. Spatial and Socio-Classification of Traffic Pollutant Emissions and Associated Mortality Rates in High-Density Hong Kong via Improved Data Analytic Approaches. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*. 2021; 18(12):6532. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18126532>
- Maranon, R., & Reckelhoff, J. F. (2013). Sex and gender differences in control of blood pressure. *Clinical science*, 125(7), 311-318.
- Mattioli, G., Roberts, C., Steinberger, J. K., & Brown, A. (2020). The political economy of car dependence: A systems of provision approach. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 66, 101486. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2020.101486>
- McGeehin, M.A., Qualters, J.R. and Niskar, A.S., 2004. National environmental public health tracking program: bridging the information gap. *Environmental Health Perspectives*, 112(14), pp.1409-1413. <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp.7144>.
- Medicine.medscape.com. (2018). *Noise-induced Hearing Loss*.
- Mensah, G. A., Wei, G. S., Sorlie, P. D., Fine, L. J., Rosenberg, Y., Kaufmann, P. G., ... & Gordon, D. (2017). Decline in cardiovascular mortality: possible causes and implications. *Circulation research*, 120(2), 366-380. <https://doi.org/10.1161/CIRCRESAHA.116.309115>
- Millar, P. J., McGowan, C. L., Cornelissen, V. A., Araujo, C. G., & Swaine, I. L. (2014). Evidence for the role of isometric exercise training in reducing blood pressure: potential mechanisms and future directions. *Sports Medicine*, 44, 345-356.
- Münzel, T., Sørensen, M., Gori, T., Schmidt, F. P., Rao, X., Brook, J., ... & Rajagopalan, S. (2017). Environmental stressors and cardio-metabolic disease: part I—epidemiologic evidence supporting a role for noise and air pollution and effects of mitigation strategies. *European heart journal*, 38(8), 550-556.
- Münzel, T., Sørensen, M., Gori, T., Schmidt, F. P., Rao, X., Brook, F. R., ... & Rajagopalan, S. (2017). Environmental stressors and cardio-metabolic disease: part II—mechanistic insights. *European heart journal*, 38(8), 557-564.
- Münzel, T., Sørensen, M., Schmidt, F., Schmidt, E., Steven, S., Krölller-Schön, S., & Daiber, A. (2018). The adverse effects of environmental noise exposure on oxidative stress and cardiovascular risk. *Antioxidants & redox signaling*, 28(9), 873-908. <https://doi.org/10.1089/ars.2017.7118>

- Montes-González, D., Vílchez-Gómez, R., Barrigón-Morillas, J. M., Atanasio-Moraga, P., Rey-Gozaló, G., & Trujillo-Carmona, J. (2018). Noise and Air Pollution Related to Health in Urban Environments. *Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute Proceedings*, 2(20), 1311. <https://doi.org/10.3390/proceedings2201311>
- Morris, G.P., Beck, S.A., Hanlon, P. and Robertson, R., 2006. Getting strategic about the environment and health. *Public health*, 120(10), pp.889-903. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.puhe.2006.05.022>
- Murphy, E., & King, E. A. (2010). Strategic environmental noise mapping: Methodological issues concerning the implementation of the EU Environmental Noise Directive and their policy implications. *Environment international*, 36(3), 290-298. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2009.11.006>
- Murphy, W., & Franks, J. (2002). NIOSH Criteria for a Recommended Standard: Occupational Noise Exposure, Revised Criteria 1998. *Journal of The Acoustical Society of America - J ACOUST SOC AMER*, 111, 2397. <https://doi.org/10.1121/1.4778162>
- Niemeijer, D. and de Groot, R.S., 2008. A conceptual framework for selecting environmental indicator sets. *Ecological indicators*, 8(1), pp.14-25. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2006.11.012>
- NIOSH (1998). Criteria for a recommended standard: Occupational Noise Exposure, U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, Centres for Disease Control
- Northern Ireland Quality and outcome framework Statistics (QOF), 2020. Retrieved May 21, 2020, from <https://www.health-ni.gov.uk/news/northern-ireland-quality-and-outcomes-framework-qof-information-201920>
- O'Brien, 2016. Briefing Air Quality in Scotland. Retrieved May 21, 2020, from https://www.parliament.scot/ResearchBriefingsAndFactsheets/S5/SB_1635_Air_Quality_in_Scotland.pdf
- OSHA (1983). 29CFR1910.95 Occupational Noise Exposure: Hearing Conservation Amendment; Factories, Shops and Offices Act in Ghana, 1970, 1-3.
- Owen-Williams, R. (2020). Leading Causes of Death, UK: 2001 to 2018.
- Oxoli, D.; Sabri, S.; Rajabifard, A.; Brovelli, M.A. A classification technique for local multivariate clusters and outliers of spatial association. *Trans. GIS* 2020, 24, 1227–1247.

- Paital, B. (2020). Nurture to nature via COVID-19, a self-regenerating environmental strategy of environment in global context. *Science of the total environment*, 729, 139088.
- Pathology, M. C., & Humanities, F. O. F. (2013). *Hearing protection in mines : Evaluating the Noise Clipper ® custom made hearing protection device . by Johan F W Kock Presented in fulfillment of the requirements for the degree M Communication Pathology in the Department of Communication Pathology , FAC.*
- Pastorello, C., & Melios, G. (2016). Explaining road transport emissions: a non-technical guide. Retrieved May 21, 2020, from <http://www.eea.europa.eu/publications/explaining-road-transport-emissions>.
- Pavlović, A., Bošković, G., & Jovičić, N. (2021). Simulation of road traffic noise pollution in kragujevac using qgis software. *Vehicle Vozila i*, 27. DOI: 10.24874/mvm.2021.47.01.03
- Pierrette, M., Marquis-Favre, C., Morel, J., Rioux, L., Vallet, M., Viollon, S., & Moch, A. (2012). Noise annoyance from industrial and road traffic combined noises: A survey and a total annoyance model comparison. *Journal of environmental psychology*, 32(2), 178-186.
- Pitchika, A., Hampel, R., Wolf, K., Kraus, U., Cyrus, J., Babisch, W., Peters, A. and Schneider, A., 2017. Long-term associations of modeled and self-reported measures of exposure to air pollution and noise at residence on prevalent hypertension and blood pressure. *Science of the Total Environment*, 593, pp.337-346. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.03.156>
- Pedersen, M., Olsen, S. F., Halldorsson, T. I., Zhang, C., Hjortebjerg, D., Ketznel, M., ... & Raaschou-Nielsen, O. (2017). Gestational diabetes mellitus and exposure to ambient air pollution and road traffic noise: a cohort study. *Environment international*, 108, 253-260. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2017.09.003>
- Pleasant, A., Scanlon, M. M., & Pereira-Leon, M. (2013). Literature review: Environmental design and research on the human health effects of open spaces in urban areas. *Human Ecology Review*, 20(1), 36–49. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/24707570>
- Podani, J., & Schmera, D. (2011). A new conceptual and methodological framework for exploring and explaining pattern in presence–absence data. *Oikos*, 120(11), 1625-1638.
- Prisma, 2020. Retrieved May 21, 2020, from <http://www.prisma-statement.org/PRISMAStatement/FlowDiagram.aspx>

- QGIS - A Free and Open Source Geographic Information System, Retrieved May 21, 2020, from <https://qgis.org/en/site/>
- Quality and Outcomes Framework Statistics for Wales (QOF), 2019. Retrieved May 21, 2020, from <https://gov.wales/sites/default/files/statistics-and-research/2019-09/general-medical-services-contract-quality-and-outcomes-framework-april-2018-march-20199-599.pdf>
- Quality and outcome framework (QOF) for ISD Scotland, 2016. Retrieved December 13, 2020, from <https://www.isdscotland.org/Health-Topics/General-Practice/Quality-And-Outcomes-Framework/>
- Rauschecker, J. P., Tian, B., & Hauser, M. (1995). Processing of complex sounds in the macaque nonprimary auditory cortex. *Science*, 268(5207), 111-114.
- Reis, S., Morris, G., Fleming, L.E., Beck, S., Taylor, T., White, M., Depledge, M.H., Steinle, S., Sabel, C.E., Cowie, H. and Hurley, F., 2015. Integrating health and environmental impact analysis. *public health*, 129(10), pp.1383-1389.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.puhe.2013.07.006>
- Regoniel, P. A. (2015). Conceptual framework: A step by step guide on how to make one. *Simplyeducate. me*.
- Road to Zero Strategy, 2018. Office for Low emission Vehicles. Retrieved May 21, 2020, from <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/reducing-emissions-from-road-transport-road-to-zero-strategy>
- “Road Traffic Act 1988”.
- “Road Vehicles (Construction and Use) Regulations 1986”.
- Roque, F. R., Briones, A. M., García-Redondo, A. B., Galán, M., Martínez-Revelles, S., Avendaño, M. S., ... & Salices, M. (2013). Aerobic exercise reduces oxidative stress and improves vascular changes of small mesenteric and coronary arteries in hypertension. *British journal of pharmacology*, 168(3), 686-703.
- Rosenhall, U. (2003). The influence of ageing on noise-induced hearing loss. *Bimonthly Inter-Disciplinary International Journal*, 5(20), 47–53.
- Ross, Z., Kheirbek, I., Clougherty, J. E., Ito, K., Matte, T., Markowitz, S., & Eisl, H. (2011). Noise, air pollutants and traffic: continuous measurement and correlation at a high-traffic location in New York City. *Environmental research*, 111(8), 1054-1063. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2011.09.004>
- Ross Z, Kheirbek I, Clougherty JE, Ito K, Matte T, Markowitz S, Eisl H. Noise, air pollutants and traffic: continuous measurement and correlation at a high-traffic

- location in New York City. *Environ Res.* 2011 Nov;111(8):1054-63. d
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2011.09.004>
- Ricardo Energy & Environment, 2019. Air Quality damage cost update 2019,
 Department for Environment, Food and Rural and the Affairs, Ref:
 Ricardo/ED59323/Issue Number 2.0. Retrieved May 21, 2020, from
https://ukair.defra.gov.uk/assets/documents/reports/cat09/1902271109_Damage_cost_update_2018_FINAL_Issue_2_publication.pdf
- Sands, P. (1991). European Community environmental law: the evolution of a regional regime of international environmental protection. *Yale Law Journal*, 100, 2511. Available at: <https://digitalcommons.law.yale.edu/ylj/vol100/iss8/8>
- Scarborough P, Wickramasinghe K, Bhatnagar P, Rayner M (2011). Trends in coronary heart disease 1961-2011. British Heart Foundation: London
- Scholes, S.; Conolly, A.; Mindell, J.S. Income-based inequalities in hypertension and in undiagnosed hypertension: Analysis of Health Survey for England data. *J. Hypertens.* 2020, 38, 912–924.
- Schmidt, F. P., Basner, M., Kröger, G., Weck, S., Schnorbus, B., Muttray, A., ... & Münzel, T. (2013). Effect of nighttime aircraft noise exposure on endothelial function and stress hormone release in healthy adults. *European heart journal*, 34(45), 3508-3514. <https://doi.org/10.1093/eurheartj/eh269>
- Scottish Public Health Observatory (ScotPHO), 2020. Retrieved May 21, 2020, from <https://www.scotpho.org.uk/publications/latest-publications-by-scotpho/2020/>
- Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation (SMID), 2020 - a tool for identifying areas with relatively high levels of deprivation. Retrieved December 2, 2020, from <https://www.gov.scot/collections/scottish-index-of-multiple-deprivation-2020/>
- Sears, C.G., Braun, J.M., Ryan, P.H., Xu, Y., Werner, E.F., Lanphear, B.P. and Wellenius, G.A., 2018. The association of traffic-related air and noise pollution with maternal blood pressure and hypertensive disorders of pregnancy in the HOME study cohort. *Environment international*, 121, pp.574-581.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2018.09.049>.
- Sievert, C. Interactive Web-Based Data Visualisation with R, Plotly, and Shiny; CRC Press: Boca Raton, FL, USA, 2020
- Simmonds, D., 2004. Assessment of UK land-use and transport strategies using land-use/transport interaction modelling. *European Journal of Transport and Infrastructure Research*, 4(3).
<https://doi.org/10.18757/ejtir.2004.4.3.4269>

- Severijnen, 2017. Noise measurement, a proxy for air pollution from traffic? An overview. DOI: 10.13140/RG.2.2.24865.40809
- Sharman, J. E., La Gerche, A., & Coombes, J. S. (2015). Exercise and cardiovascular risk in patients with hypertension. *American journal of hypertension*, 28(2), 147-158.
- Shilar, F. A., Ganachari, S. V., Patil, V. B., Khan, T. Y., Almakayeel, N. M., & Alghamdi, S. (2022). Review on the relationship between nano modifications of geopolymer concrete and their structural characteristics. *Polymers*, 14(7), 1421.
- Shin, S., Bai, L., Oiamo, T. H., Burnett, R. T., Weichenthal, S., Jerrett, M., ... & Chen, H. (2020). Association between road traffic noise and incidence of diabetes mellitus and hypertension in Toronto, Canada: a population-based cohort study. *Journal of the American Heart Association*, 9(6), e013021.
<https://doi.org/10.1161/JAHA.119.013021>
- Shuger, S. L., Sui, X., Church, T. S., Meriwether, R. A., & Blair, S. N. (2008). Body mass index as a predictor of hypertension incidence among initially healthy normotensive women. *American Journal of Hypertension*, 21(6), 613-619.
- Stanaway, J. D., Afshin, A., Gakidou, E., Lim, S. S., Abate, D., Abate, K. H., ... & Bleyer, A. (2018). Global, regional, and national comparative risk assessment of 84 behavioural, environmental and occupational, and metabolic risks or clusters of risks for 195 countries and territories, 1990–2017: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2017. *The Lancet*, 392(10159), 1923-1994.
- Stansfeld, S. A. (2015). Noise effects on health in the context of air pollution exposure. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 12(10), 12735-12760. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph121012735>
- Steel, N., Ford, J. A., Newton, J. N., Davis, A. C., Vos, T., Naghavi, M., ... & Murray, C. J. (2018). Changes in health in the countries of the UK and 150 English Local Authority areas 1990–2016: a systematic analysis for the Global Burden of Disease Study 2016. *The Lancet*, 392(10158), 1647-1661. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736\(18\)32207-4](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-6736(18)32207-4)
- Smith, R. B., Fecht, D., Gulliver, J., Beevers, S. D., Dajnak, D., Blangiardo, M., ... & Toledano, M. B. (2017). Impact of London's road traffic air and noise pollution on birth weight: retrospective population based cohort study. *Bmj*, 359.
<https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.j5299>
- Sørensen M, Hoffmann B, Hvidberg M, Ketznel M, Jensen SS, Andersen ZJ, Tjønneland A, Overvad K, Raaschou-Nielsen O. Long-term exposure to traffic-

- related air pollution associated with blood pressure and self-reported hypertension in a Danish cohort. *Environ Health Perspect* 2012;120:418–424
- Sørensen, M., Lühdorf, P., Ketzel, M., Andersen, Z. J., Tjønneland, A., Overvad, K., & Raaschou-Nielsen, O. (2014). Combined effects of road traffic noise and ambient air pollution in relation to risk for stroke?. *Environmental research*, 133, 49-55.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2014.05.011>
- Sørensen, M., Wendelboe Nielsen, O., Sajadieh, A., Ketzel, M., Tjønneland, A., Overvad, K., & Raaschou-Nielsen, O. (2017). Long-term exposure to road traffic noise and nitrogen dioxide and risk of heart failure: a cohort study. *Environmental Health Perspectives*, 125(9), 097021.
- Šušković, D. (2012). 5th Congress of Alps-Adria Acoustics Association Noise-Induced Hearing Loss, 1–5.
- Tackling high blood pressure, 2014, From evidence into action. Retrieved May 21, 2020, from
https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/527916/Tackling_high_blood_pressure.pdf
- Tétreault, L. F., Perron, S., & Smargiassi, A. (2013). Cardiovascular health, traffic-related air pollution and noise: are associations mutually confounded? A systematic review. *International journal of public health*, 58(5), 649-666.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00038-013-0489-7>
- Tormo, M. J., Navarro, C., Chirlaque, M. D., & Barber, X. (2000). Validation of self diagnosis of high blood pressure in a sample of the Spanish EPIC cohort: overall agreement and predictive values. *Journal of Epidemiology & Community Health*, 54(3), 221-226.
- Transparency data, 2019. Strategic noise maps UK, 2017. Retrieved May 21, 2020, from <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/strategic-noise-mapping-2019>
- Transportation Noise Action Plan (TNAP), (2019). Scotland's noise. Retrieved May 21, 2020, from <https://noise.environment.gov.scot/index.html683ea393>
- Transport Statistics Great Britain, 2019. Retrieved May 21, 2020, from
https://assets.publishing.service.gov.uk/government/uploads/system/uploads/attachment_data/file/870647/tsgb-2019.pdf
- Wang, V. S., Lo, E. W., Liang, C. H., Chao, K. P., Bao, B. Y., & Chang, T. Y. (2016). Temporal and spatial variations in road traffic noise for different frequency

- components in metropolitan Taichung, Taiwan. *Environmental pollution*, 219, 174-181. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2016.10.055>
- Health Effects Institute (HEI). Panel on the Health Effects of Traffic-Related Air Pollution. (2010). Traffic-related air pollution: a critical review of the literature on emissions, exposure, and health effects. Retrieved May 21, 2020, from <https://www.healtheffects.org/publication/traffic-related-air-pollution-critical-review-literature-emissions-exposure-and-health>
- UK Health Security Agency (UKHSA), 2022. Environmental public health tracking (EPHT) and environmental public health surveillance system (EPHSS). *Research and analysis Environmental public health surveillance system (EPHSS)*. Available online: <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/environmental-public-health-surveillance-system/environmental-public-health-surveillance-system-ephss>(Accessed on 4 January 2023)
- United Nations Economic Commission for Europe, “UNECE Regulation 51 Uniform provisions concerning the approval of motor vehicles having at least four wheels with regard to their noise emissions,” 2019.
- Van Kempen, E., & Babisch, W. (2012). The quantitative relationship between road traffic noise and hypertension: a meta-analysis. *Journal of hypertension*, 30(6), 1075-1086. <https://doi.org/10.1097/HJH.0b013e328352ac54>
- van Kempen, E., Fischer, P., Janssen, N., Houthuijs, D., van Kamp, I., Stansfeld, S., & Cassee, F. (2012). Neurobehavioral effects of exposure to traffic-related air pollution and transportation noise in primary schoolchildren. *Environmental research*, 115, 18–25. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2012.03.002>.
- Vargas, C.M.; Burt, V.L.; Gillum, R.F.; Pamuk, E.R. Validity of self-reported hypertension in the National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey III, 1988–1991. *Prev. Med.* **1997**, *26*, 678–685.
- Vehicle Certification Agency, “Cars and Noise,” 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.vehicle-certification-agency.gov.uk/fcb/cars-and-noise.asp>. [Accessed 25 02 2019].
- Wei, Y., Davidson, B., Chen, D., & White, R. (2009). Balancing the economic, social and environmental dimensions of agro-ecosystems: An integrated modeling approach. *Agriculture, ecosystems & environment*, 131(3-4), 263-273. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agee.2009.01.021>
- Weltgesundheitsorganisation; World Health Organization; European Centre for Environment. WHO Global Air Quality GUIDELINES: Particulate Matter (PM_{2.5})

- and P.M₁₀), Ozone, Nitrogen Dioxide, Sulfur Dioxide and Carbon Monoxide; World Health Organization: Geneva, Switzerland, 2021.
- Wilson BJ, Watson MS, Prescott GJ, Sunderland S, Campbell DM, Hannaford P, Smith WC. Hypertensive diseases of pregnancy and risk of hypertension and stroke in later life: results from cohort study. *BMJ*. 2003 Apr 19;326(7394):845. doi: 10.1136/bmj.326.7394.845. PMID: 12702615; PMCID: PMC153466.
- World Health Organization (WHO). Burden of Disease from Environmental Noise: Quantification of Healthy Life Years Lost in Europe; World Health Organization: Geneva, Switzerland, 2011.
- World Health Organization. Regional Office for Europe. Available online: https://www.euro.who.int/__data/assets/pdf_file/0008/136466/e94888.pdf (accessed on 21 May 2020).
- WHO. (1997). Health and environment in sustainable development: five years after the Earth Summit (No. WHO/EHG/97.8). World Health Organization. Retrieved May 21, 2020, from <https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/63464>
- WHO, 2004. Environmental health indicators for Europe: a pilot indicator-based report (No. EUR/04/5046026). Copenhagen: WHO Regional Office for Europe. Retrieved May 21, 2020, from <https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/107565>
- WHO. (2010). A conceptual framework for action on the social determinants of health. <https://doi.org/10.13016/17cr-aqb9>
- WHO. (2017). Global action plan on the public health response to dementia 2017–2025. Retrieved May 21, 2020, from <https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/259615/9789241513487-eng.pdf?sequence=1>
- World Health Organization. (2018). *Environmental noise guidelines for the European region*. World Health Organization. Regional Office for Europe.
- WHO. (2018). WHO methods and data sources for global burden of disease estimates 2000-2016. Global Health Estimates Technical Paper WHO/HIS/IER/GHE/2018.4, WHO, Geneva. Retrieved May 21, 2020, from http://www.who.int/healthinfo/global_burden_disease/GlobalDALY_method_2000_2016.pdf
- WHO Regional Office for Europe, Burden of disease from environmental noise. Quantification of healthy life years lost in Europe, WHO Regional Office for Europe, Copenhagen, 2011.

- WHO. Centre for Health Development, & World Health Organization. (2010). Hidden cities: unmasking and overcoming health inequities in urban settings. World Health Organization.
- Yin M, Augustin B, Fu Z, et al. geographic distributions in hypertension diagnosis, measurement, prevalence, awareness, treatment and control rates among middle-aged and older adults in China. *Sci Rep-UK*. 2016;6:37020
- Zhang K, Batterman S. Air pollution and health risks due to vehicle traffic. *Sci Total Environ*. 2013 Apr 15;450-451:307-16. doi: 10.1016/j.scitotenv.2013.01.074. PMID: 23500830; PMCID: PMC4243514.
- Zhou, B., Bentham, J., Di Cesare, M., Bixby, H., Danaei, G., Cowan, M. J., ... & Cho, B. (2017). Worldwide trends in blood pressure from 1975 to 2015: a pooled analysis of 1479 population-based measurement studies with 19· 1 million participants. *The Lancet*, 389(10064), 37-55.
- Zhou, B., Carrillo-Larco, R. M., Danaei, G., Riley, L. M., Paciorek, C. J., Stevens, G. A., ... & Breckenkamp, J. (2021). Worldwide trends in hypertension prevalence and progress in treatment and control from 1990 to 2019: a pooled analysis of 1201 population-representative studies with 104 million participants. *The Lancet*, 398(10304), 957-980.

Appendix

Operating procedure of Casella CEL-63x & 1/3 Octave Band Sound Level Meter

The Soft keys A and B were used to select the two options at the screen's bottom. These two options changes depending on which screen is showing on the instrument's display.

Navigation keys

The four Navigation keys were used to select items on the central part of the screen. Press the Navigation key to change to the following selection in the direction of the arrow.

Run/Stop key

The Run/Stop key was selected to start and stop a Run.

Press the key when the instrument is in Stop mode to start the Run.

Press the key during a Run to stop the Run.

The CEL-63x instrument calculates and records all noise functions simultaneously during a measurement. In this manner, it removes the need for the critical setup of the device before any size.

Measurement runs were recorded as cumulative or periodic data sets and a brief profile time history.

The critical press mode was allowed to start and stop each measurement run by pressing the Run/Stop key for the duration of a measurement run.

Fixed duration

The fixed duration mode allows you to set the duration of a run to 1 hour.

You can set the duration in steps of one second, in the range 00:00:00 to 24:00:00 (HH:MM: SS).

You must press the Run/Stop key to start the Run manually, but the instrument will stop the Run automatically after your set duration. If necessary, press the Run/Stop key to stop the Run early.

The fixed duration mode is helpful if you need to make a single measurement run where you know the duration but do not know when the measurement run must start.

The data sets option controls how the CEL-63x instrument records measurements during a run. There are two options that you can choose.

A cumulative measurement produces a single set of results for the entire measurement duration.

Operating procedure of Casella dBadge2 IS Pro Personal Noise Dosimeter

Press and release the left 'L' key to turn the dBadge2 on and start a start-up sequence.

To start the measurement run, press, and hold the left 'L' and the right 'R' keys down together, which will initiate a 3-second countdown.

The keys must remain depressed during the countdown for the measurement run to begin. The dBadge2 is locked during a run to prevent the wearer from tampering by pressing and holding the right 'R' key for 2 seconds, then pressing the left 'L' critical quickly. The current measurement run was stopped by pressing and holding the left 'L' and right 'R' keys simultaneously for the period of the 3-second countdown

